

EXAMINING THE AUDACITY OF CHARLES DARWIN'S EVOLUTIONARY THEORY ON MORALITY AND PSEUDO- CHRISTIANITY IN THE 21ST CENTURY INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

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Abstract

There has been a long-time debate on whether Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory has actually influenced Christianity, moral ethics and political thinking or not. While some opined that his book on evolution gave birth to the audacity of the present wave of moral bankruptcy and decadence in the society, others are of the view that men can live without God as his theory questioned the omniscience and the omnipotence nature of God over creation in its application. The paper pointed out how Charles Darwin's theory has shaped and changed the entire world to the level of questioning the authority of God on earth; which led to the questioning of the Holy Book, morality, fidelity and the sanctity of lives and the ethics of marriage in the modern world. To achieve these, qualitative research method was adopted in sequentially consulting secondary sources of information in the library, books, achieves, journals, newspapers, bulletins among others. The paper observed that Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory of 1859 has had a damaging influence on Christianity and morality especially among the German's scholars and soldiers like Hitler, Friedrich Ratzel, Sir Helford Mackinder, and General Karl Haushofer a general in the German army. The paper propounded the concept of mind mutation which says: the mind infinitely mutates infinitely towards the direction it progresses positively or negatively (i.e. as one continues to do same thing over and again, the mind keeps adjusting(mutating) to it infinitely be it good or bad. The paper concluded by asking: 'Will morality and Christianity be eroded and the world will not be brought to its knees with the survival of the fittest theory of Charles Darwin? Shouldn't there be accepted moral ethics, laws and justice that governs and favor all?

Keywords: Audacity, Evolutionary, Theory, Morality, Pseudo-Christianity, International Relations

Introduction

Christianity and morality and in fact, all known religion, points to the need to order society and bring about justice, fairness and equity. According to Oaikhena (2022) he rightly observed that “morality is the health of a society, that a society plagued with immorality is a sick society”. In the same vein, distinctive difference was established between human and animals with man as higher being with dominion over other creation. In trying to achieve this societal order, all known religion be it Christianity, Islam, Hinduism, Buddhism or African Traditional Religion (ATR) have at its core values; the sanctity of life, the concept of judgment after death, repentance, forgiveness, holy living, love for one another and the law of sowing and reaping which points to judgment or Karma and this birthed idealism and realism which has long history in international relations. This has also led to intentional or obvious harmful attitudes or behavior towards a party because of their identity, (e.g. race, religion, sexual orientation, etc (Oaikhena, 2022)

Today, Christianity and morality is under siege as a new world order was birthed following the several interpretations given to the publication of Charles Darwin’s evolutionary theory of (1859) that as of present, the world pattern, views, perception as to the value attached to human life has changed drastically from peace to war, love to hate, brotherliness to enmity and from moral to amoral. This could be the reason why Oaikhena and Ikhayere (2023) posit that “an underdeveloped society or country is characterized by backwardness, primitiveness, tribalism, dependency, neo-colonialism, non-liberalism, exploitation, late capitalism, lack of modern differentiated industries, state of poverty in the society, the domination of foreign capital in the hands of foreign and local bourgeoisie or local comprador, low technology, low level politics, including social and cultural development” Lest we forget we are first and foremost the children of God whose identity is love before our tribe, beliefs, religion, socialization and civilization. We own to this God some reverence, loyalty, fear and respect for from him we came and unto Him we shall all return after our sojourn on earth as contained in the two major Abrahamic religions (Christianity and Islam).

Statement of the Problem

There has been a long-time debate on whether Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory has actually influenced Christianity, moral ethics and political thinking or not. While some opined that his Book on evolution gave birth to the audacity of the present wave of moral bankruptcy and decadence in the world, others are of the view that man can live without God. Is his theory questioning the omniscience and the omnipotence nature of God over creation? Is the concept of God an illusory or abstract imagination? Can man live the way he likes as an evolving being without recourse to God? While the issues of the influence of Darwin's evolutionary theory on Christianity and morality was added at the later part of 19th century debate the issue of morality in international relation has been on even before Darwin was born as the debate on idealism and realism in international politics dates back to the classical political theorists, Thucydides (C. 460–C. 400 B.C.E).

A century and a half after the publication of *The Origin of Species*, which Darwin was skeptical to publish, it's difficult for us today to appreciate the seismic shift in attitudes that began with its publication. Most of us have grown up having been taught Darwin's theory from our elementary schools. Many people accept it unquestioningly. Few questioned the teaching of his ideas in our public schools without much ado and now its application is in almost every field of human endeavours. Today, its applications are different from what it was in (1859). Richard Weikart, head of the history department at California State University, Stanislaus, describes how some viewed the book's initial publication: In his words "A *good deal of the initial resistance to Darwinism sprang from a perceived threat to the moral order*". Adam Sedgwick, Darwin's former mentor in natural science at the University of Cambridge, expressed this fear poignantly in a letter he wrote to Darwin in (1859), shortly after reading 'The Origin of Species'. He stated, '*Passages in your book...greatly shocked my moral taste*' " (From Darwin to Hitler, 2004, p. 1); warning of the consequences of the book's publication, Sedgwick added that "*humanity, in my mind, would suffer a damage that might brutalize it, and sink the human race into a lower grade of degradation than any into which it has fallen since its written records tell us of its history*" (From Darwin to Hitler, 2004, p. 1)

Today, the moral and Christian doctrine's attack which started then has gradually gotten to a point that twenty-three (23) countries have at the moment adapted same sex marriage as against Biblical teachings and moral laws. As of June 2025, same-sex marriage is legal in many countries. In Europe we have: **Netherlands** (2001), **Belgium** (2003), **Canada** (2005), **Spain** (2005), **Norway** (2002), **Sweden** (2006), **Portugal** (2017), **Denmark** (2012), **Finland** (2017) **Ireland** (2015), **Luxembourg** (2015), **Malta** (2017), **Germany** (2017), **Iceland** (2010), **Slovenia** (2022). Among the American countries we have: **Canada** (2005), **Argentina** (2010), **United States** (2015), **Mexico** (2010), **Colombia** (2016) and **Uruguay** (2013). In Oceania, we have: **Australia** (2017) and in Africa we have **South Africa** (2006) and their defense is premised on Charles Darwin's theory of evolution.

Prior to the publication of Darwin's "*Origin of Species*" in (1859), the field of evolutionary was nearly non-existent. No sooner the book was published, evolutionary theory and its associated applications soon became the focus of intense activity, and today a vast literature, including entire periodicals exists which are devoted to this field and its various specialties. Darwin's theory of evolution based upon natural selection changed the thinking of countless fields of study from biology to anthropology. His work established that "evolution" had occurred: not necessarily that it was by natural or sexual selection but by gradual change and development. In many senses, Darwin's theories created a societal transformation. In other word, Darwin's theory consisted of two main points; i) diverse groups of animals evolve from one or a few common ancestors; ii) the mechanism by which this evolution takes place is natural selection (<https://www.sparknotes.com/biology/evolution/darwin/summary/> retrieved on 4/06/25).

By the time of Darwin's death in (1882), the fact of evolution was almost universally accepted by his contemporaries, the mechanism for this evolution. However, the theory of natural selection did not become orthodoxy until long after his death. Enthused by Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory where the world is right now, the level of moral bankruptcy could not have been imagined in the days of Charles Darwin and one wonders where the world is heading. The moral suasion of the Bible which is now being

called to question among others is what this article intends to bring to the fore in the course of this researched articles.

Purpose of the study

The study seeks to: i). Examine Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory and its impact on Christianity and morality; ii) Identify the major crusader of the war against Christianity and morality; iii) Recommend possible approach to achieving positive world order.

Charles Darwin's biography

Charles Darwin was born in Shrewsbury, Shropshire, England, on February 12, 1809, at the family home, the Mount House. He was the fifth of six children of Robert Darwin and Susannah Darwin the daughter of Wedgwood. In 1825, Darwin went to Edinburgh University to study medicine then theology, but his revulsion at the brutality of surgery led him to neglect his medical studies. In 1827, his father, unhappy that his younger son would not become a physician, enrolled him in a Bachelor of Arts course at Christ's College, University of Cambridge, which would qualify him to be a clergyman. At Cambridge, Darwin preferred riding and shooting to studying. He was later introduced to the Reverend John Stevens Henslow, professor of botany, for expert advice on beetles. Darwin subsequently joined Henslow's natural history course, becoming the "favorite pupil," known as "the man who walks with Henslow." (The Complete Work of Charles Darwin Online : <https://darwin-online.org.uk> › biography retrieved on June 12, 2025).

Inspired by Alexander von Humboldt's *Personal Narrative*, he planned to visit Madeira to study natural history in the tropics with some classmates after graduation. To prepare for this project, Darwin now joined the geology course of the Reverend Adam Sedgwick, then during the summer break worked with him at mapping strata in Wales. Darwin was surveying strata in Wales on his own when his plans to visit Madeira were dashed by a message that his intended companion had died. Before then, Henslow had recommended Darwin for the unpaid position of gentleman's companion to Robert FitzRoy, the captain of HMS *Beagle*, on a two-year expedition to chart the coastline of South America which would give Darwin valuable opportunities to develop his career as a

naturalist. His father objected to the voyage, regarding it as a waste of time, but was persuaded by Josiah Wedgwood to agree to his son's participation. This voyage became a five-year expedition that would change science dramatically. In his lifetime, Charles Darwin gained international fame as a pre-eminent scientist (The Complete Work of Charles Darwin Online: <https://darwin-online.org.uk> › biography retrieved on June 12, 2025)

However, from 1837 onwards, Darwin was repeatedly incapacitated with illnesses ranging from stomach pains, vomiting, severe boils, palpitations, trembling, and other symptoms, which particularly affected him in times of stress, when attending meetings, or dealing with controversy over his theory. While organizing *Zoology* and correcting proofs of his *Journal*, Darwin's health suffered major setbacks. On September 20, 1837, he suffered "palpitations of the heart" and left for a month of recuperation in the countryside (The Complete Work of Charles Darwin Online: <https://darwin-online.org.uk> › biography retrieved on June 12, 2025).

Upon being fully recuperated, Darwin returned home to Shrewsbury. Pondering his career and prospects, he drew up a list with columns headed "Marry" and "Not Marry." Having come down in favor of marrying, he discussed it with his father, and then went to visit his cousin Emma on July 29, 1838. Charles chose to marry his first cousin Emma Wedgwood. He did not get around to proposing, but against his father's advice he told her of his ideas on transmutation. On November 11, 1838, he returned and proposed to Emma, telling her his ideas. He eventually got married to Emma Wedgwood on 29 January, 1839 at St. Peter Anglican Church ceremony. The Darwin's had ten children, three of whom died early. These were: William Erasmus Darwin (December 27, 1839 – 1914) Anne Elizabeth Darwin (March 2, 1841 – April 22, 1851) Mary Eleanor Darwin (September 23, 1842 – October 16, 1842)Henrietta Emma "Etty" Darwin (September 25, 1843 – 1929) George Howard Darwin (July 9, 1845 – December 7, 1912) Elizabeth "Bessy" Darwin (July 8, 1847 – 1926) Francis Darwin (August 16, 1848 – September 19, 1925) Leonard Darwin (January 15, 1850 – March 26, 1943) Horace Darwin (May 13, 1851 – September 29, 1928) Charles Waring Darwin (December 6, 1856 – June 28, 1858). Several of their children suffered illness or weaknesses, and Charles Darwin's fear

that this might be due to the closeness of his and Emma's lineage was expressed in his writings on the ill effects of inbreeding and advantages of crossing.

Darwin died in Downe, Kent, England, on April 19, 1882 and buried in Westminster Abbey close to Sir William Herschel and Sir Isaac Newton (The Complete Work of Charles Darwin Online : <https://darwin-online.org.uk> › biography retrieved on June 12, 2025) .

Theoretical framework

Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory which was published in 1859 is the theoretical framework for this article. This became necessary as it is the influence of this theory that is the basis of the discussion under consideration. Considered the "father of evolutionary theory," Darwin made two contributions of enormous impact to the idea of evolution in his theory. First, Darwin marshaled substantial evidence for the theory of descent with modification, a kinematic theory that treats non-causal relations between things which deals with the pattern of evolution. The second is, Darwin's theory of natural selection. This dynamic theory that involves mechanisms and causal relationships deals with the process of evolution which consisted of two main points: (i) Diverse groups of animals evolve from one or a few common ancestors; and (ii) the mechanism by which this evolution takes place is by natural selection. <https://www.sparknotes.com/>.

Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory established that "evolution" had occurred: not necessarily that it was by natural or sexual selection but through diverse groups of animals evolving from one or a few common ancestors and that the mechanism by which this evolution takes place is by natural selection and had nothing to do with God or man. These claims negate the biblical teachings of God being the author of life. By the time of Darwin's death in 1882, the fact of evolution was almost universally accepted by his contemporaries and disciples. According to Idehen and Oaikhena (2021), "stable policies and strong institutions are crucial elements of an enabling environment, which, is necessary for thriving prosperous economy".

Of course, innumerable developments in evolutionary theory have taken place since the time of Darwin, and some of Darwin's concepts have proven wrong. Darwin

accepted both the principle of use and disuse (Lamarck's "First Law") and the formulation of inheritance of acquired characteristics (Lamarck's "Second Law"). In *The Origin of Species*, he stated that "there can be little doubt that use in our domestic animals strengthens and enlarges certain parts and disuse diminishes them; and that such modifications are inherited." Indeed, Darwin devoted an entire section in chapter 5 to the concept of use and disuse (Bull, 1995).

The second concept is the concept of mind mutation. The world is being turned upside down or downside up by the major world players and the weaker world may not be able to stop them and may be forced to join them. Be it known today that the end is near either in line with Biblical predictions or by man's scientific inquisitiveness and invention. It may be recalled that covid-19 experiment and adventures wherein the world was brought to its knees, is still very fresh as it affects survival of the fittest principle. The Covid-19 experience and experiment coupled with human being married to animals are the effects of 'mind mutation' with its root from Darwin's evolutionary theory. The concept states that: *the mind infinitely mutates infinitely towards the direction it progresses positively or negatively* (i.e. as one continues to do same thing over and again, the mind keeps adjusting (mutating) to it infinitely, be it good or bad. The present moral bankruptcies are some of the byproducts of the negative implications and applications of Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory which is thus interpreted to mean 'the end justifies the means by the likes of Micaville and Hitler. This is nothing but the aftermaths of what this study called 'mind mutation' from Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory of survival of the fittest.

Mind mutation from Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory

The mind mutation model/theory holds that just as diseases like malaria and typhoid mutates and becomes more resistant to drugs, plants mutate to produce better yielding and disease resistant species and organisms including humans also mutates to bring about resistant off springs; so do human mind mutates over time which is parts of what the advanced world called new world order? It is what is called new world order, which takes its root from the Darwin's theory of 1859, called mind mutation. The theory/model

further says that: *the mind infinitely mutates towards the direction it progresses positively or negatively* (i.e. as one continues to do same thing over and again, the mind keeps adjusting (mutating) to it infinitely, be it good or bad. In other words, if one continues to do evil for so long; the mind keeps adapting and adjusting towards the direction you so trained it. If for good, the mind keeps turning like radio receptive chip and get to a level that the individual seamlessly do good and naturally abhors evil; and if for bad, the mind over time tastes for evil naturally. It is the law of the mind as contained in proverbs 4:23 and Romans 1:28.

This applies to the individual, the community, states and nations in international relations and world politics. The major players in international politics (the developed world) have reached the level of infinite mind mutation negatively as anything moral is seen as weakness, and amoral behavior is seen as strength, freedom and superiority.

See model/theory of mind mutation.

The Bible mentions bestiality in four different passages. Exodus 22:19 says, “Anyone who has sexual relations with an animal must be put to death.” Leviticus

18:23 declares, “Do not have sexual relations with an animal and defile yourself with it. A woman must not present herself to an animal to have sexual relations with it; that is a perversion.” Leviticus 20:15-16 commands, “If a man has sexual relations with an animal, he must be put to death, and you must kill the animal. If a woman approaches an animal to have sexual relations with it, kill both the woman and the animal. They must be put to death; their blood will be on their own heads.” Deuteronomy 27:21 agrees, “Cursed is the man who has sexual relations with any animal.” From these verses, it is abundantly clear that, according to the Bible, bestiality is a horrible, unnatural, and abominable sin.

Why is bestiality condemned so strongly? First, it is an unnatural perversion. Clearly, human beings were designed/intended to mate with other human beings, not animals. Anything outside this Biblical injunction is against morality, God and reduces man to a beast. In the creation account, none of the animals were “suitable” for Adam (Genesis 2:20). Second, bestiality represents the ultimate of sexual deviancy. The fact that the animal was to be put to death (Leviticus 20:15-16), despite the fact that the anima(s) may be “innocent,” indicates how wickedly perverse bestiality is. Third, and perhaps most importantly, bestiality essentially denies the uniqueness of humanity which God created in His image (Genesis 1:27). Bestiality lowers humanity to nothing more than an animal, a beast which is unable to distinguish right from wrong, natural from unnatural, love from lust and good from evil.

The New Testament nowhere mentions bestiality by name, but that should not be interpreted as an allowance for bestiality or a weakening of God’s moral standards. Bestiality is by definition included in Scripture’s many prohibitions against sexual immorality as contained (1 Corinthians 6:9; Galatians 5:19; Colossians 3:5; Hebrews 13:4).

What about gay marriage? It is the height of moral bankruptcy and an affront against God who could have, but did not; create man for man. He knew that man could not procreate with man. Beyond the pleasure of sexual intimacy, God’s intention for creating the woman for man is for procreation (Genesis 2:18). Today, it therefore will shock the moral taste of any man in the image of God to learn that "Gay marriage

is legal in 6 states and having sex with a horse is legal in 23 states in America!." This should shock the moral taste of any religious or moral minds.

Methodology

The researcher employed library research methodology to explore the relevant literatures on the influence of Charles Darwin's Evolutionary Theory on Christianity and morality in the 21st Century international relations. This method was seen to be appropriate as it allowed for in-depth, extensive and comprehensive examination of the existing relevant books, journals, texts, newspapers and scholarly articles on Darwin, his theory of evolution as it relates to Christianity, morality and international relations. By reviewing a wide range of literatures, key concepts and theories, this study was able to identify areas where Darwin's evolutionary theory have influenced Pseudo-Christianity and morality in international relations; synthesize the discussions and findings as well as generate incisive enquiries that could inform and affect future studies in its recommendations.

Discussion

Where did Darwin's ideas and theory lead? who was Charles Darwin? Devil or Angel, Christian or Atheist, a radical who wanted to destroy society or Conservative, can we separate his scientific idea from who he was as a person?

These can be looked upon from two perspectives viz: Moral cum religion and political. Enthused with his new theory, it's doubtful that Charles Darwin gave much thought to the possible moral consequences of what he was writing. What actually happened was that evolution was promoted as a faith. Galton hoped that eugenics would one day have the authority of the church. Haeckel set up his "Monist League" explicitly in order to found an "evolutionary religion". And, for Huxley, trans-humanism was quite obviously a religion-substitute.

In fact, evolution may have been seen as progress, however progress is understood if I understood what progress means. But the confusion of the two is probably incurable. It expresses a central illusion of modern times - the myth that scientific knowledge can enable the human species to seize control of its destiny. The lesson of

Darwinism is that species have no collective purpose. It is not “humanity” that uses the results of scientific inquiry. Instead, some human beings use science to control others. Happily, and fortunately too, no group is likely ever going to be able to control humankind as a whole. Huxley’s vision will remain no more than an ugly dream. Yet the appeal of this fantasy is unlikely to wane, because it satisfies the need of the amoral faith while offering the alluring prospect of power. Darwin certainly could not have foreseen that less than 75 years later, his ideas would lead to Adolf Hitler and the Holocaust, the Nazi attempt at exterminating the Jews. But Professor Weikart’s detailed book documents the connection, with plenty of quotes from mostly German philosophers and scientists in the intervening years.

Dr. Richard Evans, professor of modern history at the University of Cambridge and author of *The Coming of the Third Reich*, says that Weikart’s book “shows in sober and convincing detail how Darwinist thinkers in Germany had developed an amoral attitude to human society by the time of the First World War, in which the supposed good of the race was applied as the sole criterion of public policy and ‘racial hygiene.’ “Without over-simplifying the lines that connected this body of thought to Hitler, he demonstrates with chilling clarity how policies such as infanticide, assisted suicide, marriage prohibitions, and much else were being proposed for those considered racially or eugenically inferior by a variety of Darwinist writers and scientists, providing Hitler and the Nazis with a scientific justification for the policies they pursued ...” (Richard, 2004).

Many have asked how the nation that produced Beethoven, Bach, Goethe and Schiller could have allowed a man like Hitler to become their supreme leader. Weikart’s research helps us understand how this happened, by showing the gradual change in thinking that took place “from Darwin to Hitler”—a degeneration in appreciating the value of human life that continues to this day. In Nigeria today, Boko Haran, Fulani Herdsmen, ritualists, cultists etc, could be slaughtering human beings on camera with dignity and effrontery without any moral guilt or feelings that differentiate human from beasts! It wasn’t only Hitler’s National Socialist (Nazi) movement that was heavily influenced by Darwin. “After reading Darwin’s *Origin of Species*, Karl Marx [the founder of the communist movement] wrote to Friedrich Engels, ‘Although developed in a coarse

English manner, this is the book that contains the foundation in natural history for our view.’ Furthermore, many pacifists, feminists, birth control advocates, and homosexual rights activists some of whom were persecuted and even killed by the Nazis—were enthusiastic Darwinists and used Darwinian arguments to support their political and social agendas” (Richard Weikart, 2004).

Consequent upon Darwin’s theory, a whole new scale of national state was clearly on the horizon for the 20th C—Russia and the U.S. These had larger populations (over 100 million each—Britain a little over 40 million, France about 60 million, Germany over 60 million) and enormous resources; they were in fact continental powers. Russia had always been larger than other European states, but the size had been offset by the fact that Russia was very backward in industrial terms and thus in military terms also. However, by the 1890s, although still behind other parts of northern Europe, Russia was beginning to industrialize.

As it caught up industrially, Russia’s size would begin to have its impact in terms of power. The label for these new larger entities was ‘world power’. The problem nagging people in Germany, Britain and France was how would they get the additional resources i.e., like poker chips, to remain in the game. They were threatened with being reduced to ‘second class or second rate’ status. If you want to understand the frenzy for acquiring empire in the late 19th C, these concerns were probably more important than anything else; colonies were believed to provide extra resources, human and material, to keep European great powers in the game of world powers and the colonies who were regarded as the inferior race were to be used to service the European’s industrial needs. In his explanation of Darwin’s theory, Friedrich Ratzel (1844-1904) argued that national states were organisms and as such were subject to the same Darwinist pressures and requirements as other living organisms. This model carried many ramifications: nations were born, grew and matured; nations could also die. As with all organisms, nations require land, space, in order to survive. (<https://www.google.com/> 2025).

A new political order

Darwin's ideas led to a radically different worldview on the part of many European thinkers. "In 1904 one of the leading German Darwinian biologists, Arnold Dodel, proclaimed, 'The new world view actually rests on the theory of evolution. On it we have to construct a new ethics ... All values will be revalued' ... Their moral relativism implied that some moral values might have been valid in the past, but may no longer apply under modern conditions" (p. 43). Interestingly, a contemporary of Dodel, the famous American anti-evolutionist William Jennings Bryan, "was largely motivated by concern over the moral implications of Darwinism. As a pacifist, Bryan was outraged by the Darwinian rhetoric of German militarists, whom he held responsible for the outbreak of World War I" (p. 1). Bryan's concerns were proven right, as their thinking was just a stepping-stone to Hitler's racial theories leading to a second global conflict a quarter century later.

Besides, Darwin's theory did not just alter political thinking, contributing to fascism, communism and two world wars. It also changed the thinking of huge numbers of people within Western societies on moral and Biblical teachings.

Values based on centuries of Judeo-Christian teaching on the sanctity of marriage and human life in general began to erode. Darwin's theory did not just provide an alternative explanation to the biblical account of creation, it effectively led to doubts on *everything* in the Bible, including the moral laws. Today, many in the West view marriage as a quaint but outdated custom, while the idea of fidelity (sexual commitment) to one partner for life is held by only a small minority both in the western world and the world over. In the minds of many today, sex is solely for pleasure, and children are an inconvenience and a burden. Without realizing it, one of the inevitable consequences of Darwinism is the very real threat to the very existence of the human race as people who have embraced his teaching are increasing by the day.

Rejection of Judeo-Christian values

Weikart explains how accepting Darwinist dogma shifted society's thinking on human life: "Before Darwinism burst onto the scene in the mid-nineteenth century, the idea of the

sanctity of human life was dominant in European thought and law (though, as with all ethical principles, not always followed in practice). Judeo-Christian ethics proscribed the killing of innocent human life, and the Christian churches explicitly forbade murder, infanticide, abortion, and even assisted suicide. “The sanctity of human life became enshrined in classical liberal human rights ideology as ‘the right to life,’ which according to John Locke and the United States Declaration of Independence, was one of the supreme rights of every individual” (p. 75) but things have changed. But that was to change, “Only in the late nineteenth and especially the early twentieth century did significant debate erupt over issues relating to the sanctity of human life, especially infanticide, euthanasia, abortion, and suicide. It was no mere coincidence that these contentious issues emerged at the same time that Darwinism was gaining in influence. Darwinism played an important role in this debate, for it altered many people’s conceptions of the importance and value of human life, as well as the significance of death” (<https://www.google.com/2025>).

Consequences from rejecting God in the practice of bestiality

This progression in Western thinking is not surprising to Biblical readers who are familiar with the Apostle Paul’s letter to the Romans, written 18 centuries before Darwin. In it, the apostle showed how people’s rejection of the true God, in spite of the abundant physical evidence of His existence all around them in His creation, led inevitably to the worship of *things* and, in turn, to casting off moral values and restraint. “For since the creation of the world God’s invisible qualities ... have been clearly seen, being understood from what has been made, so that men are without excuse. For although they knew God, they neither glorified him as God nor gave thanks to him ... Although they claimed to be wise, they became fools and exchanged the glory of the immortal God for images made to look like mortal man and birds and animals ... and worshiped and served created things rather than the Creator” (Romans 1:20-25, New International Version). In the ancient world, the peoples who rejected God soon found the need for something to replace Him. Thus, they came up with the pagan gods of their imaginations, many of which reflected man’s own blood-lust and sexual appetites that are so much the opposite of the true Creator of the Bible. Rejecting the true God also had social and sexual consequences, as Paul

showed in subsequent verses. “For this reason, God gave them up to vile passions. For even their women exchanged the natural use for what is against nature. Likewise, also the men, leaving the natural use of the woman, burned in their lust for one another, men with men committing what is shameful, and receiving in themselves the penalty of their error which was due” (verses 26-27).

Just as man’s earlier rejection of God led to throwing off morality, once societies began to reject the Bible as the inerrant Word of God, people no longer saw any justification for their nations to be governed by God’s moral laws. Many enthusiastically embraced Darwin’s theory as it gave them excuse and freedom to reject the moral and Biblical laws of God and live sexually liberated lives like animals. The world we live is right now in disarray and mankind no longer value the Biblical, ethical and moral laws as government of all continents are approving and applauding amoral tendencies such as same sex marriage, killing, suicide, war, hatred, infanticide, love for money, survival of the fittest, marriage between human and animal like cat, dog and horse and ridiculing Biblical principles of value for human life, love, humility, righteous living, care for the weak, the widows, the fatherless, the voiceless, the orphans, victims of war, care for strangers, fairness, justice and the ultimate final destination of man either in hell with the devil or in heaven with God. It’s now part of the new world order in America and other so called developed world.

Dr. Richard Evans, professor of modern history at the University of Cambridge and author of *The Coming of the Third Reich*, says that Weikart’s book “shows that “Without over-simplifying the lines that connected this body of thought to Hitler, he demonstrates with chilling clarity how policies such as infanticide, assisted suicide, marriage prohibitions, same sex marriage, abortion and much else were being proposed for those considered racially or eugenically inferior by a variety of Darwinist writers and scientists, providing Hitler and the Nazis with a scientific justification for the policies they pursued ...” (From Darwin to Hitler, back cover).

Today, it’s no longer secret that in America and Indian human and animals are now having carnal knowledge and cohabiting in marriage. In 2014, California Allows First-Ever State Recognized Human-Animal Marriage. National Report in San Francisco

says history was made at the Chapel of Our Lady at the Presidio in San Francisco as the first-ever state recognized human-animal marriage took place. Local resident 35-year-old Paul Horner was the groom during the ceremony. Joining him was his faithful dog Mac who is 36-years-old in dog years. Paul Horner, a 35-year-old local resident, was the groom during the wedding ceremony. He was joined in 'unholy' matrimony with Mac, his faithful dog.

Again, on 11th Oct 2017, independent newspaper published that 43-year-old Wilhelmina Morgan Callaghan, from Northern Ireland, married her dog Henry eight years ago! In 2005, another British woman reportedly married a dolphin. The Sudanese goat marriage incident made headlines in 2006, when a man was forced to marry a goat after being caught in a sexual interaction with it. Other reports of human animal marriage include animals such as dogs, cats, frogs, and a dolphin.

A British woman, Amanda Rodgers, made headlines with her unique take on marriage. Her story became a sensation when she wed her beloved dog, Sheba, in a grand ceremony witnessed by 200 people in Croatia on 29 Oct 2023.

India with its vast rural population is a source for many of these stories. Recently the British Broadcasting Cooperation (BBC) ran an article entitled “Man ‘marries’ dog to beat curse.” As promised, it celebrates the marriage of one Selvakumar, a 33-year-old man, to a dog called Selvi in a village in Tamil Nadu. The marriage was intended to cure the groom of paralysis, which the villagers believed has resulted from his having killed dogs. It’s fun to read about the man who was forced to marry a goat in Sudan — a somewhat tragic story since his goat-wife apparently died soon after when she choked on a piece of plastic — but when a Western media organization reports on the odd happenings in parts of the developing world, is there an implicit moral judgment? Yes, it’s true that in 2007, a man in Tamil Nadu, India, named P. Selvakumar, "married" a dog named Selvi in a traditional Hindu ceremony to ward off a perceived curse, as reported by NBC_News and the BBC.

In America today, in the name of freedom, civilization and socialization, parents can no longer control their children anymore else the child will call the police and the government will dispossess the parents of the child on the accusation of child abuse as is

currently the case in most so-called civilized world. There is therefore the urgent need to raise alarm as in the novel 'Things Fall Apart by a Nigerian novelist Chinua Achebe. Like a movie, it appears anything goes in developed countries as "Gay marriage is legal in 6 states. Having sex with a horse is legal in 23 states in America." Four states such as Hawaii, New Mexico, West Virginia and Wyoming do not have laws that formally prohibit sexual abuse of animals, traditionally known as bestiality.

Early societies responded to bestiality in various ways. In some, such as ancient Greece, sex between humans and nonhuman animals not only went unpunished, but it was possibly commonplace (Miletski, 2005). Other societies, however, punished bestiality severely. The first known bestiality laws were established by another ancient civilization, the Anatolian Hittites, who inscribed their legal code on clay tablets. The tablets, which are estimated to date from 1650 B.C.E. to 1500 B.C.E., also contain an array of rules related to the treatment of animals (Gordon S.2015). Similar to Hammurabi's code, many Hittite laws treat animals as property with economic value and provide for recompense if one's animal is injured or killed. Unlike Hammurabi's code, the Hittites specifically address bestiality in two of their approximately 200 rules. The first rule states: *If anyone has sexual relations with a pig or a dog, he shall die. He shall bring him to the palace gate. The king may have them killed or he may spare them, but the human shall not approach the king. If an ox leaps on a man, the ox shall die; the man shall not die. They shall substitute one sheep for the man and put it to death. If a pig leaps on a man, it is not an offense* (Roth, Hoffner, and Michalowski, 1995).

The second rule states: *If anyone has sexual relations with either a horse or a mule, it is not an offense, but he shall not approach the king, nor shall he become a priest. If anyone sleeps with an a married-woman, and also sleeps with her mother, it is not an offense* (Roth, et al, 1995).

The Hittite laws regarding bestiality offer a glimpse into the legislative motivation of the Hittite rulers and their society's views regarding animals in general. It is note-worthy that the laws regarding bestiality does not consider the animal's economic value. If they did, they would not proscribe death for an ox that "leaps on a man" in sexual excitement. On the contrary, there are some other value systems at play defining

the animals for which bestiality is punishable. The array of punishments ranges from death for the human, the animal, or both; to nothing; or to some middling social sanction preventing one from becoming a priest. One legal scholar has suggested that the Hittite society developed rules related to sexual activity with animals based on the concept of cleanliness (Bryce, 2002). Sexual acts thought to put the community at risk of disease were defined as *hurkel* and therefore forbidden.

The texts of modern-day religions provide a window into how other early societies viewed bestiality. The Torah, known as the Pentateuch in the Christian tradition, composes the first five books of the Hebrew and Christian Bibles. The Torah is thought to have been completed by 400 B.C.E. and to express the beliefs and traditions of the Israelites, who lived in the Near East around 600 B.C.E. (Blenkinsopp, 1992). One of the books of the Torah, Leviticus, expressly forbids acts of bestiality: *Do not have sexual relations with an animal and defile yourself with it. A woman must not present herself to an animal to have sexual relations with it; that is a perversion. (Leviticus 18:23) (The Holy Bible. New Reversed Standard Version, Catholic Edition.* Leviticus 20:15 states: *If a man has sexual relations with an animal, he shall be put to death; and you shall kill the animal (The Holy Bible. New Reversed Standard Version, Catholic Edition).*

According to the Israelites, bestiality represented, a forbidden relationship. One was meant to give up his or her life rather than engage in such activity. The concern regarding defilement or, in other translations, “becoming unclean” (The Holy Bible. New International Reader’s Version) suggests that the Israelites had concerns like the Hittites’ regarding cleanliness or the risk posed to their society by sexual acts involving animals. Bestiality’s condemnation in the Bible likely affected societal responses to sexual acts involving animals for centuries. As scripture became a source of moral and ethical guidance for followers of Judeo-Christian religions, violations of rules in the Bible could be used as grounds to morally condemn and prosecute such behavior. From the fifteenth to seventeenth centuries in England and mainland Europe, the punishment for “buggery” was death for both human and nonhuman parties (Fudge, 2000).

One historian note that, “his disgusting crime appears to have been very common” (Evans, 2013). Such harsh, moralistic punishment was imported to the

American colonies. The execution of Thomas Grainger in Plymouth Colony in 1642 serves as a clear example of moral punishment as a motivation for legal action. At the age of 16 or 17, Grainger was sentenced to death for “buggery” involving “a mare, two goats, five sheep, two calves, and a turkey” (Brandfold, and Morison, 1952). The animals were reportedly killed in front of Grainger, then thrown into a pit. Grainger was then hanged. Clearly, whatever moral harms resulted from Grainger’s acts of bestiality was thought to override any potential economic value of the animals with which he had sex.

The religious or moral condemnation of bestiality remains evident as a motivation for legislation in the names of statutes in some jurisdictions of the United States. For example, Maryland’s law is entitled “unnatural or perverted sexual practice” (Maryland Criminal Code, 2002). North Carolina’s law is named “crime against nature” (North Carolina General Sttutes, 1994) and simply states, “If any person commits a crime against nature, with mankind or beast, he shall be punished as a Class I felon.”

The law seemingly criminalizes anal intercourse, including consensual anal intercourse between two adult humans and the host of other sexual acts that humans may commit with animals. The problem at the moment is that these laws have been compromised in the same united states and other so called developed world and this article seeks to point to the inherent danger this poses to the human race, moral codes and laws including the Bible and an affront against the almighty God. From the above, just as the Holy Bible provide the foundation for moral behaviour so do Darwin’s theory provided the foundation for amoral tendencies today.

In the discipline of international relations there are contending general theories or theoretical perspectives. Realism, also known as political realism, is a view of international politics that stresses its competitiveness and power (amoral). It is usually contrasted with idealism or liberalism, which tends to emphasize cooperation (moral). Realists consider the principal actors in the international arena to be states, which are concerned with their own security, ego and interest and so act in pursuit of their own national interests, and struggle for power and protection as pressure groups. The negative side of the realists, emphasizes on power and self-interest. The realists are often skeptical regarding the relevance of ethical and Biblical norms to relationship among states. The

realists do not really care about justice but concerned about how to use strength and resources to dominate in the conflict among states which agrees with Darwin's theory of survival of the fittest. Some of the apostles of Darwinism are theorists as Reinhold Niebuhr, Hans Morgenthau and Machiavelli who were radical or extreme realism. Their doctrine involves the glorification of war or conflict in international politics and that "anything is justified by reason of state" as their belief is that only the fittest should survive and the weak should be eliminated (Bull 1995).

They are rather critical of morals which they regarded as abstract discourse that does not take into account political realities. They assign supreme value to successful political action based on prudence and the ability to judge the rightness of a given action from among possible alternatives on the basis of its likely political consequences. This could be the reason why Oaikhena (2021) asserted that "it is imperative to integrate strategies to deal with eradicating poverty and implementing adequate policies geared towards equitable distribution of resources, wealth and income that could easily lead to social protection coverage". Realism encompasses a variety of approaches and claims a long theoretical tradition. Among its founding fathers are: Thucydides, Machiavelli and Hobbes.

Nevertheless, twentieth-century classical realism has today been largely replaced by neo-realism, which is an attempt to construct a more scientific approach to the study of international relations. Both classical realism and neo-realism have long been subjected to criticism from international relation theorists representing liberal and post-modern perspectives in line with Christian doctrines and morality. Yet, the damage of Darwin's theory on the mind of the developed world as it affects the world's moral psyche and Christianity is better imagined than experienced.

Given the above model, realism aligned with the amoral (Negative thoughts: Hate, war, rape, infanticide, suicide, kidnapping, killing, etc) which the developed world represents and the idealist aligned with the Biblical/Christian teachings and moral laws (Positive thoughts: love, mercy, justice, love, kindness, fairness, affection, forgiveness and cooperation etc) which the third world countries crave for.

Prudence, and not conviction of one's own moral or ideological superiority, should guide political action. This is stressed in the fifth principle, where Morgenthau again emphasizes the idea that all state actors, including our own, must be looked at solely as political entities pursuing their respective interests defined in terms of power. By taking this point of view vis-à-vis its counterparts and thus avoiding ideological confrontation, a state would then be able to pursue policies that respected the interests of other states, while protecting and promoting its own.

Insofar as power, or interest defined as power, is the concept that defines politics, politics is an autonomous sphere, as Morgenthau says in his sixth principle of realism. It cannot be subordinated to ethics. However, ethics does still play a role in politics. "A man who was nothing but 'political man' would be a beast, for he would be completely lacking in moral restraints. A man who was nothing but 'moral man' would be a fool, for he would be completely lacking in prudence" (12). Political art requires that these two dimensions of human life, power and morality, be taken into consideration. *(First published Mon Jul 26, 2010; substantive revision Wed May 24, 2017). A man without religious inclination will act ruthlessly, brutal and not be different from beast. Here lies the burden of the need to align with moral and Biblical ethics if the society must be ordered in line with God's plan for humanity. A man is both physical and spiritual being and it's this spiritual nature of man that differentiate man from other lower being for GOD said" Let us make man in our own image after our likeness (Gen. 1:26) but could not say so while creating other beings.*

Recommendation

The world is being turned upside down or downside up by the major world players and the weaker world may not be able to stop them and may be forced to join them. Be it known today that the end is near either in line with Biblical predictions or by man's scientific inquisitiveness and invention. It may be recalled that covid 19 experiment and adventures wherein the world was brought to its knees is still very fresh as it affects survival of the fittest principle. The Covid 19 experience and experiment coupled with human being married to animals are the effects of 'mind mutation' with its root from

Darwin's evolutionary theory. The present moral bankruptcies are some of the byproducts of the negative implications and applications of Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory which is thus interpreted to mean 'the end justifies the means by the likes of Micaville and Hitler. This is nothing but the aftermaths of what I called 'mind mutation' from Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory of survival of the fittest.

Conclusion

Political realism is usually contrasted by IR scholars with idealism or liberalism, a theoretical perspective that emphasizes international norms, interdependence among states, and international cooperation. Can international politics be based on a moral order derived from the principles of justice, Biblical teachings or will it forever remain in the arena of conflicting national interests and power based on survival of the fittest? Will morality and Christianity be eroded and the world will not be brought to its knees with the survival of the fittest theory?

Although Darwin thought Man's innate nobility would predispose him kindly towards the sick and poor – or perhaps those who think or look differently from ourselves, his successors tended to have no such scruples. The bulk of Sewell's book is taken up with the colorful history of the eugenics movement, which, by the early 20th century, had managed to gain the approval of Parliament. The Mental Deficiency Act 1913 classified people as "idiots", "imbeciles", "the feeble-minded" and "moral defectives" and led to at least 50 years of people being locked up or lobotomized on the flimsiest pretexts. The concurrent situation across the Atlantic was similar; countless low-income Americans were sterilized under largely false pretenses on grounds of weak species.

A clear-eyed look at history shows us that tyrannies tend to go underground or become bit by bit so institutionalized that they are eventually "hidden in plain sight". One of the central beliefs of the eugenics movement was the superiority of western civilization, whose values would eventually eliminate "an endless number of the lower races" (Darwin's words). This is precisely the assumption behind the policies of the World Bank, whose loans restructure developing nations' cultures after capitalist, earth-plundering models and so on. Whatever you may think of the gentle, doubting man,

Darwin's cold-blooded ideas continue to wreak havoc in our world and if care is not taken, man is already on his way to self-destruction.

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EDUCATIONAL POLICY AND CHALLENGES OF PROGRAMME IMPLEMENTATION IN FUNDING TEACHER EDUCATION AND UNIVERSAL BASIC EDUCATION IN NIGERIA.

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Abstract

In order to determine the effects on educational quality and the efficacy of policy, this study examined the difficulties in financing teacher education and implementing the Universal Basic Education (UBE) program in Nigeria. Despite important government initiatives to improve educational quality and access, there were many challenges in putting these policies into practice. These include socioeconomic constraints that restricted educational access, especially for marginalised populations, a shortage of competent teachers, inadequate facilities, and inadequate finance. Through a thorough literature review and document analysis, a qualitative research approach was used to get insights into the historical background of Nigerian educational policy. The study also looked at Nigeria's educational policy's historical background, emphasising how earlier policies influenced the country's current educational system. The results emphasised how important it is for stakeholders—including communities, non-governmental organisations, educational institutions, and government agencies—to work together in order to effectively solve these problems. According to the report, the UBE program's efficacy was weakened by corruption, poor management, and a small portion of the national budget going towards education. Additionally, sociocultural elements like community involvement and gender inequality were major impediments to educational advancement. These findings led to the proposal of a number of proposals aimed at improving educational quality, expanding educational access, and guaranteeing the effective implementation of educational policy. Increasing school funding, bolstering teacher preparation programs, improving monitoring and assessment systems, and encouraging community involvement were some of these.

Keywords: Universal Basic Education, teacher education, funding challenges, educational policy.

Introduction

In addition to being a vital component of social and economic advancement, education is a fundamental human right. Education is crucial for attaining sustainable development, lowering poverty, and advancing equality, according to the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) (Canton, 2021). Nigeria's government has made major pledges to improve educational access and quality through a number of programs because it understands how important education is to the country's growth. The Universal Basic Education (UBE) program, which was introduced in 2004 with the goal of offering free and mandatory education to all school-age children, is among the most noteworthy initiatives (Anaduaka & Okafor, 2013).

Nigeria's educational system has long struggled with issues of educational quality and access, which the UBE program was created to solve (Anaduaka et al., 2015). High dropout rates, poor infrastructure, and a lack of finance for educational institutions were among the major obstacles to education that the nation faced before the UBE program was launched. Historically, these problems have prevented many children from accessing high-quality education, which is essential for personal development and empowerment for the advancement of the country. Nigerian educational policy includes a variety of programs designed to raise the standard and accessibility of education (Aliyu et al., 2025). The goals and objectives of the educational system are outlined in the National Policy on Education (NPE), which was initially published in 1977 and has undergone numerous revisions. It emphasises the necessity of universal access to high-quality education (Ezewuzie et al., 2025). With an emphasis on fairness, inclusivity, and the encouragement of lifelong learning, the NPE seeks to offer a framework for educational progress. Nevertheless, there are still many obstacles to overcome in the implementation of these policy frameworks.

There are several obstacles in the way of Nigeria's educational policy and the UBE program's lofty objectives. These include a shortage of competent teachers, poor facilities, and insufficient budget. These difficulties impair the quality of education that

children get and make it more difficult to implement educational policy effectively. According to Ohaegbulem and Chijioke (2023), the Nigerian government has continuously allotted a little portion of its national budget to education, falling short of the 15-20% UNESCO recommended. Furthermore, problems with corruption and poor administration in the educational system make the funding difficulties worse. According to reports, a sizeable amount of the funds allotted for education are embezzled, which compromises the efficacy of educational initiatives (Ololube, 2016).

Corruption damages public confidence in government programs and educational institutions in addition to taking money away from its intended uses. The UBE program's advancement is hampered by this cycle of inefficiency and underfunding. In Nigeria, socioeconomic variables also have a big impact on educational quality and access. Families' capacity to pay for school-related costs like uniforms, books, and transportation is hampered by high poverty rates (Lott, 2025). Long commutes to school and poor infrastructure are two further issues that children frequently encounter in rural locations, where poverty is more severe. Gender discrepancies in educational access are influenced by cultural issues as well, as some communities may place a higher value on boys' education than girls' (Ajala & Alonge, 2013). The implementation of successful educational programs and the accomplishment of the UBE program's objectives are made more difficult by these socioeconomic obstacles.

Given these difficulties, the purpose of this essay is to investigate how funding and implementation concerns affect Nigerian educational quality. The study aims to shed light on Nigeria's larger educational environment by examining the obstacles to the efficient implementation of the UBE program and financing for teacher education.

Educational policies in Nigeria

Historical Context

The colonial period, which established the framework for the present educational system, is when Nigeria's educational policies began to change (Daniel-Kalio, 2018). The primary goal of the formal education system set up by the British colonial government was to create a small elite class that would help run the colony (Imam, 2012). The emphasis was

on Western education, which frequently disregarded local languages and knowledge systems. There were notable differences in educational access between urban and rural populations as a result of the majority of schools being located in urban areas.

Colonial Era

Throughout the colonial era, missionary work had a significant impact on education. Although missionaries founded basic education schools, their numbers and reach were constrained (Kallaway, 2016). The primary goals of the education offered were religious instruction and the development of a devoted labour force for the colonial government. The education system was dispersed due to the absence of a unified national educational policy, with different regions implementing distinct curriculum in response to local demands and the influence of various missionary organisations. An important turning point in Nigeria's educational history was the 1948 Education Ordinance (Salahu, 2020). By establishing a framework for formal education, this legislation highlighted the need for a more organised approach to education nationwide. It established the foundation for upcoming educational policy and acknowledged the value of education in promoting national development. Even so, there were still barriers to education, especially for girls and kids living in rural areas.

Post-Independence Developments

After Nigeria gained its independence in 1960, the government realised how urgently the educational gaps brought about by colonialism needed to be addressed. The first National Curriculum Conference was held in 1969, and the National Policy on Education (NPE) was created in 1977 as a result (Alade, 2011). With an emphasis on fairness, inclusivity, and the encouragement of lifelong learning, the NPE sought to offer a framework for the advancement of education in Nigeria. It aimed to establish an educational system that would support national development and meet the various demands of Nigeria's populace. Ikpuri (2018) claims that the NPE placed a strong emphasis on a number of important goals, such as: Universal access making sure that every child has access to a basic education quality education improving the quality of education through better curriculum

development and teacher training technical and vocational education promoting technical and vocational education to meet the demands of the labour market cultural relevance integrating Nigerian culture and values into the educational system to promote national identity revisions and new initiatives. Since its inception, the NPE has undergone multiple adjustments to accommodate the nation's evolving educational demands (Ezewuzie et al., 2025).

Enhancing the quality of education and tackling problems including funding, teacher preparation, and infrastructure development were the main goals of the 1981 and 1998 modifications. The goal of these changes was to develop a more resilient educational framework that could change to accommodate Nigeria's changing socioeconomic environment. The launch of the Universal Basic Education (UBE) program in 2004 is regarded as one of the most important turning points in Nigeria's educational policy history (Kolade, 2019). The global Education for All (EFA) movement, which sought to guarantee that all children get high-quality basic education, prompted the creation of the UBE program. With a focus on removing obstacles to the educational system and fostering inclusivity, the UBE program aimed to offer free and mandatory education to all students between the ages of 6 and 15.

Anaduaka and Okafor (2013) state that the UBE program was created to address a number of important issues that the Nigerian educational system was facing, such as: community involvement—the program promoted community participation in school management and decision-making processes to foster ownership and accountability quality of education—the UBE program highlighted the need for improved teaching standards, better learning materials, and improved school infrastructure—and access to education—the program sought to increase enrolment rates, particularly among marginalised groups like girls, children with disabilities, and those living in rural areas.

The UBE program's implementation has been fraught with difficulties, despite its lofty objectives. Progress has been hampered by a shortage of competent teachers, inadequate facilities, and inadequate finance. Nigeria has continuously fallen short of the UNESCO standard by allocating a little portion of its national budget on education. A shortage of vital resources, such as certified teachers, instructional materials, and suitable

school buildings, has resulted from this underfunding. Additionally, it has made room for inconsistent policies. "The educational sector, like the universities, for example, had witnessed series of policy summersaults," Oaihena and Idehen (2021) claimed. The system was subjected to a number of regulations, which led to restrictions and distortions in admissions procedures and programs.

The impact of inadequate funding on teacher education and educational quality

The quality of teacher preparation programs and, by extension, students' overall educational experiences can be seriously harmed by inadequate funding for education. This demonstrates how inadequate funding impacts infrastructure development, teacher retention, student performance, teacher training programs, and the lack of instructional materials. The foundation of any educational system is funding. It establishes the resources available for curriculum development, facility upkeep, teacher training, and learning materials. In a perfect world, sufficient funding guarantees that programs for teacher education can draw in skilled instructors, provide thorough instruction, and give aspiring teachers the tools they need to succeed in the classroom.

Qualified educators have been recruited and retained as a result of inadequate funding. Insufficient funding makes it difficult for teacher education programs to recruit highly skilled and experienced instructors (See et al., 2020). This problem is made worse by the fact that many prospective teachers might look for work in more profitable settings or in areas with more competitive pay and benefits. This may be the cause of the numerous instances in which "millions and billions of naira, intended for staff development, have been embezzled by individuals and groups in charge, without any serious actions taken to that effect," according to Oaikhena (2021).

Furthermore, poor teacher pay brought on by a lack of funding frequently lead to significant turnover rates (Carver-Thomas & Darling-Hammond, 2019). When instructors quit their jobs because of financial difficulties, the remaining teachers may have to take on more work, which can cause burnout and more attrition. This cycle results in a teacher shortage, which lowers the standard of education that pupils get. "As employability and productive capacity need to be linked to the provision of training and

skills development, as well as the provision of health care," writes Oaikhena (2021). Thus, the implementation of an education and training system focused on skill development and social-economic advancement is crucial. Funding is crucial for continuing professional development in order to draw in talented educators. To stay up with changing pedagogical methods and educational developments, teachers must constantly refresh their knowledge and abilities. Access to training programs, conferences, and workshops that are essential for improving teachers' abilities is restricted by a lack of finance (Nnokami& Sule, 2019).

Teachers may become less effective in the classroom if they rely on antiquated techniques and materials in the absence of professional development. This lack of development directly impacts student learning outcomes in addition to teachers. The value of funding teacher education is underscored by the fact that studies regularly demonstrate that highly qualified educators are more successful in raising student achievement (Kovarthini et al., 2024). Access to a variety of resources, such as lab equipment, digital resources, textbooks, and classroom supplies, is necessary for effective instruction. Teacher education programs may find it difficult to offer these crucial tools if financing is inadequate (Amadi & Nwogu, 2023).

Curriculum development leading to technological access

For teacher education programs to appropriately train future educators, a well-rounded curriculum is essential. However, a significant financial commitment is necessary for the creation and execution of top-notch courses. Curricula that are out of date or obsolete that do not meet students' requirements or current educational standards can result from inadequate funding (Amadi & Nwogu, 2023). Furthermore, teacher education programs might not have the funds to carry out the required research and curriculum review if they are not adequately funded.

The quality of education kids receive may suffer as a result of this discrepancy between what is taught in teacher preparation programs and the realities of the classroom. Additionally, for teaching and learning to be effective, digital access to technology is necessary. However, a lack of financing makes it difficult for many teacher education programs to include technology into their curricula. This restriction may make it difficult

for aspiring teachers to acquire the abilities they need to successfully integrate technology into their lessons (Vatanartiran& Karadeniz, 2015).

Students' educational experiences are also impacted by limited access to technology. Teachers who lack digital tool proficiency may find it difficult to engage pupils or implement cutting-edge teaching strategies that improve learning. Because of this, students can lose out on important chances to acquire the vital skills necessary for success in the twenty-first century, which also depends on having enough financing.

Curriculum development and the infrastructure of teacher education institutes are greatly impacted by inadequate funding. Teachers' educational experiences are greatly influenced by the physical setting in which they are trained. According to Ramli et al. (2018), inadequately maintained facilities can impede the educational process and have a detrimental impact on student performance. Effective teacher education requires a supportive learning environment. To enable high-quality training, classrooms, libraries, labs, and other facilities need to be properly furnished and maintained. Inadequate funding frequently results in outdated infrastructure, packed classrooms, and insufficient supplies, all of which can hinder learning (Biyela, 2019). Effective teaching methods are difficult to implement at teacher education institutes with inadequate infrastructure. For instance, future teachers would not have the practical experience required to teach science successfully if a teacher training program lacks access to science labs. Students who depend on qualified teachers to direct their learning may suffer long-term effects from this training gap. Lack of finance may make it difficult for schools to keep their spaces secure, which may discourage students from becoming teachers (Hargreaves & Fullan, 2015). Access to teacher education programs may be further restricted by institutions' inability to provide accommodations for students with impairments.

Teacher morale and job satisfaction

Teachers' job satisfaction and morale can be significantly impacted by inadequate funding. Teachers may become less motivated to teach if they feel underappreciated as a result of low pay, a lack of resources, and inadequate support (Uzoh & Anya, 2024). The quality of education that pupils get may suffer as a result of this drop in morale. Teachers

frequently experience burnout and job discontent as a result of higher workloads brought on by low budget (Hassan et al., 2023). Teachers' capacity to deliver high-quality education is weakened when they are asked to take on more duties without receiving enough pay or assistance.

High turnover rates brought on by burnout can make it more difficult to keep a steady and productive teaching staff. As a result, student learning results are significantly impacted by teacher morale. According to research, happy teachers are more likely to engage pupils, establish positive learning environments, and support academic success. On the other hand, discontented teachers may result in disengaged pupils, poorer academic achievement, and a rise in dropout rates (Darling-Hammond, 2016). Student results suffer greatly as a result of insufficient funding for teacher education (Hassan et al., 2023). Students suffer the most when teachers are underprepared, have little resources, and operate in unsatisfactory conditions. Student academic achievement and teacher quality are strongly correlated, according to numerous studies like Bird (2017). Students are less likely to do well academically when teachers are not appropriately prepared or supported.

This disparity in performance has the potential to prolong poverty cycles and restrict prospects for future prosperity (Eze, 2021). Students from low-income families, underprivileged neighborhoods, and rural places are disproportionately impacted by inadequate funding (Rana, 2024). These pupils frequently encounter extra obstacles to receiving a high-quality education, including a lack of funding, inadequate facilities, and teachers with inadequate training. As a result, systemic inequalities in education are sustained as the achievement gap between wealthy and underprivileged pupils grows. Insufficient funding for teacher education has long-term effects that go beyond short-term academic results. Students who don't get a good education could find it difficult to go to college or find steady work later on. This lack of opportunity can hinder social mobility and prolong poverty cycles, which will ultimately affect local and national economic development.

Challenges of programme implementation in Universal Basic Education (UBE) in Nigeria

In Nigeria, the Universal Basic Education (UBE) program was started in 2004 with the goal of giving all school-age children free, mandatory, and universal education (Adekunle, 2019). Notwithstanding the well-organised policy framework, there have been some obstacles to UBE's successful and efficient implementation. This section examines the different program implementation issues in UBE, with an emphasis on the gaps in policy execution and the socioeconomic variables that exacerbate these issues. Effective implementation of the UBE strategy is hampered by a number of shortcomings, notwithstanding its comprehensive character.

Four main categories can be used to group these gaps: i. Lack of Coordination: The federal, state, and local levels of government do not coordinate well, which is one of the biggest obstacles to the UBE program's execution. Every governmental level has distinct duties in the field of education, but a lack of cooperation and communication frequently results in the dispersed execution of educational initiatives (Ejere, 2011; Enyiazu, 2022). Program delivery may be inconsistent, for example, because state and local governments may have various objectives and methods, even though the federal government may establish national standards and laws. Teachers, parents, and students may become confused as a result of this misalignment, which would ultimately reduce the UBE initiative's efficacy. ii. Inadequate Monitoring and Evaluation: The lack of strong monitoring and evaluation systems is another significant weakness in the UBE implementation process (Abutu, 2015). Assessing the effectiveness and progress of educational programs, pinpointing areas for development, and guaranteeing stakeholder accountability all depend on effective monitoring (Obiakor, 2023).

However, it is difficult to assess whether the UBE program is accomplishing its intended goals or to make well-informed decisions about necessary adjustments because the existing monitoring frameworks for UBE are frequently inadequate and lack the resources and expertise to conduct comprehensive evaluations. It is challenging to hold government organisations responsible for their roles in the implementation process in the absence of efficient monitoring and assessment. iii. Inadequate Teacher Training: The

proficiency of instructors is a critical component of the quality of education provided under the UBE program.

Regretfully, a large number of Nigerian educators lack the professional growth and training required to successfully execute the UBE curriculum (Ogundele et al., 2019). Inadequate pre-service training programs, restricted access to opportunities for continuous professional development, and a lack of support from educational authorities are some of the factors causing this problem. Because of this, educators could find it difficult to provide high-quality instruction, apply contemporary teaching strategies, and meet the various requirements of their pupils. This lack of teacher preparation compromises the UBE program's overarching objectives in addition to having an impact on student learning outcomes.

Need for community engagement

Another major issue with UBE implementation is the lack of community involvement in the educational process. To guarantee sustainability and relevance, communities, parents, and local stakeholders must actively participate in educational projects (Adewunmi, 2025). However, there is frequently a gap between the demands of the community and the services offered by schools as a result of communities not being sufficiently involved in the planning and implementation of educational programs. Low enrolment rates, high dropout rates, and a lack of support for educational efforts can all be consequences of this lack of involvement. In order to promote a sense of ownership and dedication to educational programs, which will ultimately increase their efficacy, it is imperative to strengthen community involvement.

The difficulties in implementing UBE in Nigeria are mostly due to socioeconomic reasons in addition to inadequacies in policy implementation. Among these difficulties are: i. Poverty: Because many households cannot afford school-related costs like uniforms, books, and transportation, Nigeria's high poverty rates severely restrict access to education (Akinmoladun, 2021). Disenfranchised populations, such as girls, children with disabilities, and people from rural areas, are disproportionately impacted by this economic obstacle. Many kids continue to skip school as a result,

undermining the UBE program's objectives. Asemah and Oaikhena (2024) contended that "...a high incidence of poverty not only undermines the country's development, but also perpetuates social inequalities and instability" for this reason. Improving access to education and guaranteeing that all children may take advantage of the UBE initiative require addressing poverty through focused interventions, such as financial aid for low-income families and scholarship programs. ii. Cultural Barriers: According to Daura and Audu (2015), cultural customs and beliefs in some parts of Nigeria present extra difficulties for the implementation of UBE. In certain societies, gender stereotypes that favour boys' education over girls' are reinforced by cultural conventions that prohibit girls from pursuing higher education.

Furthermore, children from low socioeconomic origins and members of ethnic minorities may be excluded from educational opportunities and subjected to discrimination. Lower enrolment rates, higher dropout rates, and a lack of educational attainment among impacted communities can all result from these cultural hurdles. Campaigns for advocacy and awareness that question damaging cultural norms and support inclusive teaching methods are crucial in addressing these issues. iii. Insecurity and Conflict: The UBE program's overall execution and educational activities are negatively impacted by the ongoing wars and instability in several parts of Nigeria. Schools have been damaged, teachers have been displaced, and students have been forced to evacuate violent places, such as the northeastern region where the Boko Haram insurgency is raging (Mallam, 2019).

It is difficult to guarantee regular access to education because of this instability, which disrupts educational activities and forces pupils to relocate. For the UBE program to succeed, a secure and supportive learning environment must be established by addressing the underlying causes of conflict and supporting peacebuilding efforts. This may explain why "communal conflicts are consequently merchandise of social family members," (Umenze, et al., 2024).

The role of government and stakeholders in addressing the challenges of educational policy implementation

The quality and accessibility of education are greatly influenced by educational policies. However, there are frequently major obstacles in the way of these policies' effective implementation, such as a lack of infrastructure, inadequate finance, a lack of teacher training, and sociocultural hurdles. The government has a major influence on how educational policies are formulated and carried out. Its duties include developing policies, distributing funds, and fostering an atmosphere that supports the success of educational establishments. The degree to which such policies are in line with the real requirements of the educational system determines how effective they will be (Butler et al., 2018).

To guarantee that schools have the facilities, instructional materials, and technology they require, the government must give education top priority when allocating funds. Governments frequently have limited resources, which results in inadequate support for educational programs. Governments might investigate novel funding methods, such public-private partnerships, to improve resource availability and augment public spending in order to solve this. A regulatory structure that encourages accountability and openness in educational institutions is required, claim Austin & Jones (2016).

This entails establishing requirements for curriculum creation, school administration, and teacher qualifications. To determine their efficacy and make the required modifications, educational policies must be regularly monitored and evaluated. To encourage schools to perform better, governments should use performance-based funding models that link financial resources to quantifiable results (Darling-Hammond, 2016). Successful policy implementation in educational institutions depends on having effective leadership. Principals, administrators, and other school leaders need to be knowledgeable about educational policy and dedicated to creating a supportive learning environment (Ni et al., 2018). To encourage cooperation and ownership of educational projects, these school leaders can involve educators, parents, and the community in decision-making procedures. Teachers have a crucial role in putting educational policies into practice. But a lot of teachers might not have the assistance and training they need to execute new policies successfully (DaRosa et al., 2011).

Ongoing assistance and training can increase teachers' efficacy, which will ultimately improve student results. Parents and community members are more likely to support school initiatives and create a positive learning environment when they are involved in the educational process (Đurišić & Bunijevac, 2017).

The Role of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs)

The implementation of educational policies is greatly aided by non-governmental organisations (NGOs), especially in regions where government funding may be scarce. NGOs frequently take part in lobbying campaigns to reform policies and increase public awareness of educational concerns. They have the power to hold governments responsible for their promises and galvanise popular support for educational programs. For example, groups like the Global Partnership for Education emphasise the value of education as a fundamental right and seek to boost financing and support for education in impoverished nations (Albright & Bundy, 2018). By giving teachers and school administrators resources and training, many NGOs concentrate on increasing capacity. In order to improve teaching methods and school administration, they might provide seminars, workshops, and instructional resources.

NGOs support the effective execution of educational policy by providing educators with the required resources and expertise (Gali & Schechter, 2021). NGOs frequently carry out pilot projects that evaluate novel pedagogical strategies (Dyck & Silvestre, 2019). By offering insightful information and best practices that governments and educational institutions can scale up or modify, these initiatives can act as models for the successful implementation of policies. For example, NGOs may implement technological integration, alternative teaching strategies, or community-based education programs that target particular issues that schools face.

Private businesses can also contribute to educational endeavours by offering funds and resources to support educational programs and schools. This investment can be made in a number of ways, such as by integrating technology, developing infrastructure, and providing educational resources. Partnerships between the public and commercial sectors can improve educational quality and guarantee that schools have the tools they

need to successfully carry out governmental directives (Marx, 2019). Numerous businesses take part in education-focused corporate social responsibility (CSR) programs. Businesses can provide scholarships, help local schools, and train instructors through CSR initiatives (Nehru, 2016).

In addition to helping to promote education, these initiatives also increase the company's standing and fortify its ties to the community. When it comes to technological innovation, the private sector frequently leads the way. Businesses and educational institutions can work together to create and execute technology-driven solutions that improve instruction. For instance, educational software and online learning environments can offer teachers and students more resources, making it easier to adopt new educational regulations. In order to assist their children's education, parents are essential. Active parental involvement in their children's education has a favourable impact on attendance and academic achievement. Through frequent communication, workshops, and chances for involvement in school events, schools should promote parental involvement. By supporting educational projects, volunteering, and donating resources, communities may offer schools invaluable help. Leaders in the community and local organisations can assist spread the word about the value of education and rally support for the execution of policies. Communities that support education provide a nurturing atmosphere that promotes student achievement (Darling-Hammond & Cook-Harvey, 2018).

Theoretical framework

The foundation of this research is Policy Implementation Theory, a paradigm created by Paul Sabatier and Daniel Mazmanian that looks at the discrepancy between the creation and application of public policies. The theory seeks to pinpoint the circumstances under which policy goals are successfully converted into initiatives and results (Sabatier & Mazmanian, 1983). It focusses on the settings, characters, and procedures that affect whether policies are successful or unsuccessful during the implementation stage.

Policy Implementation Theory is especially pertinent to the analysis of the difficulties encountered by the Universal Basic Education (UBE) program and the financing of teacher education in Nigerian education. Nigeria has made great progress in

creating good educational policies, such as the UBE Act and the National Policy on Education (NPE), but there is still a big disparity in how these policies are implemented at the federal, state, and local levels (Ogunkoya, 2023).

Conclusion

In Nigeria, financing teacher education and carrying out the Universal Basic Education program present a number of complex issues with strong socioeconomic, political, and cultural underpinnings. Significant obstacles still stand in the way of the efficient implementation of educational policy, notwithstanding the government's dedication to enhancing educational access and quality. All parties involved government organisations, academic institutions, non-governmental organisations, the commercial sector, and communities must work together to address these issues. Together, we can build a more effective and equitable educational system that serves the needs of every child in Nigeria.

Recommendations

- i. In light of the study's findings, the following actions are advised: Increasing Education Funding: The Nigerian government should make education a top priority in its budget, striving to reach or above the UNESCO recommendation that 15–25% of the national budget be allocated to education.
- ii. Enhancing Teacher Training Programs: To ensure that instructors have the abilities and information required for successful instruction, funding thorough pre-service and in-service training programs is crucial.
- iii. Improving Monitoring and Evaluation Mechanisms: To evaluate how well educational policies are being implemented, it is essential to set up strong monitoring and evaluation frameworks.
- iv. Fostering Community Engagement: To promote a sense of ownership and dedication to educational programs, it is essential to encourage parents and communities to actively participate in the educational process.

- v. Resolving Socio-Cultural Barriers: It is crucial to launch awareness programs to combat damaging cultural norms that impede educational access, especially for girls and under-represented groups.

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CULTURAL PATRIARCHY: A WEAPON DEPLOYED TOWARDS FEMALE GENDER

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Abstract

Culture is associated with belief system, values customs artifacts and behaviour that is associated with the people in a society, community or environment. It has to do with language, social habits, arts, rituals and norms that guide the interactions and lives of the people. Women are deeply involved in cultural practices across societies. They play a crucial role in the preservation of cultural norms, as they often act as custodians of traditions, ceremonies and rituals. Cultural patriarchy therefore is a pervasive framework that gives the male gender privileges to restrict the roles of women, freedom and shaping social relations and cultural expectations in our society. This study is thus set to find out how the female gender are discriminated against in our cultural environment, and why cultural patriarchy prevailed in our social system in Africa. The study adopted secondary research data generational approach. It adopted feminist theory to criticize cultural patriarchy, which explains inequality and injustice meted out to the women. The study also adopted the Maputo Protocol of 2004 which has been rectified by over 40 African countries, and an African Charter on Human and People's Right of women in Africa. The study recommended that women's rights should be respected, they should be fairly treated, allowed to hold leadership positions and given a pride of place in the society.

Keywords: Cultural patriarchy, gender, social relations, tradition.

Introduction

Cultural patriarchy has been described as a means of male dominance in both family and society. Some societies have justified gender inequalities through cultural patriarchy. The believe that the male authority and control has brought about dominance and social inequalities, necessitating social order and economic productivity. According to Godelier (1981) he posits that "it is crucial to pinpoint the real importance, or specific weight, of each social inequality within the hierarchy of causes that shape the functioning and

evolution of our society”. Patriarchy ideology rationalizes exclusion of the female gender from participating actively in political, economic and social roles as men are leaders and providers, and women are relegated to domestic roles and subordinated. Enweonwu, et al (2023) inclined that “culture as a concept is only meaningful in the context of human society. In other words, it presumes existence of human society and is imbued with tools and skills with which the human society is enabled to work”. The cultural defense of patriarchy supports systemic gender-based violence and discrimination. Male superiority in the area of culture portrays inequalities as male dominance has legitimized patriarchy. This could be the reason why Oaikhena (2022), rightly observed that “when an individual is treated equally and given opportunity to express himself, he is able to effectively utilize the talents and resources to improve the living standard of himself and those around”.

In furtherance, religion has also played significant role in cultural patriarchy, as doctrine, institutional structures and practices have given the male gender legitimacy. Religions scriptures and teachings has often defined gender roles as male dominance, while the women are restricted as caregivers. According to Karami (2021) he said that “when human has formed a society culture has also been formed”. The sustainability of cultural patriarchy perpetuates gender inequalities, limiting women from participating in activities or limiting their access to authoritative positions, as they are portrayed as subordinates, passive, and primarily valued for their appearance and nurturing roles. This hegemonic representation supports traditional gender roles, as men are associated with strength, leadership and assertiveness. Female character tends to be sexualized through their physical attractiveness or dependence on men.

In view of these, the study investigates if cultural patriarchy is a weapon deployed towards female gender; and the reasons why women are targets of cultural patriarchy in the society, as women played significant roles in providing for the family and promoting traditional beliefs across society.

Traditional values

Traditional values are long standing beliefs, customs and principles passed down from generation to generation, within a society or cultural environment. These values emphasize what is considered important or admissible in a community. It is from these values that families promote social cohesion, respect for elders, authority to stability and order in the community. These limitations are often upheld by literal interpretations of text associated or pronounced by traditional belief that associate leadership with muscularity. This was why Oaikhena observed that “in a society where there is freedom of belief, freedom of religion, the freedom to hold any opinion and belong to any association of one’s choice, these has to be tolerance”. Meanwhile Udofia (2021) quoting Chukwuemeka Eze, traditional African society has a great assert in its practice of a mode of life called communalism. This used to be the bedrock and the result of the wonderful relationship prevalent in the community as well as the purpose existence of the community and the Africa man.

In Nigeria, cultural patriarchy has seen significant growth in most communities and village settings accompanied by rigid gender roles. While the female gender constitutes the majority in terms of geographical spread, they are largely excluded from leadership roles, and positions. These disparity raises sociological questions about power, culture, and institutional control within cultural spaces. Understanding the roots of gender discrimination or cultural patriarchy within the society requires a sociological lens that considers cultural and traditional experience of women.

This could be the reason why Johnson-Bashua (2020) observed that “African culture has set mold of beliefs and values for women which are not taken lightly neither are they negotiable. Gender relations in Africa has a bearing on familial lines which assigns roles to both sex makes the household duties a woman’s principal responsibility”.

These exclusionary farmwork perpetuates patriarchal structures that limit the agency of women within communities. This leads to diminished self-esteem, restricted social influence, and limited opportunities for personal growth towards leadership roles. Discriminatory practices in communities or within societies often mirror and reinforce broader societal inequalities. Oaikhena rightly observed that “in a society of community

filled with hatred, people begin to feel suffocated and depressed, as discrimination makes miserable lives for not just those discriminated against, but everyone in the society.

Living in a patriarchy society

Despite global and national efforts to promote gender equality, female gender discrimination remains a persistent issue within many cultural communities. In most communities in Africa there is the growing concern over the limited roles and recognition accorded to women in community leadership and decision making. This was why Salisu et al (2024) observed that “literatures has shown that controversy over the proper role of public administration in the political process is just too far from being resolved”. For instance, the Esan women in Edo State, Nigeria, experience cultural patriarchy. Under the Esan customary laws women face significant discrimination, especially in matter of inheritance, succession and burial rites, where the rule of primogenitures often excludes daughters and widows from inheriting properties. According to Enakireru and Edewor (2024), quoting Magbele (2016), they asserted that “customary laws among various tribes in Nigeria typically prohibit women from inheriting the estates of their deceased husbands and fathers. Nonetheless, certain customary laws grant women a limited right to inherit such estates”. Inheritance can be divided into two primary categories: testamentary and intestate. In cases of testamentary inheritance, the deceased has documented their wishes through a formal will, whereas in intestate inheritance, the deceased has passed away without leaving such a document. Property held by an individual can be categorized as either "personal" or "real" property (African Customary and Religious Law Review 1 (2020).

Moreso, during Esan burial ceremonies, gender discrimination is prevalent. Women are excluded from participating in key funeral rites, which is also associated with inheritance. The Esan culture only recognized the male – especially the first-born male child, while daughters and widows are generally barred from certain significant roles. This clearly indicate the notion that men hold authority and social values, while the women are relegated and marginalized in both family and community life. These reinforces the idea that women are less capable of leadership responsibilities and this also

limit them from family resources and social recognition. Additionally, Esan women actively participate in traditional and cultural activities, their access to authoritative positions and policy making roles appears disproportionately restricted. This reality raises critical sociological questions about the institutional structures, cultural norms, and women's right and opportunity that continues to sustain gender inequalities within Africa. According to Mofoluwawo (2014), "discrimination against women is a global phenomenon it is as old as human history".

The prescience of such discrimination undermines the principle of equity, inclusion and community development, potentially discouraging women's full participation and impacting the identity and voice. While accounts are evidence suggesting pattern of marginalization of women in Africa, there is a lack of systematic sociological investigation into the lived experience of women, the power dynamics at play, and the broader implications for social change and cultural practices.

Interrogating the sociological dynamics

Weaponizing patriarchy reinforces male dominance across social structures through legitimate ideological rationalization of gender inequality by attributing it to natural or divine order, justifying men's control over women in family business, politics and society at large. According to Makama (2013) quoting Salaam,2003, "patriarchy justifies the marginalization of women in education, economy, labour market, politics, business, family, domestic matters and inheritance".

Patriarchy imposes power relations hierarchically, as male control the female reproductive system sexually, thus reinforcing male dominance in both private and public sphere of the female gender. Men are also socialized into leadership and dominant roles, while the female folks are relegated to subordinate roles perpetuating unequal power dynamics across social institutions. These social institutions pave the way for maintaining a broader system of oppression, when marginalized women face compounded subjugation, like in the case of Esan women in Edo State as pointed earlier by the study. Compounded subjugation affects women by intensifying their oppression to several social, economic, cultural, political and psychological consequences. As a result, there is

increase in vulnerability, as they are prone to domestic violence sanctioned by societal norms. According to Oaikhena and Osawe (2012), quoting Walter 1972, they observed that “in any given economy, the various components should reflect the well-being of others. As depression in one sector invariably transfer itself to others to some extent”.

In these respect, cultural norms or processes like marriage, burial, etc, often function as mechanism of control, subjecting women to emotional physical and psychological abuse and limitations. Despite being the majority, most times in the community, women are often excluded from meaningful leadership roles. This exclusion not reflects institutional sexism, but also denies women access to authority and voice in the community. The structural discrimination undermines the moral doctrinal direction of their community as they are systematically undervalued, which could lead to emotional psychological distress. Over time, these effects can manifest to depression, self-doubt, and withdrawal from cute participation in social activities. These concerns made Oaikhena et al (2013) to observe that “people become attached to ideas over time through a social-political processes of putting their ideas into good use”.

In view of these, the sociological dynamics began to play a significant role by focusing on how the female gender face oppression embedded and reproduced across social structure, shaping women’s experiences and limiting their opportunities. Women face systematic disadvantages in several important social functions such social cohesion, moral guidance, and community formation. However, when these happens, it disrupts social balance and perpetuate systemic inequality. These symbolic practices construct and reinforces the idea that women are to be submissive and men authoritative. This authority pave way for moral dominance and gender inequality, as men hold primary power and women are largely excluded from full participation in various aspect of life. This has hindered women’s advocacy, leadership, and economic progress.

Empirical evidence has showed that gender discrimination emanates within the society or community that creates multifaceted harm. It marginalizes female voice, undermines mental well-being, and reduces long-term commitment to social institutions. At the same time, gender discrimination in Africa cannot be fully understood without engaging with the social-cultural, historical, and post-colonial dynamics that shapes the

livid realities of African women. It was in support of this assertion that Anna-Sophia (2022) on her seminar paper wrote that “in a patriarchally dominated society, gender positions construct the female role as weak, dark, emotional, domestic, inferior, and passive while the male role is depicted as strong, enlightened, rational, superior, and active”. While Western feminisms often emphasize liberal individualism and gender equality through legal and institutional reforms, Africa feminist theory offer frameworks that are deeply rooted in community, spiritual heritage, motherhood, and resistance to colonial legacies.

Fig: 1 Diagram: The Maputo Protocol of 2024

Source: *Author's design 2025 using the literature*

The Maputo Protocol, formally known as the Protocol to the African Charter on Human and People's Rights on the Rights of Women in African is a comprehensive treaty adopted by the African Union in 2003 to promote and protect women's right across the continent (Wikipedia). The Protocol is widely regarded as one of the most progressive human rights instruments for women globally, addressing both private and public spheres of life.

Thus, the above diagram is a clear indication of the result which could emanate if patriarchy continue to play leading roles in our community. Patriarchy against women manifest as systemic discrimination, oppression, exploitation, and violence, rooted in the historical and cultural enforcement of male dominance across all aspect of society, especially Africa. It establishes a social structure where men hold primary power and authority at the expense of women's agency and well-being.

However, patriarchy puts pressure on men to operate in realms that they may not be gifted for. Thus, men are pressured into leadership roles they are not called to, gifted for, and equipped to fulfil while women who are called, gifted, and equipped are passed over. Women are envisioned as "temptresses," and anything beyond superficial contract is rigorously avoided. Within appropriate boundaries, friendship between men and women (both married or single) can be spiritual and encouraged discipleship. Pursuing gender equality and justice in the society at large will not just benefit women, it will benefit men as well.

Gender-based inequality policies and social welfare programmes

Policies that are restrictive falls under the gender-based inequality and social welfare programmes. These policies limit the rights, resources, and opportunities of women. Restrictive policies, such as those that limit the rights of the female gender, perpetuates inequality by reinforcing social norms and power structures that prevent one gender from another. This could be why Oaikhena (2023) wrote that "it is the duty of society to prevent the strong, greedy, and unscrupulous individuals from exploiting the weak and over-enriching themselves at their expense"

The female gender integrates spiritual material, and communal values, which are deeply embedded in Africa societies, offering a culturally sensitive framework for social welfare and change. Women provides a valuable epistemological tool for gender studies, postcolonial theory, and cultural studies. Disparities that exist in various aspects of life limits women access to opportunities and resources. Inequalities affecting feminism in Africa pave way for economic growth that undermine human rights and sustainable development and progress necessitating ongoing efforts towards policy programmes. These programmes typically focus on economic empowerment, education, legal reforms, access to healthcare and political participation. Initiatives such as these promotes gender participation and the dismantling of systematic barriers. Systematic barriers significantly impact the welfare of women through the creation of inequalities across economic, social, cultural and political spheres. These barriers are often embedded in institution, policies, societal norms and practices. They distort opportunities for women and hinders them from decision making power and restrict their ability to support themselves and their families. Social injustice prevents transformation and economic development (Oaikhena, 2024).

As a result, deep-rooted stereotypes and cultural expectations confine women to traditional roles centered on domesticity and ecological justice. The fact that women are often underrepresented in political and leadership positions, limits their influence on policies and decision-making process affecting their welfare. The principle of fairness and fair representation in the distribution of environmental benefits and burdens, ensure that no person suffer from environmental harm or excluded from environmental benefits. Restrictive policies according to the study paved way for women to be unfortunately treated and perceived as marginalized groups in the environment or communities, as their voices are not amplified in decision – making processes and environmental programs or policies.

The welfare of women in social programs promote the economic, social and health needs through various interventions. Such interventions usually empower women, improve healthcare, enhance financial independence, and also provide social protection. Through these means, positive impact such as increased incomes, assets ownership and

reduced dependency on begging or exploitation. As a result, welfare programs for women emphasize a strong evaluation of framework to adopt and improve interventions continually, to ensuring that women benefit substantially.

Feminism theory as framework for analysis

This theory does not merely critique gender oppression, but also seek to reframe womanhood in African terms, thereby resisting both indigenous patriarchy and imported colonial ideologies. The relevance lies in its' ability to offer culturally grounded solutions to gender-based inequality, tailored to the African socio-political landscape. The early propounders of the feminist theory was Mary Wollstonecraft, whose influential work "A vindication of the Right of Women" was published in 1792, advocating for women's education and equality (Wikipedia). The feminist theory critiques patriarchal systems that uphold male dominance and challenge the exclusion of women from leadership and decision-making with the society. According to Benda (2008) wrote that "instruments to tackle specific elements of discrimination include the 1967 Declaration on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women which predated to the women's convention otherwise known as Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW)".

The adoption of the feminist theory by the study is borne out of the fact that it analyses gender-based discrimination in the society. This theory aims to understand gender inequality as it encompasses ideas from diverse disciplines, exploring how social structures, power dynamics and cultural norms contributes to women's oppression and inequality. The evolvment of this theory largely emerges from the 18th century onward, notably influenced by Mary Wollstonecraft. The growth of this theory in 1960s and 1970s focused on social and cultural inequalities in addition to political rights.

Issued highlighted in this study clearly shows that patriarchy, gender roles, discrimination and inequality with various branches including liberal, radical, postcolonial, and black feminism. As clearly outlined by this theory, the perspective focused primarily on women's experiences, and potentially neglecting men's viewpoints. The inequalities and cultural differences where women still face significant restrictions

which can alienate men and some women who might otherwise support gender equality, creating polarization rather than dialogue. According to Otto (2022) the principles of non-discrimination is often not respected, frequently in the area of women's right.

The study's critiques within feminisms, challenges each other's assumptions and approaches, sometimes resulting in disagreement over priorities and methodology, that the focus on critique itself can become counterproductive or self-limiting, with calls for feminism to move beyond constant criticism or existing systems towards new positive frameworks.

In furtherance, the feminist theorist highlights how the marginalization of women in the society contributes to their psychological alienation and social disempowerment. According to Kwork Pui-lan (2025) "feminist theology must take seriously the lived experienced of women, particularly those from post-colonial and minority contest, to unmask the layers forms of discrimination of theological language, liturgy, and to reflect equality and inclusiveness. The principles of equality and non-discrimination forms the basis of all human rights instruments and cut across all the rights found within human rights treaties influenced both the interpretation and of rights (Vandenhole, 2005).

Understanding the effect of discrimination against the female gender requires examining how power, social roles, identity, and learning interest within social institutions. By the application of the feminist theory, it can be deduced that deeper understanding of how discrimination is sustained and how it can be dismantled. Such analysis is essential for advocating for justice, equity and full inclusion within the society. This dual marginalization has had many women to seek alternative space when their leadership is affirmed. This could be the reason why Oaikhena (2021) asserted that "fighting poverty requires direct policy interventions. Considering the fact that African countries are less effective in reaching their poor citizens". The theory of feminism faces criticisms about inclusivity, focus, representation, and strategic approach. The intersection of gender, race, class, and colonialism, upholds communalism and the centrality of the family. Unlike mainstream feminism that often centers on individual

liberation, African women emphasize harmony between men and women communal survival, and cultural relevance.

Summary and Conclusion

The female gender integrates spiritual, material, and communal values, which are deeply embedded in African societies, offering a culturally sensitives framework for social welfare and change. The study emphasize that women provide a valuable epistemological tool for gender studies, postcolonial theory, and cultural studies. It is acknowledged that the intersectional identities of African women shaped by globalization, race, colonialism, socio-economic class, argues that gender discrimination must be addressed across Africa. As a result, women are given lower responsibilities compared to men. Discrimination against the female folks has historically reinforced broader societal gender inequalities by legitimizing male authority in both cultural and traditional spheres. The studies shows that women with strong political or cultural values are less likely to hold leadership positions especially in corporate leadership and traditional roles, as they encounter gender barriers. These challenges have made it difficult for reforms to take place, even in denominations that claim to support gender justice.

In addition to analyzing the characteristics of gender inequality in Africa, this paper empirically studied the key drivers of gender equality in our society as it affects the well-being of people generally. It also draws out important policy implications for African countries. The model is estimated by Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method with country fixed effects. Therefore, a deeper understanding of the key determinants of gender equality in Africa is crucial for implementing effective policies to make Africa society more inclusive for economic and social development so as to reap its benefits. The study also revealed that inequality exacerbate social tension, violence against women and increased vulnerability.

Recommendations

- a. Women's participation in decision-making processes should be increased and promoted;
- b. Women's leadership in communities, organizations, and economic activities to ensure their voices are heard and their needs addressed;
- c. Need for skill development particularly in rural areas and informal sectors;
- d. Policy reforms should be advocated to dismantle patriarchy in Africa;
- e. There should be social and cultural change through campaign awareness and education programmes to shift social norms and foster equality in communities.

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COVID-19 VACCINATION SAFETY AMONG GUIDANCE AND COUNSELLING STUDENTS OF AMBROSE ALLI UNIVERSITY, EKPOMA, EDO STATE.

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Abstract

The study investigated issues of COVID-19 vaccination safety among Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, as well as the perceived benefits of the COVID-19 vaccine among the students. The study adopted the descriptive method of research design. The population consisted of all 131 Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University. Since the sample size was small, the entire population was used as the sample. Hence, no sampling technique was employed to draw a sample from the students. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire. Based on findings, the researcher concluded by suggesting that students of Ambrose Alli University are aware of COVID-19, the risk factors associated with contracting it, and the preventive measures required to avoid infection.

Keywords: Covid-19, Counselling Students, Vaccines, Diseases

Introduction

Coronavirus disease (COVID-19), a rapidly spreading respiratory viral illness with significant morbidity and fatality rates, has dominated public health debates throughout the world. Since 2019, the disease has swiftly expanded, assisted mostly by international air travel, to encompass every area of the world, forcing the World Health Organization (WHO) to declare a global COVID-19 pandemic on 30th January, 2020. It continues to pose a significant danger to global public health (Hyland et al., 2021). As observed by Oaikhena and Aligbe, (2023), "it is the duty of society to prevent the strong, greedy, and

unscrupulous individuals from exploiting the weak and over-enriching themselves at their expense”.

Coronavirus, a respiratory tract illness considered to have been transmitted initially from animals to people at Wuhan, China—other schools of thought say a laboratory leak, which has symptoms that include fever with high or low grade, and cough. This is generally from persistent body weakness, headache, and vomiting in some cases (Dolgin, 2021). Contact with cough droplets, which might be on the hands of cough sufferers or resting on surfaces such as door handles, in some circumstances, touching the face, nose, and mouth with the same hands, is known to transmit it. Over 273 million cases and 5.3 million fatalities from COVID-19 and associated disorders had been documented globally as of 21st December (WHO, 2021). With a rising number of cases and deaths worldwide, there was a global panic, and the WHO quickly proposed preventive means to curb the disease’s spread. This could be the reason why Oaikhena and Aligbe (2023) posit that “to overcome limitations, government and individuals have to render their co-operation to group efforts, so that together they could achieve more and meet target group demands”.

In view of these, regular handwashing/hand sanitizing, maintaining social distance of at least 6 meters apart, regular disinfecting of surfaces, especially in public areas, wearing of face masks, especially in public, isolation of suspected people, widespread availability of testing facilities, and counselling and testing when feeling symptoms was advised. The COVID-19 pandemic remains a major problem among the world to date. There are reports of increasing numbers of unexplained deaths in various communities in the country (Elimian et al., 2024), but the extent to which these are related to the COVID-19 pandemic has not been systematically investigated. It is not clear how various groups in the country perceive individual and group risks for the virus, and how they have responded to various interventions designed to mitigate the infection.

The release of safe and effective COVID-19 vaccinations by multiple pharmaceutical firms in 2020 marked a significant milestone. Vaccination was thus highlighted as a vital, game-changing instrument in the battle against COVID-19, with a focus on equitable global access to vaccination (WHO, 2020). This comment emphasized

that despite the availability of vaccinations, there must be equal access to them and a desire to take them, which must be equitably shared and accepted around the world, because vaccines will not halt the pandemic, but immunization would (WHO, 2020).

Vaccines have previously been used with great effectiveness to help prevent the spread or eliminate the severity of illness all around the world. It is a normal practice in many countries to administer immunizations to newborns at birth in order to avoid endemic illnesses. This method has been shown to reduce the spread, severity, and incidence of certain endemic diseases (Briisow, 2021). However, successes in the field of children's immunization did not occur without early hurdles of hesitation, which were exacerbated by misconceptions, misinformation, and disinformation. Currently, there is a sizeable anti-vaccine group whose beliefs are based on the notion that vaccinations are hazardous—issues bolstered by misconceptions and conspiracy theories surrounding vaccination (Lodish, 2000).

Statement of the Problem

The COVID-19 vaccine has raised several issues among students and people in the public domain. Issues of vaccine safety in relation to the reproductive and mental health of people. Some questioned whether the producers of the vaccine may have hurriedly developed the vaccines to make more money and in doing so produced something hazardous that could cause more harm than good to human health. According to Oaikhena (2021) he rightly observed that, "the lack of formal economic opportunities, combined with the legacy of entrenched political conflicts and instability, as well as the rise of Covid-19 pandemic, high rates of malnutrition, illness, and poor education, poses many challenges on the African continent".

Vaccine was also considered as religion based which heightened the fears of some people in the society. Church leaders such as Pastor Chris Oyakhilome openly stated that "the COVID-19 and the vaccine is a devil's scam at the church to suppress the faith of believers" (Ilesanme & Afolabi, 2020). It is against these backdrop that this study examined salient issues that mitigated COVID-19 vaccination safety amongst Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State.

Purpose of the Study

The main concern of this study is to examine the issues of COVID-19 vaccination; to examine the need for the COVID-19 vaccine; to examine the issues of COVID-19 vaccine safety; and to examine the benefits of the COVID-19 vaccine among Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study: i) What are the issues on the need for the COVID-19 vaccine among Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State? ii) What are the issues of COVID-19 vaccine safety among Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State? iii) What are the issues concerning the benefits of the COVID-19 vaccine among Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State?

Design of the Study

This study adopted the descriptive study design. Sekaran (2013) defined descriptive survey research as one in which information is collected without changing the environment or manipulating the variables of the study. He noted that it is a research design in which the researcher interacts with the participants through interviews or questionnaires to collect the necessary information. This design was employed in the study because the variables are not manipulated under controlled environmental or laboratory conditions. However, data collected from Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University would be presented in their natural setting to draw inferences.

Population

The population of the study consists of all 131 Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State. These comprised of 24 students in 100

level, 19 students in 200 level, 56 in 300 level, and 32 in 400 level, in the Department of Guidance and Counselling, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State.

Sampling

A sample of 131 Guidance and Counselling students was drawn. Since the sample size is relatively small and from a finite population, the entire population was used as the sample. Hence, no sampling technique was employed to draw the sample.

Instrument

The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire developed by the researcher. The instrument was titled: *Issues of COVID-19 Survey Questionnaire (ICSQ)*. The instrument was divided into Sections A and B.

Section A contains information on the personal data of students, that is, sex, and age bracket of the students. While section B contains item statements bordering on the subject focus of the study, that is, issues of COVID-19 vaccination (items 11–15). Each item was rated on a four-point Likert scale: Strongly Agree – 4; Agree – 3; Disagree – 2; Strongly Disagree – 1.

Validity and reliability of study

The face and content validity of the instrument was carried out by the researcher and two other experts in the Department of Guidance and Counselling, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma. Copies of the questionnaire were presented to them for corrections, and the amendments made were incorporated into the final draft to ensure the contents of the instrument were clear and relevant.

The test-retest reliability method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument. This procedure was carried out by administering copies of the instrument to 30 students outside the study sample, within the study area. After a few weeks, the same instrument was re-administered to the same respondents. Their responses in the first and second tests were correlated using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation technique. The

result of the coefficient is expected to produce an r -value of 0.70 or higher, to show that the instrument is reliable.

Data Analysis

Research Questions 1, 2, and 3 were analyzed using the mean (\bar{x}) and standard deviation (S.D.). A mean score of 2.50 was used as the criterion mean for determining students' perception of the issues. This was obtained by adding the four Likert scale points (Strongly Agree – 4, Agree – 3, Disagree – 2, and Strongly Disagree – 1) and dividing the sum (10) by the total number of scale options (4), giving 2.50. The research questions were analyzed with the aid of the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), IBM Version 20.

S/N	Item statements	X	S.D	Remarks
1.	COVID-19 is a scam and not real	2.71	1.040	Agreed
2.	COVID-19 is as infectious as many claim	2.69	.968	Agreed
3.	COVID-19 is a strategy of the government to loot public funds	2.36	1.041	Disagreed
4.	COVID-19 is dead and does not exist anymore	2.25	1.011	Disagreed
5.	I do not believe I can be affected with COVID-19	2.41	1.028	Disagreed

Results

Research question 1: What are the issues on the need for COVID-19 vaccine among guidance and counselling students of Ambrose Alli University Ekpoma Edo State?

Table 1: *Mean and standard score on the issues on the Need for COVID-19 vaccine among guidance and counselling students of Ambrose Alli University Ekpoma Edo State.*

Overall mean score= 2.42

Significant mean $x > 2.50$

Results in *Table 1* showed that students have the awareness on items 1 and 2 at a mean score range of 2.69 and to 2.71 respectively. The overall mean score of 2.63 is lesser than the criterion mean of 2.50 (i.e. $X = 2.42 < 2.50$). Hence the result showed that COVID-19 is a scam and not real and COVID-19 is as infectious as many claims are the issues on the need for COVID-19 vaccine among guidance and counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State.

Research question 2: what are the issues of COVID-19 vaccine safety among guidance and counselling students of Ambrose Alli University Ekpoma, Edo State

Table 2: *mean and standard score on issues of COVID-19 vaccine safety among guidance and counselling students of Ambrose Alli University Ekpoma Edo State*

S/N	Issues of COVID-19 safety	X	S.D	Remarks
1.	I think taking COVID-19 vaccine is taking the harmful virus itself	2.64*	1.068	Agreed
2.	I think the vaccine will give me the sign of the antichrist that us against my religion	2.59*	1.089	Agreed
3	I think the vaccine has a microchip designed to control me after sometime	2.62*	1.149	Agreed
4	Taking the vaccine will bring about a side effect sooner or later	2.58	1.170	Agreed
5	The reports of other that have taken it is not good enough to encourage acceptance	2.28	.988	Disagreed
	Overall mean score= 2.64			

Significant mean ($x \geq 2.50$)

Results in Table 2 showed that students agreed with Item 1, 2, 3, and 4 at a mean score ranging from 2.58 to 2.6, while they disagreed on Item 5 at a mean score of 2.8, respectively. The overall mean score of 2.64 is greater than the criterion mean of 2.50 (i.e.

$X = 2.64 > 2.50$). Hence, the result showed that respondents think taking the COVID-19 vaccine is equivalent to taking the harmful virus itself; that the vaccine has a microchip designed to control them after some time; and that taking the vaccine will bring about a side effect sooner or later. These are the issues of COVID-19 vaccine safety among Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State.

Research Question 3: What are the issues on the benefits of the COVID-19 vaccine among Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation score on the Benefits of COVID-19 vaccine among guidance and counselling students of Ambrose Alli University Ekpoma Edo State.

S/N	ITEMS	X	S.D	REMARKS
1.	Us live without fear of staying in social gathering with people	2.72	1.014	Agreed
2	Reduce the spread of the virus from person to person	2.75	1.062	Agreed
3.	Reduce the health damage caused by the virus	2.57	1.062	Agreed
4.	Reduce the fear if contracting the virus by handshake	2.62	.976	Agreed
5.	Reduce the fear of contracting the virus by touching items in publicity used facilities	2.71	.909	Agreed
	Overall mean score= 2.53			

Significant $y(x > 2.50)$

Discussions

Findings from the study were discussed under the following sub-headings:

- The issues on the need for the COVID-19 vaccine
- The issues of COVID-19 vaccine safety
- The issues on the benefits of the COVID-19 vaccine

The Issues on the Need for the COVID-19 Vaccine:

The result showed that the belief that COVID-19 is a scam and not real, and that it is not as infectious as many claim, are the issues surrounding the need for the COVID-19 vaccine among Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State. The result is in line with that of Claide et al. (2021), who found that prior vaccination views and anxiety about the pace of testing and licensing of vaccines were the most predictive variables (p.007). Multivariate analysis confirmed these findings, while additionally revealing that perceived personal risk was significant ($P = 0.033$). The result also corroborates the findings of Shahid et al. (2021), who revealed that 52% and 48% of hospital employees, respectively, were willing and refused the corona vaccine. This study is notable for its use of mixed methodologies, including qualitative approaches to analyze socio-demographic effects and evaluate issues.

The result agreed with that of Amirhossein et al. (2021), who found relationships between female gender, higher age, and higher education and knowledge, attitude, and practice of Iranians during the COVID-19 pandemic, and vaccine approval. The result supported that of Dzieciolowka et al. (2021), who stated that the novelty of the vaccination, the desire for others to have it first, and limited time for decision-making were all reasons for rejection. The result is in consonance with that of Efani et al. (2020), who revealed a substantial relationship between female gender, older age, and greater education with knowledge, attitude, and practice.

The Issues of COVID-19 Vaccine Safety:

The result showed that respondents think taking the COVID-19 vaccine is equivalent to taking the harmful virus itself; that the vaccine will give them the sign of the Antichrist, which is against their religion; that the vaccine has a microchip designed to control them after some time; and that taking the vaccine will bring about side effects sooner or later. These are the issues of COVID-19 vaccine safety among Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State. This could be the reason why Oaikhena (2023) observed that “it is attributable to the characteristics of individuals and populations to deal with the primordial objective of surviving”.

The Issues on the Benefits of the COVID-19 Vaccine:

The result showed that living without fear of being in social gatherings with people, reducing the spread of the virus from person to person, reducing the health damage caused by the virus, reducing the fear of contracting the virus through handshakes, and reducing the fear of contracting the virus by touching items in publicly used facilities are among the issues on the benefits of the COVID-19 vaccine among Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State.

Results in Table 3 showed that students agreed on items 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 at a mean score ranging from 2.57 to 2.75, respectively. The overall mean score of 2.53 is greater than the criterion mean of 2.50 (i.e. $\bar{x} = 2.53 > 2.50$). Hence, the result showed that living without fear of being in social gatherings with people, reducing the spread of the virus from person to person, reducing the health damage caused by the virus, and reducing the fear of contracting the virus through touching items in publicly used facilities are the issues on the benefits of the COVID-19 vaccine among Guidance and Counselling students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study concluded that students in secondary schools are aware of COVID-19 in Esan West Local Government Area of Edo State. Students are also aware that risk factors for contracting COVID-19 include rubbing hands on frequently touched

surfaces, staying in close contact with infected persons, shaking hands with infected persons, ignoring the use of nose masks, and maintaining social closeness with people in crowded places. While practicing hand washing with clean water and soap, avoiding shaking hands with people, covering one's mouth while coughing, self-isolation, and maintaining social distancing are recognized as control strategies for COVID-19 among secondary school students in Esan West Local Government Area of Edo State.

Recommendations

Based on findings from the study, the following were recommended:

1. More emphasis should be placed on updating knowledge regarding the diagnosis and treatment components of the COVID-19 disease. Interactive educational webinars can be conducted, focusing primarily on the pandemic and the disaster management of such infectious diseases.
2. It is imperative to commence early education and training of students to have in-depth knowledge to allay their fears and concerns. This will help change the narrative and their perception, enabling them to become good ambassadors and beacons of advocacy for the vaccine, in order to prevent mortality from the pandemic.

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IMPACT OF POVERTY ALLEVIATION PROGRAMME ON VULNERABLE COMMUNITIES IN EDO STATE: AN OVERVIEW

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Abstract

This study is an overview of the impact of poverty alleviation programs on vulnerable communities in Edo State, Nigeria. It examined the effectiveness of these programs in reducing poverty, improving living standards, and empowering marginalized populations. One of the fundamental problems facing our country today is how to alleviate poverty at the grassroot level where over 70% of Nigerians live. Though Nigeria is a country blessed with abundant mineral and human resources, many Nigerians still find it difficult to live above poverty level. This has led to children of school age, instead of being in school, hawk goods, such as sachet water, bread, groundnut, orange etc, and our young graduates roam the streets without employment. The consequence of the above situation is lack of purchasing power, exposure to risk, high mortality rate, low life expectancy, and insufficient access to social and economic services. The research employs quantitative data for data collection. Studies had revealed that some of these vulnerable communities are being taken advantage off, by most humanitarian agencies, as they end up not doing what was promised. Communities in Edo State are primarily identified within specific Local Government Areas (LGAs) that are considered high risk, especially in relation to human trafficking and socio-economic challenges. These LGAs span across the three senatorial districts: Edo South, Edo Central, and Edo North. Preliminary findings suggests that while poverty alleviation programs have had some positive effects, challenges remain in terms of program reach, sustainability, and targeting of the most vulnerable. The study concludes with recommendations for enhancing the design and implementation of these programs to achieve greater impact and promote inclusive development in Edo State.

Keywords: Poverty alleviation, programmes, communities, vulnerability

Introduction

Poverty remains one of the most pressing challenges confronting Nigeria and its states, including Edo State. Despite Nigeria's significant natural resources and economic potential, a substantial portion of its population continues to live below the poverty line, struggling to meet basic needs such as adequate food, shelter, healthcare, and education. According to Nwaobi (2003) the country is rich but the people are poor. Vulnerable communities comprising women, youths, persons with disabilities, rural inhabitants, and marginalized groups are disproportionately affected by poverty, often facing systemic barriers that hinder their socio-economic development. According to Oaikhena, et al., (2013) "the growing distrust of established and traditional routines and procedures which has failed to provide solutions, demonstrates that a paradigm shift is imperative". In response to these challenges, the Nigerian government, along with various local and international agencies, has implemented numerous poverty alleviation programmes aimed at reducing economic disparities, promoting sustainable development, and empowering vulnerable populations.

In Edo State, these initiatives include social safety nets, microcredit schemes, skills development programmes, conditional cash transfers, and employment stimulation projects. As pointed by Omotola (2008) Nigeria is richly endowed and the country's wealth potentials manifest in the forms of natural, geographical and socio-economic factors, and with that, Nigeria should be one of the richest countries in the world which should have no business with extreme poverty.

While these programmes have shown promise, their actual impact on improving the livelihoods of targeted communities remains a subject of ongoing debate and investigation. Investigating poverty alleviation programmes is highly relevant for several critical reasons; it aids effectiveness and impact assessment as it helps determine whether these programmes are actually reducing poverty and improving the well-being of target populations. For example, studies in Nigeria shows that many poverty alleviation efforts have failed to meet their objectives due to poor implementation, corruption, or misdirected resources. Evaluations can identify what works and what doesn't. Resource optimization also aids governments and agencies have limited resources. Investigations

thus ensure that funds and efforts are efficiently allocated to programmes that deliver measurable benefits, such as employment generation, food security, or education access. By analyzing successes and failures of policies, investigations provide evidence-based recommendations to refine poverty alleviation strategies. Accordingly, strategic policies, becomes written statement of an organization's choices in its operations, whether it is profit or nonprofit oriented agency, chosen to solve society's problems (Oaikhena, 2023)

This is crucial for designing inclusive growth policies that address multidimensional poverty, including income, health, education, and social inclusion. The economic side research shows that poverty alleviation programmes can positively impact economic development by increasing income levels and reducing unemployment, which in turn fosters sustainable growth. Investigations promote accountability by exposing corruption or inefficiencies, ensuring that programmes reach intended beneficiaries and uphold public trust; understanding local contexts and challenges through investigation allows for community-driven and culturally appropriate solutions; and increasing the likelihood of sustainable poverty reduction. Okpe and Abu (2009) laments that “Nigeria had witnessed a very high increase in the level of poverty”.

According to the UNDP Report (2024) Multidimensional Poverty index (MPI) report highlighted severe poverty challenges in Nigeria. It reveals that 63% of Nigerians, or about 133 million people, live in multidimensional poverty as of 2022 data analyzed in the report. Nigeria earned approximately N50.88 trillion from crude oil sales in 2024, based on production of 408.7 million barrels at an average price of \$80.53 per barrel and an exchange rate of N1,546 per dollar (Dare, 2025). Despite all these problems caused by the increasing rate of poverty, the Federal government of Nigeria went ahead to deregulate the economy. Deregulation was a move to increase the price of petroleum products which today is N900 per liter as against proposed reduced rate which has triggered mass discontent and high cost of goods and services, as the negative ripple effects are being felt by the rural poor.

The effectiveness of poverty alleviation efforts in Edo State is crucial for informing policy decisions, optimizing resource allocation, and ensuring that initiatives truly benefit the disadvantaged populations they are designed to serve. Investigating

poverty alleviation programmes is essential to ensure they are effective, efficient, equitable, and contribute to broader economic and social development goals. It supports continuous improvement and accountability, ultimately helping to break the cycle of poverty in a sustainable manner. This research aims to critically examine the extent to which these programmes have alleviated poverty among vulnerable communities in Edo State, identify the challenges faced during implementation, and propose strategies for enhancing their impact. The study hoped to address the following research questions: What types of poverty alleviation programmes are operational in Edo State? have these initiatives impacted the economic and social well-being of vulnerable communities? What challenges hinder their effectiveness? By exploring these research questions, the study endeavors to contribute valuable insights towards designing more inclusive and impactful poverty reduction strategies in Edo State and beyond.

Problems associated with poverty alleviation programmes

Poverty alleviation programs face numerous challenges, including ineffective design and implementation, inadequate funding, corruption, and lack of coordination. These issues can lead to programs failing to reach their intended beneficiaries, resources being misused, and a lack of sustainable impact on poverty reduction. These has impacted negatively on most rural communities. According to Oaikhena and Osawe (2012) they observed that “Governmental authority is legitimately exercised only in accordance with written, publicly disclosed laws adopted and enforced in accordance with established procedure”. Edo state government implements several poverty alleviation programmes, primarily focused on agriculture, education, infrastructure, and social support schemes. Some of the poverty alleviation programs associated with communities in Edo state are as follows:

- a. Edo State Agricultural Development Programme (ESADP): Targets plantain and banana farmers primarily, aiming to improve agricultural productivity and incomes. However, studies have shown limited awareness and effectiveness among farmers, indicating a need for increased funding, extension services, and youth engagement to boost poverty alleviation.

- b. Millennium Development Goals Conditional Cash Transfer Programme: A social safety net initiative providing financial support to vulnerable groups as part of poverty alleviation efforts in the state.
- c. Adult Education Programmes: Adult education is used as a strategic tool to help rural and disadvantaged populations acquire skills for self-reliance and improved livelihoods. These programmes also promote poverty reduction by increasing awareness, providing skills, and encouraging participation in economic activities.
- d. Rural Infrastructure and Development Initiatives: Efforts focus on improving rural accessibility by constructing roads and enhancing facilities, which directly affect poverty reduction by improving market access and transportation. Soft loans to farmers and improved health facilities and rural electrification are part of recommended strategies.
- e. National Programmes implemented locally: Schemes like the Directorate of Food, Roads and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI), National Directorate of Employment (NDE), and Better Life for Rural Women Programme (BLP) have been part of the poverty alleviation framework in Edo state to enhance employment and infrastructure.

Despite government efforts at eradicating poverty with all its intended programmes, Ovwasa (2000) Adesopo, (2000) Omotola (2008) all argued that, all these programmes have failed to achieve the objectives for which they were established by the government. Edo state's poverty alleviation programmes combine agricultural support, cash transfers, adult education, infrastructure development, and other social welfare initiatives. However, challenges such as low awareness, poor funding, and limited access hinder their full impact, calling for integrated improvement efforts by the government and NGOs.

Meanwhile, the above issues and perspectives have not coalesced into a universally relevant participatory poverty alleviation strategy, a number of lines of enquiry or actions are beginning to emerge which gives the strategy some shapes. These include: i) the decentralization of functions and resources to local government thus

strengthening the accountability of local leaders to programme beneficiaries; ii) the development of local level organization of the rural and urban poor as a basic means of their participation; iii) the direct target of productive assets (e.g. credit) at the poor in order to enable them to build a minimum economic base from which they can begin to play more active role in development; iv) donor-led pressure for macro-level reforms and economic and political “rules, customs and procedures, in favour of the poor (Lipton, 1994)

Overview of Poverty Alleviation Programme Strategies in the Past

According to World Bank report (2002) poverty is seen as the inability to attain a minimum standard of living while Aluko (1995) views it as lack of command over basic consumption needs, this arises due to inadequate consumption level, for example lack of sufficient-food, clothing and shelter. Agbi (2011) opined that “poverty in Nigeria is characterized by hunger, homelessness, diseases, malnutrition, high child mortality rate, family disintegration, high rate of unemployment, human trafficking, child labour, kidnapping, sexual assault, drug abuse, prostitution and high mortality rate among others”. She however argued that while majority of Nigerian's wallow in abject poverty, very few individuals live in opulence.

However, in a bid to reduce the increasing rate of poverty in Edo state and Nigeria at large various government (state and local) has adopted one form of poverty alleviation measure or the other but just like every other thing in Nigeria, poverty alleviation programmes have been handled with so much noise that they have yielded little or no result (Agbi, 2011). By way of illustration, the government of Yakubu Gowon, 1972 set up the National Accelerated Food Production Programme (NAFPP) and the Nigerian Agricultural and Cooperative Bank (NACB) aimed at ensuring adequate funding of Agricultural production in the country and in 1976, Gen. Olusegun Obasanjo initiated the Operation Feed the Nation (OFN) which also was geared towards encouraging food production and food security in Nigeria yet the two programmes did not achieve its objectives.

On assumption of office in 1979, as a civilian president of Nigeria, Alhaji Shehu Shagari established the Green Revolution Programme. The programme was aimed at providing more food for Nigerians by reducing importation of food through increasing crop and fibre productions but the programme of empowering the poor farmers by providing them with modern agricultural facilities they needed rather produced overnight elitist farmers who had no business with farming. With the programme, both serving and retired army officers, senior civil servants, business men and politicians used their influence to acquire areas of land and certificate of occupancy in the pretense of wanting to establish a farm.

The programme ended up by widening the gap between the rich and the poor where the rich became richer and the poor becomes poorer. In 1986, General Babangida as Nigerian's Military Head of State, introduced the People's bank aimed at offering soft loans to the masses, and the Directorate of Foods, Roads, and Rural infrastructure which aimed at providing some basic infrastructures to the people on the rural areas so as to reduce rural-urban migration. The programme failed to achieve its objective as it encouraged the diversion of public funds into private pockets. The regime also introduced structural adjustment programme (SAP) and the National Directorate of Employment (NDE) and like every other programme, it failed also to alleviate the suffering of the Nigerian masses as it worsened the socio-economic problem of the people by encouraging income inequality, unequal access to food, shelter, education, health and other necessities of life.

However, in 1993, Late General Sani Abacha in an attempt to alleviate poverty in Nigeria introduced the Family Economic Advancement Programme (FEAP) which gulped over 7 billion without achieving the objectives. Also, the wife of the then President Mrs. Maryam Babangida introduced the Better Life for Rural Women and in 1993 also, the Wife of the Late Sani Abacha introduced the Family Support Programme, all were aimed at alleviating poverty on the assumption that women in Nigeria should have a better deal in the national economy as a result of their contribution towards the growth of the nation as small scale entrepreneurs like every other programme, the programme only

improved the life of their friends and associates while majority of Nigerians wallow in abject poverty.

During President Goodluck Jonathan's administration (2010-2015), several poverty alleviation programs were implemented in Nigeria. The Youth Enterprise with Innovation in Nigeria (YouWIN) was a program aimed to promote entrepreneurship among young Nigerians by providing funding and training to start or expand their businesses. It targeted various sectors and aimed to create jobs and diversify the economy. Another program was Subsidy Reinvestment and Empowerment Program (SURE-P). This program was launched following the partial removal of fuel subsidies. The funds saved were reinvested in critical infrastructure projects, social safety nets, and job creation schemes. SURE-P aimed to mitigate the impact of subsidy removal on vulnerable populations and stimulate economic growth. The Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA) was not solely a poverty alleviation program, but aimed to boost agricultural productivity and income for farmers. By providing improved seeds, fertilizers, and access to credit, the government sought to increase food security and reduce rural poverty. The Conditional Cash Transfer (CCT) Programs was another government program implemented to target pregnant women and new mothers, to improve health and nutrition outcomes. These programs provided cash transfers to beneficiaries who met certain conditions, such as attending antenatal care appointments or immunizing their children.

These programs were implemented with the aim of reducing poverty, creating jobs, and improving the overall standard of living for Nigerians. While they had some successes, they also faced challenges such as corruption, implementation bottlenecks, and limited reach. The era of late President Muhammadu Buhari's administration in Nigeria (2015-2023), several poverty alleviation programs were implemented, with the aim of reducing poverty and improving the living standards of vulnerable populations. It started with the National Social Investment Programme (NSIP). This was a cornerstone of the Buhari administration's poverty reduction efforts. It comprised several sub-programs, including: N-Power: which was aimed at providing young unemployed graduates and non-graduates with skills development and job opportunities. Participants were deployed to various sectors like education, health, and agriculture, and received a monthly stipend.

Conditional Cash Transfer (CCT) Program (Household Uplifting Programme - HUP). Was aimed at provided direct cash transfers to vulnerable households, particularly those with women and children. The goal was to improve household consumption and promote human capital development. Another programme was the Government Enterprise and Empowerment Programme (GEEP). Which offered interest-free loans to small business owners, artisans, and farmers. The program aimed to boost economic activity at the grassroots level. The National Home Grown School Feeding Programme (NHGSFP) was another program that Focused on providing free meals to primary school children, with the objectives of improving school enrollment, attendance, and nutrition, while also supporting local agriculture. Trader Moni and Market Moni., was aimed towards microcredit schemes designed to provide small loans to petty traders and market women to expand their businesses. President Bola Ahmed Tinubu assumed office in May 2023, so any assessment of his poverty alleviation programs is necessarily preliminary. However, we can discuss the initial steps taken and the policy direction signaled by his administration. Early Policy Actions and Signals are:

- a. Fuel Subsidy Removal and its Impact: This is one of the first major decisions which was the removal of fuel subsidies. While intended to free up government revenue and curb corruption, this immediately led to a sharp increase in fuel prices, impacting transportation costs and the prices of goods and services, potentially worsening poverty in the short term.
- b. Cash Transfers and Palliatives: Recognizing the immediate impact of subsidy removal, the Tinubu administration announced plans for cash transfers and other palliative measures to cushion the effect on vulnerable populations. Details of these programs are still being developed and implemented.
- c. Focus on Economic Growth: A key theme of the Tinubu administration is a focus on stimulating economic growth as a means of poverty reduction. This includes efforts to attract foreign investment, improve the business environment, and promote diversification of the economy beyond oil.
- d. Review and Restructuring of Social Investment Programs: There have been indications that the administration plans to review and potentially restructure

existing social investment programs like the NSIP. The aim is likely to improve their effectiveness, transparency, and targeting.

Meanwhile, it's still early in President Tinubu's administration, and the specific details of his poverty alleviation programs are evolving. Observing the design, implementation, and impact of these programs will be crucial to assess their effectiveness in the coming years. Edo State government has over the years implements several poverty alleviation programmes, primarily focused on agriculture, education, infrastructure, and social support schemes. These includes: Edo State Agricultural Development Programme (ESADP), which targets plantain and banana farmers primarily, aiming to improve agricultural productivity and incomes. However, studies have shown limited awareness and effectiveness among farmers, indicating a need for increased funding, extension services, and youth engagement to boost poverty alleviation (Segun, 2003). The Millennium Development Goals Conditional Cash Transfer Programme, is a social safety net initiative providing financial support to vulnerable groups as part of poverty alleviation efforts in the state. while the Adult Education Programmes is used as a strategic tool to help rural and disadvantaged populations acquire skills for self-reliance and improved livelihoods. These programmes also promote poverty reduction by increasing awareness, providing skills, and encouraging participation in economic activities.

Rural Infrastructure and Development Initiatives is an effort focused on improving rural accessibility by constructing roads and enhancing facilities, which directly affect poverty reduction by improving market access and transportation. Soft loans to farmers and improved health facilities and rural electrification are part of recommended strategies. The National Programmes implemented locally fall under the schemes like the Directorate of Food, Roads and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI), National Directorate of Employment (NDE), and Better Life for Rural Women Programme (BLP) have been part of the poverty alleviation framework in Edo state to enhance employment and infrastructure.

NAPEP as a Tool for Alleviating Poverty at the Grassroots

An Appraisal on assumption of office in 1999, the former Nigerian president, Chief Olusegun Obasanjo introduced the National Poverty Eradication Programme which came into being in 2001 with the sole aim of eradicating poverty in Nigeria by 2010. By the policy the president assured Nigerians that unemployment, poor educational system, lack of portable water, poor power generation and supply, poor health care system, lack of basic infrastructure and general insecurity of life and property of all Nigerians will be a thing of the past. Up till today, NAPEP had existed for over 10 years of its implementation but yet, not much progress has been recorded as the situation is still the same if not worse. Today, Nigerians cannot boast of potable water, better health care system, employment generation, security of life and property, etc and a lot of factors are responsible for the inability of NAPEP to achieve its objective of alleviating poverty since its inception.

These factors are: *Corruption*: Corruption has afflicted all segments of the Nigerian society, it means the diversion of revenue for the betterment of the entire masses to the gain of individuals at the expense of the masses. Various forms of corrupt practices in the implementation of NAPEP programmes in Nigeria are manifested in such areas as project finances, diversion of resources, and conversion of public funds to private uses (Okoye and Onyeukwu, 2007). Sometimes some of the programmes are established by various governments in Nigeria as a way of compensating all political associates who have in one way or the other helped them to win an election. As with the case of the National Poverty Eradication Programme, there is total lack of accountability and transparency in the implementation of NAPEP programme, and as a conduct-pipe for draining National resources and as a result poverty is on the high increase in Nigeria, the programme has failed to achieve the purpose for which it was established.

Lack of Sincerity: There is general lack of sincerity of purpose among our leaders who design and implement various poverty alleviation programmes since Nigeria's independence in 1960 as some of them are not committed to the goals of eradicating poverty in Nigeria (Ogunna, 2007). He however posited that since our leaders lack

adequate knowledge of the problems of the poor in Nigeria, it however becomes very difficult for them to achieve the objective. In designing the programmes for eradicating poverty in Nigeria, our leaders are only interested in what they will get from the programme instead of using the programme to help the poor in the society.

Poor Implementation: One of the major challenges which hinder the achievement of objectives of the entire poverty eradication programme in Nigeria including NAPEP is the poor management of resources with its poor maintenance culture common among Nigerians. According to Oaikhena (2024) he argued that “these classes of people selected and recruited into the groups are expected to work closely with the elders in the community, resulting in mutual love, confidence, cooperation and respect. With this therefore, facilities are either not completed or broken down and as well being abandoned. Also lack of involvement of the target group via the poor in both the formulation and implementation of the programmes had posed a serious set back for NAPEP. The programme lacks poor planning, maladministration, poor funding, embezzlement of available fund etc.

Programme Inconsistency: The efficacy of the National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP) has been undermined as a result of constant changes in policy and inconsistent implementation, which hinders the attainment of its objectives. Also, another problem which hinders NAPEP from helping to reduce poverty in Nigeria is that the top management officials of NAPEP who are full time politicians who are only loyal to those who appointed them, and not to utilize the available resources to impact on the lives of the poor in Nigeria.

Politics of Poverty: According to Ovwasa (2000) the politics of poverty is one of the major problems militating against NAPEP in its bid to help reduce poverty in Nigeria. This is because; those who were bestowed with the responsibility of alleviating poverty are the non-poor and are the source of the problem. Adesopo (2008) however lamented that the condition of the poor people in Nigeria have been worsened by the excessive power of those in authority, a situation where a few privileged individual benefits from state generosity, at the expense of the majority who wallow in abject poverty.

Bad Governance: Bad governance is another problem that hinders poverty alleviation programme from alleviating poverty in Nigeria. The UNDP (2010) report posited that the GDP growths rate in Nigeria is a complete opposite of governance indicators, what is obtainable in Nigeria is an era of violence, instability, inconsistency of government policies, government inefficiency, and the recent state of terrorism by members of Boko Haram, ISWAP, banditry, etc., which hinders economic and political stability of the country. These therefore has posed a serious challenge to development and poverty reduction initiatives in Nigeria.

Theoretical framework

Two theories were used for this study, these are human capital theory and social safety theory. These theories offer valuable insights into different approaches for addressing poverty and are often implemented in combination to provide comprehensive support for individuals and communities.

The human capital theory was initially rooted in the ideas of Adams Smith in the 18th century. He emphasized on training and skill development. The theory became popular through the work of Theodore Schuter and Gary Becker in the 50s and 60s, it emphasized the importance of investing in people as a way to improve economic growth and reduce poverty. According to this theory, poverty can be alleviated by enhancing the skills, education, and health of individuals, thus increasing their productivity and earning potential. Programs based on this theory might include educational initiatives, vocational training, healthcare improvements, and other measures that help individuals acquire the skills and knowledge necessary to participate effectively in the economy. The underlying idea is that a more educated and healthier workforce can drive economic progress, which benefits society at large.

While the social safety net theory focuses on the provision of direct support to individuals' families, to cushion them against economic shocks and vulnerabilities. Social safety nets include a range of programs such as unemployment benefits, food assistance, cash transfers, and housing support. The goal is to provide a temporary safety net that prevents individuals and families from falling into deeper poverty during times of

economic hardship. This theory posits that by ensuring a basic level of consumption, individuals and families can maintain their well-being, participate in the economy, and have the stability needed to seek better opportunities.

Summary

The study revealed that Edo state has undertaken a variety of poverty alleviation initiatives aimed at improving the livelihoods of its citizens and fostering sustainable development. These programs ranged from economic empowerment schemes, agricultural support, education and skill development, health interventions, and social safety nets. Analyzing their impacts, it reveals both achievements and areas needing further improvement to ensure the effective reduction of poverty across the state.

According to the study one of the notable successes of Edo state's poverty reduction efforts is the promotion of agricultural productivity through initiatives such as the Edo State Agricultural Development Projects. These programs have enhanced food security, increased income levels among farmers, and created employment opportunities. The provision of farming inputs, training, and access to markets has been instrumental in empowering rural communities, which constitute a significant portion of the state's poor population.

In addition to agriculture, Edo state has implemented vocational training and skill acquisition programs targeting youths and women. These initiatives have helped diversify income sources, reduce dependence on traditional agriculture, and foster entrepreneurial activities. Notable programs like the Edo State Youth Employment and Entrepreneurship Program (EYEEP) have contributed to increased self-employment and reduced urban unemployment rates. Health-related interventions, including expanded access to healthcare services and health education campaigns, have played a critical role in reducing disease burden among impoverished communities. This could be the reason why Oaikhena and Ajagun (2015) posited that “the refusal of a society to acknowledge monumental problems and apply sincere approach in their resolution will not only further polarize the community but also would continue to dangerously promote egocentrism and

retrogression in all facets of the community”. These efforts improve productivity and quality of life, thereby contributing to poverty alleviation. Furthermore, social welfare schemes, such as the N-Power initiative and other direct cash transfer programs, have temporarily increased household income levels and mitigated the adverse effects of poverty. Such programs enhance social protection and provide a safety net for vulnerable populations.

Conclusion

The study has revealed that the impact made by poverty alleviation programmes on the economic and social well-being of vulnerable communities in Edo state has not yielded the desired achievements because of the numerous challenges. As a result, several challenges hinder the full realization of poverty alleviation objectives. Funding constraints, inadequate infrastructure, and corruption have often limited the reach and effectiveness of programs. Many rural communities still lack access to basic social amenities such as clean water, electricity, and healthcare, constraining economic opportunities. There is also a concern regarding the sustainability of these programs. Many initiatives are project-based with limited long-term strategies for maintaining gains after funding concludes.

Finally, the exclusion of marginalized groups and improper targeting have reduced program efficacy, leaving some vulnerable populations unassisted. The study was also quick to note that, challenges are the low level of financial literacy and limited access to financial services among the poor, which restricts their ability to benefit from microfinance and other economic empowerment schemes. There is also a need for better data collection and monitoring systems to evaluate program effectiveness accurately and inform policy adjustments.

Recommendations

Having examined some of the factors that have hindered the impact of poverty alleviation programme on vulnerable communities in Edo state, the following recommendations were made:

- a. To enhance the impact of poverty alleviation programs in Edo state, a multifaceted approach is essential. First, increased investment in infrastructure is necessary to create an enabling environment for economic growth. This includes improved roads, electricity, and healthcare facilities, particularly in rural areas.
- b. Government should emphasize the integration of various programs to create a comprehensive approach that addresses multiple dimensions of poverty simultaneously. This includes combining agricultural support with education, health, and social protection schemes.
- c. Strengthening institutional capacity and promoting transparency and accountability in program implementation will foster greater trust and efficiency. Engaging community stakeholders and beneficiaries in planning and execution will ensure that initiatives are culturally relevant and better aligned with local needs.
- d. Expanding financial inclusion initiatives, such as microfinance and mobile banking, will empower the poor to access credit, save, and invest. This will stimulate entrepreneurship and help build resilient local economies.
- e. Continuous monitoring and impact assessment are vital for measuring success, identifying gaps, and making data-driven improvements. Establishing a centralized data system can facilitate better coordination among agencies and ensure that resources are directed to the most vulnerable groups

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IMPACTS OF POVERTY ALLEVIATION PROGRAMMES IN ESAN WEST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, EDO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This research work was conducted to investigate the impact of poverty alleviation programmes in Esan West Local Government Area of Edo State, South-South region Nigeria. It examined the impact of the programmes on household income, employment opportunities, and living standards of beneficiaries in the region. It identified inadequate funding, corruption, and inefficiencies in programme implementation as major challenges confronting the implementation of poverty alleviation programmes in the South-South region, with Esan West Local Government Area as case study. Research questions and hypotheses were raised to guide the study. The study adopted a survey design which involves the use of structured questionnaire to collect data from diverse groups of respondents, including programme beneficiaries, community leaders, and policymakers. The total population of the study was estimated at one hundred and eighty-eight thousand, seven hundred (188, 700). Taro Yamane formula was used for determining the sample size and response rate of 60% was adopted for analysis. The result of the findings revealed that poverty alleviation programmes have not substantially improved household income among beneficiaries; poverty alleviation programmes were perceived as moderately effective in creating employment opportunities; and skills acquisition initiatives were noted as particularly important in enhancing employability; corruption and mismanagement of funds were rated as significant obstacles. The study recommended that the government should prioritise increased and consistent funding for poverty alleviation programmes; incorporating community members in the planning, implementation, and monitoring of poverty alleviation programmes is crucial.

Keywords: Poverty Alleviation; Poverty Elimination; Poverty Dimension; Human Capital.

Introduction

Poverty remains a major socio-economic issue in Nigeria, despite the country's abundant natural resources and position as Africa's largest economy. The World Bank (2022) estimates about 40% of Nigeria's population lives below the poverty line of \$1 per day, with more classified as living just above it. Various factors contribute to this widespread poverty, including economic instability, high unemployment rates, inadequate infrastructure, and limited access to quality education and healthcare. In rural areas, these issues are often magnified by limited government support and insufficient employment opportunities (International Labour Organisation, 2021).

To combat poverty, the Nigerian government introduced numerous poverty alleviation programmes over the years. Examples include the National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP), launched in 2001, which focuses on areas like youth employment, rural infrastructure development, and social welfare support (Akpan, 2019). Other initiatives, such as the Conditional Cash Transfer programme (CCTP), were created to provide financial aid to low-income households, particularly in rural communities (Oseni, 2020). These programmes are generally impactful as they face various challenges which include insufficient funding, weak infrastructure, and operational inefficiencies (Bello & Oyinlola, 2019).

Within Edo State, and specifically in Esan West Local Government Area (LGA), poverty levels remain high, exacerbated by factors such as limited access to education, healthcare, and employment opportunities. Esan West is primarily rural, with a significant portion of its population reliant on agriculture. However, challenges like limited access to modern agricultural inputs, poor road infrastructure, and inconsistent access to markets restrict the economic productivity of many households (Edo State Bureau of Statistics, 2021).

Poverty alleviation programmes in Esan West Local Government Area is aimed at addressing these barriers, through the provision of financial resources, training, and support to promote self-employment and skills acquisition. This could be the reason why Oaikhena (2021) said that initiative like these "...should be to build an open, efficient,

effective and globally competitive, integrated and collaborative environment in Africa that will facilitate the development and growth of humanitarian investment”. These initiatives often target women, youth, and farmers, who are among the most economically vulnerable. For instance, the N-Power programmes offer skill acquisition and training for young people, enabling them to become self-employed or gain meaningful employment in different sectors (Ojo & Adeyemi, 2021). Despite these efforts, it remains uncertain whether such programmes effectively reduce poverty and improve the living standards of beneficiaries.

Several challenges continue to undermine the potential success of these programmes. Funding limitations, implementation inefficiencies, and issues with accountability have often led to unmet programme objectives and limited reach (Onyeiwu, 2019). Corruption and bureaucratic delays further hinder the timely delivery of resources and support to intended beneficiaries, reducing the effectiveness of poverty alleviation efforts. Additionally, the absence of sufficient data to measure the outcomes of these programmes prevents the government and stakeholders from gaining clear insights into what works and where improvement is needed (Usman, 2020).

This study, therefore, seeks to investigate the effectiveness of poverty alleviation programmes within Esan West Local Government Area by examining their impact on household income, employment levels, and general well-being. It will also assess the challenges that inhibit these programmes’ success and offer recommendations for enhancing their efficacy. Through this analysis, the study aims to provide valuable insights for policymakers, helping to shape more impactful and sustainable poverty alleviation strategies in Esan West and other similar rural communities in Nigeria.

Esan West Local Government Area is a rural administrative region in Edo State, Nigeria, with a population primarily engaged in agricultural activities such as farming and trading. This Local Government Area is characterised by its economic reliance on subsistence agriculture, as well as its infrastructural challenges and limited access to quality healthcare and education services. In this study, Esan West Local Government Area serves as the geographical focus for assessing the impact of poverty alleviation programmes.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this study is built upon the understanding of poverty as a multidimensional phenomenon, the mechanisms and strategies of poverty alleviation programmes, and the indicators used to evaluate their effectiveness. This framework provides a comprehensive basis for investigating poverty alleviation programmes in Esan West Local Government Area of Edo State, Nigeria, offering insights into how these initiatives address the diverse challenges associated with poverty.

Poverty and Its Dimensions

Poverty is among the most pressing challenges impeding global development and human well-being. It is not merely a lack of income but a multidimensional condition characterised by the absence of access to basic human needs, including adequate food, shelter, healthcare, education, and social inclusion. According to the World Bank (2022), poverty is defined in monetary terms as living on less than \$2.15 per day, a benchmark reflecting the minimum income required to sustain a basic standard of living. However, this monetary definition does not fully capture the complexity of poverty, which encompasses social and structural inequalities.

In Nigeria, poverty remains pervasive and entrenched, with over 40% of the population living below the national poverty line as of 2022 (National Bureau of Statistics, 2022). The country's poverty rates vary across regions and demographics, with rural areas experiencing higher levels of deprivation than urban centres. This disparity is often attributed to limited access to essential services, infrastructural deficiencies, and reduced economic opportunities in rural communities. For instance, rural regions frequently lack adequate schools, healthcare facilities, and transportation infrastructure, further isolating these populations from opportunities for upward mobility (Bello & Oyinlola, 2019).

The multidimensional nature of poverty is increasingly recognised in global frameworks such as the global Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI), developed by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) and the Oxford Poverty and Human

Development Initiative. The MPI assesses poverty beyond income, considering deprivations in health, education, and living standards. These dimensions provide a more holistic view of poverty and highlight its deep interconnections with social, economic, and institutional factors (UNDP, 2021). Thus, agencies are putting measures in place to manage and focus on concerned groups, for the purpose of getting results from target groups by deploying resources for efficient and effective development of collaborative partnership with interested parties or stakeholders (Oaikhena and Aligbe, 2023).

Challenges of poverty alleviation programmes in Nigeria

Despite their significant potential to reduce poverty and improve living conditions, poverty alleviation programmes in Nigeria encounter numerous challenges that undermine their effectiveness. These challenges are multifaceted, stemming from systemic issues such as corruption, inadequate funding, poor targeting, and logistical inefficiencies. Addressing these obstacles is essential to maximise the impact of such programmes and ensure they reach the intended beneficiaries.

One of the most pervasive challenges is corruption and mismanagement, which have deeply rooted impacts on poverty alleviation initiatives. Corruption leads to the diversion of resources intended for beneficiaries, undermining public trust and reducing the effectiveness of these programmes. For instance, funds allocated for skill acquisition schemes or cash transfers are often misappropriated, depriving vulnerable groups of the support they need. Bello and Oyinlola (2019) argue that corruption in Nigeria not only diminishes the impact of these interventions but also creates a sense of disillusionment among citizens, discouraging participation in government-led initiatives.

Another critical issue is inadequate funding, which limits the scope and scale of poverty alleviation programmes. Many initiatives are underfunded, reducing their capacity to reach all targeted populations, especially in rural areas where poverty is most concentrated. Budgetary constraints often lead to incomplete projects, poorly maintained infrastructure, and insufficient support for beneficiaries. Usman (2020) opines that even when programmes are well-designed, financial shortfalls can severely hamper their implementation resulting in fragmented and unsustainable outcomes. A related challenge

is the poor targeting of beneficiaries, which undermines the fundamental goal of poverty alleviation programmes to assist the most vulnerable populations. Weak data systems, limited transparency, and political interference often result in the exclusion of eligible beneficiaries while including non-eligible individuals. This could be the reason why Oaikhena (2021) opined that “social protection is essential in addressing not only monetary poverty but also social exclusion”. For instance, programmes intended for low-income households may inadvertently benefit wealthier individuals due to inaccurate beneficiary identification processes (Akpan, 2019). This inefficiency not only wastes resources but also perpetuates inequality by failing to address the needs of the most disadvantaged groups.

Logistical and administrative challenges further compound the inefficiencies of poverty alleviation programmes. Delays in the disbursement of funds and materials, poor coordination among implementing agencies, and bureaucratic bottlenecks significantly hinder programme execution. These issues create inefficiencies that reduce the effectiveness of interventions and frustrate beneficiaries. Onyeiwu (2019) notes that such administrative inefficiencies often result in delays that diminish the intended benefits of programmes, particularly those aimed at providing timely support, such as agricultural inputs or conditional cash transfers. In addition to these systemic issues, poverty alleviation programmes in Nigeria also face challenges related to infrastructure and governance. Many rural areas lack the basic infrastructure required to support programme implementation, such as roads, reliable electricity, and communication networks. This not only increases the cost of delivering services but also limits the ability of beneficiaries to access and utilise programme resources effectively. Moreover, weak governance structures and the absence of accountability mechanisms exacerbate these challenges, allowing inefficiencies to persist unchecked (Babatunde et al., 2021).

The socio-political context in Nigeria further complicates poverty alleviation efforts. Ethnic and regional tensions, coupled with political interference, often result in an unequal distribution of resources. Programmes may be skewed in favour of politically connected individuals or regions, creating disparities in access to support. This politicisation of poverty alleviation efforts undermines their credibility and effectiveness,

leaving many deserving communities underserve. According to Oaikhena and Idehen (2021) they opined that “local government as a third-tier system of government in Nigeria was established to bring government closer to the people at the grass-root level”. Therefore, poverty alleviation programmes in Nigeria are critical tools for addressing widespread poverty, their impact is significantly diminished by challenges such as corruption, inadequate funding, poor targeting, and logistical inefficiencies. Addressing these obstacles requires comprehensive reforms, including improved transparency, better resource allocation, enhanced beneficiary identification systems, and stronger governance mechanisms. Only through such measures can poverty alleviation programmes fulfil their potential to uplift vulnerable populations and contribute to sustainable development in Nigeria.

Indicators of programme success

Evaluating the effectiveness of poverty alleviation programmes is crucial to determining their impact and sustainability. A successful programme can be identified by its ability to achieve its intended goals and deliver measurable outcomes that improve the quality of life for beneficiaries. The key indicators of programme success include household income, employment rates, living standards, social inclusion, and programme sustainability. These indicators provide a comprehensive framework for assessing the short- and long-term impacts of poverty alleviation initiatives in Nigeria, particularly in Esan West Local Government Area.

Theoretical Framework

A theoretical framework serves as the foundation for understanding and analysing the principles and mechanisms underlying poverty alleviation efforts. For this study, the Sustainable Livelihood Framework (SLF), Human Capital Theory, and Social Capital Theory provide critical perspectives on how poverty alleviation programmes can empower communities, foster development, and address the multifaceted challenges of poverty. These theories highlight different aspects of poverty and guide the design and evaluation of intervention programmes.

a. Sustainable Livelihood Framework (SLF)

The Sustainable Livelihood Framework (SLF), introduced by Chambers and Conway (1992), provides a comprehensive understanding of poverty by emphasising the resources and capabilities that individuals and households use to sustain their well-being. Unlike traditional income-based measures of poverty, the SLF recognises the multidimensional nature of livelihoods and the factors that enhance or hinder people's ability to sustain themselves. The SLF identifies five categories of livelihood assets that are critical to poverty reduction and they include human capital (skills, knowledge, and health), social capital (networks and relationships), natural capital (land, water, and biodiversity), physical capital (infrastructure and tools), and financial capital (income, savings, and credit). The framework also considers the vulnerability context, which includes economic shocks, climate variability, and other external pressures that exacerbate poverty. Policies, institutions, and processes are highlighted as essential components that influence access to assets and the effectiveness of livelihood strategies.

This framework is highly relevant to poverty alleviation programmes in Esan West Local Government Area, where many residents rely on subsistence farming and face infrastructure deficits. For example, interventions like rural infrastructure development under the National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP) aim to strengthen physical and natural capital by improving access to irrigation, roads, and markets. Similarly, skill acquisition initiatives contribute to human capital development, enabling individuals to diversify their income sources and build resilience against external shocks. Focusing on the interplay between assets, vulnerabilities, and institutional support, the SLF provides a holistic perspective on poverty reduction. It emphasises that effective poverty alleviation requires enhancing access to diverse assets, addressing systemic inequalities, and empowering communities to adapt to changing circumstances.

b. Human Capital Theory

Human Capital Theory, popularised by Becker (1993), underscores the importance of investments in education, skills, and health for enhancing productivity and economic outcomes. This theory posits that individuals are assets whose economic potential can be increased through proper investments in their capabilities. It links individual development to broader economic growth and poverty reduction efforts, providing a foundation for understanding how poverty alleviation programmes create long-term value.

According to this theory, education and skills acquisition are central to improving economic productivity. By equipping individuals with knowledge and technical skills, they become more competitive in the labour market and are better positioned to secure higher-paying jobs. Similarly, health is considered a crucial component of human capital, as healthier individuals are more productive and less likely to face financial hardships due to medical expenses or work incapacitation. Poverty alleviation programmes that align with Human Capital Theory often focus on building individual capacities. For instance, skill acquisition initiatives like the Youth Empowerment Scheme (YES) and the N-Power programme provide training in vocational and entrepreneurial skills, enabling beneficiaries to transition from unemployment to self-reliance. Additionally, healthcare-focused initiatives such as Conditional Cash Transfers (CCTs) that require beneficiaries to visit healthcare facilities address immediate health needs while fostering long-term productivity.

In Esan West Local Government Area, where limited access to quality education and healthcare perpetuates poverty, programmes that invest in human capital are particularly vital. By empowering individuals with the tools and resources to improve their circumstances, these initiatives contribute not only to individual welfare but also to the overall economic development of the region. This could be the reason why Oaikhena and Ikhayere (2023) observed that “an underdeveloped society or country is characterized by backwardness, primitiveness, tribalism, dependency, neo-colonialism, non-liberalism,

exploitation, late capitalism, lack of modern differentiated industries, state of poverty in the society, the domination of foreign capital in the hands of foreign and local bourgeoisie or local comprador, low technology, low level politics, including social and cultural development”.

c. Social Capital Theory

Social Capital Theory, as popularised by Putnam (2000), highlights the value derived from relationships, networks, and trust within communities. This theory emphasises that social connections facilitate cooperation and collective action, which are critical for achieving development goals. Unlike the other theories that focus primarily on individual resources and capabilities, Social Capital Theory underscores the role of community dynamics and social structures in poverty alleviation. The theory identifies networks, trust, and reciprocity as core elements of social capital. Networks provide access to resources, information, and opportunities that individuals might not otherwise have. Trust fosters cooperation and reduces transaction costs in economic and social interactions, while reciprocity promotes mutual support and resource sharing among community members.

Social Capital Theory is particularly relevant to poverty alleviation programmes that rely on community participation and collaboration. For example, microfinance initiatives that encourage group lending depend on social capital to ensure accountability and mutual support among participants. Similarly, cooperative farming schemes and community-based development projects leverage social networks to pool resources, share knowledge, and achieve common goals. These approaches are especially effective in rural areas like Esan West Local Government Area, where community ties often play a significant role in livelihood strategies.

Research Methodology

The research adopts a survey design to investigate the effect of poverty alleviation programmes in Esan West Local Government Area of Edo State. This design involves the use of structured questionnaire to collect data from a diverse group of respondents, including programme beneficiaries, community leaders, and policymakers. The survey approach is appropriate for this study as it allows for the collection of quantitative and qualitative data, enabling a comprehensive analysis of the programmes' outcomes.

The primary objective of this study is to evaluate the extent to which poverty alleviation programmes have addressed the multidimensional aspects of poverty in Esan West Local Government Area over the period 1999–2023 (24 years). By employing a survey design, the researchers gathered first-hand accounts of how these programmes have impacted income levels, employment opportunities, educational access, and living conditions. The data collected provided a nuanced understanding of the programmes' successes and the challenges faced during implementation.

This methodology ensures the reliability and validity of the research findings by employing systematic data collection and analysis techniques. The insights derived from this study would inform policymakers and development practitioners on strategies to improve the design and implementation of poverty alleviation programmes. The recommendations would aim to enhance the effectiveness, sustainability, and inclusivity of these programmes, thereby contributing to the broader goal of poverty reduction in Esan West Local Government Area and similar contexts across Nigeria.

The population for this research encompasses individuals or entities that meet the criteria for inclusion in the study (Adeosun & Udabah, 2017). The total population consists of residents and stakeholders in Esan West Local Government Area (LGA) of Edo State, estimated at one hundred and eighty-eight thousand seven hundred (188,700) (https://citypopulation.de/en/nigeria/admin/NGA012_edo/). As it focused on individuals such as beneficiaries of poverty alleviation programmes, local community leaders, programme facilitators, and government officials involved in implementation. These individuals provided critical insights into the design, implementation, and outcomes of

poverty alleviation programmes in the area. By examining their experiences, the study aims to uncover the effectiveness of these programmes in reducing poverty and improving the socioeconomic well-being of residents in Esan West Local Government Area. Given the large and diverse population of Esan West Local Government Area and the constraints of time and resources, a sample of 239 participants was selected. This sample includes individuals who have directly benefited from poverty alleviation programmes and key stakeholders such as programme facilitators and community representatives. The sample size is deemed sufficient to represent the broader population and ensures a practical and effective approach to data collection and analysis.

The sampling technique employed is purposive sampling, a non-probabilistic method selected for its ability to target participants with relevant experiences and exposure to poverty alleviation programmes. This approach ensures the inclusion of respondents who can provide detailed, context-specific data on the impact and challenges of these initiatives in Esan West Local Government Area. Therefore, for this research, the Taro Yamane formula was used for detecting the sample size. It states that:

$$N = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where N= Population size

e = significant level of error (0.05)

n= Sample size

For this research N= 188700

Therefore, the sample size:

$$n = \frac{188700}{1 + 188700(0.05)^2}$$

$$= \frac{188700}{427.75}$$

$$= 399.$$

~399 respondents

The research applied response rate of 60% of the respondents

To calculate 60% response rate of 400 respondents:

$$\text{Response Rate} = \frac{\text{Percentage}}{100} \times \text{Respondents}$$
$$\frac{60}{100} \times 399 = 239 \text{ respondents}$$

Out of 399 distributed questionnaires, 239 were completed and returned, resulting in a response rate of 60%. This response rate is considered adequate for statistical analysis and reflects a good level of engagement from the respondents. The high rate of return ensured that the data collected was representative and reliable for the study, minimising potential biases associated with non-response.

This study primarily utilises primary data collected directly from respondents within Esan West Local Government Area (LGA) of Edo State, Nigeria. Primary data refers to first-hand information specifically tailored to address the research objectives, providing accurate and relevant insights into the effect of poverty alleviation programmes in the region. Structured questionnaires serve as the primary data collection tool. These questionnaires are carefully crafted to gather essential information regarding the demographic characteristics of respondents, their socio-economic conditions, awareness and participation in poverty alleviation programmes, and the perceived impact of these programmes on their livelihoods. The questions are designed to elicit clear, quantifiable responses to ensure accuracy and facilitate a comprehensive analysis. Moreover, structured questionnaires offer several benefits, including standardisation, ease of administration, and the ability to collect data efficiently from a large sample size. This approach ensures that the data gathered aligns with the study's objectives and is reliable for drawing meaningful conclusions about the impact of poverty alleviation programmes on the residents of Esan West Local Government Area.

Data analysis involves examining, organising, and interpreting the collected data to answer research questions and test hypotheses. In this study, a combination of simple percentage analysis and statistical techniques were used to ensure effective and accurate interpretation of the data gathered through the questionnaire. Simple percentage analysis was applied to summarise the responses for each item on the questionnaire. This method allowed for clear representation of the data in percentage form, making it easier to identify trends and key observations among the respondents. Each questionnaire item was

assigned a score, and the total scores were calculated to generate a quantitative summary of the data.

In addition to percentage analysis, the mean score method was used to calculate the average responses for each item. This provided a measure of central tendency, offering insights into the general opinions and perceptions of the respondents. However, for a complex data analysis of this nature, the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23 was utilised. SPSS is powerful statistical software that supports various statistical methods and allows for efficient handling of large datasets. Through SPSS, the researcher performed descriptive statistics, created charts, and generated graphs, which provided a clearer understanding of the research findings. The combination of these analytical tools ensured that the data was thoroughly analysed, enabling the researcher to draw meaningful conclusions and formulate actionable recommendations

Hypotheses Testing

H0: Poverty alleviation programmes have a significant positive impact on household income in Esan West Local Government Area.

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	29903.224	1	29903.224	69.934	.004 ^b
	Residual	1282.776	3	427.592		
	Total	31186.000	4			

Source: Researcher's Computation

a. Dependent Variable: House hold income

b. Predictors: (Constant), Poverty alleviation

The results of the ANOVA test show that poverty alleviation programmes have a significant positive impact on household income in Esan West Local Government Area. With a **p-value** of 0.004, which is less than the commonly accepted significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis (H0) is rejected. This indicates that there is strong statistical evidence to support the claim that poverty alleviation programmes positively affect

household income. The high F-value (69.934) further suggests a substantial and statistically significant relationship between the programmes and increased household income. This finding implies that participation in poverty alleviation efforts contributes to improvements in the financial stability of the households involved.

H0₂: Poverty alleviation programmes increased employment opportunities for beneficiaries in Esan West Local Government Area.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	69736.265	1	69736.265	8.859	.059 ^b
	Residual	23614.935	3	7871.645		
	Total	93351.200	4			

Source: Researcher's Computation

a. Dependent Variable: Employment opportunities

b. Predictors: (Constant), Poverty alleviation programmes

In this case, the ANOVA results show that the p-value is 0.059, which is slightly above the 0.05 threshold for statistical significance. This means that the evidence is not strong enough to reject the null hypothesis (H0₂). While the F-value (8.859) suggests that there is some variation explained by the poverty alleviation programmes, the p-value indicates that the effect of these programmes on employment opportunities is not statistically significant at the 5% significance level. Therefore, the hypothesis that poverty alleviation programmes significantly increase employment opportunities for beneficiaries in Esan West Local Government Area is not supported by the data.

H0₃: Poor implementation of poverty alleviation programmes is negatively correlated with the success of these initiatives in Esan West Local Government Area.

ANOVA ^a						
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1 Regression	27457.397	1	27457.397	1.120	.321 ^b	
Residual	196202.603	8	24525.325			
Total	223660.000	9				

Source: Researcher's Computation

a. Dependent Variable: Success initiatives

b. Predictors: (Constant), Poverty alleviation programme

For this hypothesis, the ANOVA test results show a very high p-value of 0.321, which is well above the 0.05 significance level. This means that the evidence is insufficient to reject the null hypothesis (H_0). The F-value of 1.120 further supports the conclusion that the relationship between poor implementation and the success of poverty alleviation programmes is not statistically significant. Therefore, the data does not provide strong support for the idea that poor implementation is negatively correlated with the success of these programmes. This suggests that other factors might be influencing the success of poverty alleviation programmes in Esan West Local Government Area, rather than implementation quality alone.

H04: The living standards of beneficiaries in Esan West Local Government Area improve as a result of participating in poverty alleviation programmes.

<i>Model</i>	ANOVA^a				
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
1 Regression	103372.431	1	103372.431	36.667	.009 ^b
Residual	8457.569	3	2819.190		
Total	111830.000	4			

Source: Researcher's Computation

a. Dependent Variable: Standard of living

b. Predictors: (Constant), Poverty alleviation programme

The results for this hypothesis show a p-value of 0.009, which is below the 0.05 threshold for significance, indicating that there is a statistically significant relationship between participation in poverty alleviation programmes and the improvement of beneficiaries' living standards. The F-value of 36.667 is quite high, suggesting that the poverty alleviation programmes have a strong effect on the living standards of those involved. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis that poverty alleviation programmes improve the living standards of beneficiaries in Esan West Local Government Area is supported. This finding revealed the positive impact of these programmes on the quality of life for the people who participate in them.

Summary of Findings

The analysis of poverty alleviation programmes in Esan West Local Government Area presents empirical results on their effectiveness, challenges, and perceived impact. The findings are structured based on thematic areas drawn from the descriptive statistics presented in the study. The bio-data analysis reveals that the sample population in this study is diverse in terms of gender, marital status, education, and length of residence. The majority of respondents are female, married, with secondary school education, and have lived in Edo State for over a decade. These demographic factors could potentially influence the respondents' views on the effectiveness of poverty alleviation programmes,

suggesting that different socio-economic backgrounds may result in varying experiences and outcomes related to the programmes.

The data reveals that poverty alleviation programmes have not substantially improved household income among beneficiaries. Responses indicate a limited perception of reduced reliance on external financial support. Participants agreed to some extent that these programmes address immediate family needs through financial support. However, significant scepticism exists regarding the programmes' ability to deliver consistent income growth or long-term financial stability. This suggests that the interventions might lack the scope or sustainability necessary to bring about meaningful and lasting economic change for participants.

Poverty alleviation programmes were perceived as moderately effective in creating employment opportunities. Skills acquisition initiatives were noted as particularly important in enhancing employability. However, other dimensions, such as job relevance to qualifications and the promotion of self-employment, were less successful, suggesting challenges in aligning these opportunities with participants' skills and aspirations. Furthermore, while some respondents acknowledged the programmes' role in reducing unemployment at the community level, the individual benefits were not as widely experienced.

The study identified several challenges hindering the effectiveness of poverty alleviation programmes. Corruption and mismanagement of funds were rated as significant obstacles. Respondents also highlighted inadequate funding and biases in beneficiary selection as critical issues. Administrative delays and limited community involvement further compounded these challenges, reducing the programmes' inclusivity, transparency, and efficiency. These findings point to systemic issues that require urgent attention to enhance the effectiveness of poverty alleviation efforts.

Poverty alleviation programmes showed limited success in improving participants' living standards. While some respondents acknowledged slight improvements in their overall standard of living, the perceived impact on specific areas, such as access to quality healthcare, housing affordability, and education, was modest at best. The most concerning result was the minimal impact on addressing nutritional needs.

This shortfall in meeting a basic necessity undermines the overall effectiveness of the interventions.

The success or failure of poverty alleviation programmes was found to be influenced by several factors. Effective community involvement emerged as the most significant factor, underscoring the importance of participatory approaches in programme design and implementation. Poor monitoring and evaluation systems and cultural or societal factors were also identified as major contributors to programme failure. Government commitment and funding, though critical, were perceived as inadequate, while collaboration with local organisations was seen as having room for improvement in fostering partnerships.

Conclusion

The findings of this study revealed the mixed effectiveness of poverty alleviation programmes in Esan West Local Government Area, Edo State. While these programmes offer some temporary relief for basic needs and moderately address unemployment at the community level, they fail to achieve significant and sustainable improvements in household income and overall living standards. Despite some perceived benefits, challenges such as corruption, inadequate funding, administrative delays, and limited community involvement continue to undermine their effectiveness. Moreover, the absence of robust monitoring and evaluation frameworks exacerbates these issues, making it difficult to identify gaps and implement necessary improvements.

The study also revealed systemic inefficiencies in programme design, including the misalignment of job opportunities with participants' skills and qualifications. This mismatch not only limits the potential for self-employment and entrepreneurship but also contributes to underemployment and dissatisfaction among beneficiaries.

Crucially, the study emphasises the pivotal role of community participation and cultural sensitivity in ensuring the success of poverty alleviation efforts. Greater collaboration with local stakeholders, combined with a participatory approach to planning and implementation, can enhance the relevance, inclusivity, and effectiveness of these initiatives. By aligning programmes with the socio-economic realities and cultural

dynamics of the target population, poverty alleviation efforts can achieve more meaningful and lasting impacts, ultimately fostering sustainable development in Esan West Local Government Area.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed to improve the effectiveness of poverty alleviation programmes in Esan West Local Government Area:

- i. The government should prioritise increased and consistent funding for poverty alleviation programmes. Transparent allocation of resources and the establishment of accountability mechanisms are essential to ensure that funds reach intended beneficiaries and address key needs effectively.
- ii. Incorporating community members in the planning, implementation, and monitoring of poverty alleviation programmes is crucial. This participatory approach fosters a sense of ownership, ensures that initiatives are tailored to local needs, and improves programme relevance and acceptance.
- iii. Anti-corruption measures, such as regular audits and the use of technology to track resource allocation, should be implemented to reduce the diversion of funds. Establishing independent oversight committees can further enhance transparency and accountability in programme management.
- iv. Robust monitoring and evaluation frameworks should be developed to track programme progress and measure outcomes. This will help identify gaps, assess the impact of interventions, and guide evidence-based decision-making for future programmes.

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CITIZENS DIS-ALIGNMENT WITH GOVERNMENT POLICIES: PANACEA TO NIGERIA UNDERDEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

This study visited the underdevelopment problems in Nigeria by examining citizens dis-alignment with government policies. Dis-alignment is when the citizens are unsatisfied with the system thereby separating themselves from government activities and plans, which is largely due to lack of trust and suspicion. The study adopted the systems theory which emphasize understanding and interconnectedness of the components parts within a system, while recognizing the whole, which is greater than the parts. Thus, citizens dis-alignment stem from the fact that Nigeria's underdevelopment is poor leadership governance which, has resulted in her weak economy, poor policy implementation, dilapidated infrastructural facilities, poor health service delivery and low-quality education etc. However, different researches on Nigeria's underdevelopment have argued that bad leadership is not the only obstacle to Nigeria's development, and that Nigeria's citizens have in one way or the other, also contributed to the country's underdevelopment. Relying on secondary data, the study embarked on extensive and in-depth review of relevant literatures on Nigeria's underdevelopment. The study concludes that citizens should align with the country's developmental process as proposed by the government; citizens should hold the leaders accountable for their stewardship in the aspect of policy making and implementation; and that citizens should endeavour to participate in policy making, both at the proposal state to the output stages to aid even development.

Keywords: Citizens dis-alignment, Government policies, Underdevelopment, Leadership

Introduction

Despite Nigeria's abundant natural and human resources, it still struggles to achieve significant progress in providing a decent standard of living for its population, even after many years of independence. Similar to numerous developing nations in Africa, Nigeria grapples with numerous obstacles in its efforts to advance. The nation is plagued by issues such as inequality, poverty, underdevelopment which has deprived many Nigerians of the privileges associated with citizenship (Okon & Thompson, 2020). Citizens typically believed that Nigeria has not recorded any significant or essential transformation since independence. As noted by (Eneh, 2021), by the mid-1990s, Nigeria has been surpassed in development by several nations that were in poorer condition. As a result, Nigeria still ranks among the underdeveloped nations, marked by a fragile industrial sector, low per capital income, elevated levels of illiteracy, poverty, disparity, and diminished life expectancy, among other factors.

Discrepancies in perspectives regarding development and underdevelopment issues in Nigeria are not a recent phenomenon. Some researchers attribute Nigeria's developmental hurdles to the capitalist global economic structure. Conversely, others prefer to introspect in their analysis of Nigeria's underdevelopment predicament. In these context, considerable emphasis was placed on governance. For instance, Achebe (2013) pointed out that Nigeria's issues stem fundamentally from a failure in leadership. Additionally, Rufai (2019) suggested that the best way to understand Nigeria is through the lens of its leadership. He asserted that "since Nigeria's Independence, the lack of competent leaders has been a consistent theme.

Okon & Thompson (2020) contended that "Nigeria's developmental challenges are largely self-inflicted and sustained by the nation's political elite, often characterized as exceedingly self-serving, corrupt, and ineffective". While the short comings of Nigerian leaders have been a focal point of criticism regarding the nation's plight, the responsibility of citizens in the context of Nigeria's unsuccessful development has seldom been addressed. This study aims to contribute by highlighting that, government of Nigeria should sample citizen's consent in policy making in order to share accountability for the

nation's underdevelopment, and this does not contradict any research that implicated Nigerian leaders or pose negative impact on her citizens.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives for this study are: i) to examine if citizens dis-alignment with government policies is a panacea to underdevelopment; ii) to determine if government policies create obstacle to underdevelopment; and iii) to ascertain how policy inconsistency affect development in Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

Study of this nature has significant impact on both variables' government and citizens. The study would be of great benefit to the government on meeting the demands of the citizens and impact the public with trust. This is because lack of trust comes with severe consequences. Nigerian citizens would become adamant in meeting some government demands when there is citizens dis-alignment in government policies. The public trust in government can be evaluated by the extent to which citizens have confidence in the government to operate in the best interests of society. Moreso no government can enjoy absolute trust of its citizens if the power of any government represents a threat to individual freedom and welfare.

Notwithstanding, citizens possess some level of trust for the government, trust is fundamentally important for a healthy and functioning democracy. According to Oaikhena (2023) he posits that "a change in strategy, such as pattern and vision, might not be effective if strategic positions, programmes, products, and attitude do not change accordingly". As a result, citizen compliance with public policies, encourages political participation, and contributes to perceptions of governmental legitimacy.

Stakeholders on the other hand would benefit from this study particularly when they are involved in policy making. The said stakeholders are non-governmental organization (NGOs) who on the other hand, can mediate between the government and the citizens, this will emphatically be a possible panacea for Nigeria underdevelopment and poor policies in the governance.

Concept of Citizenship in Nigeria

As articulated by (Tilly, 2006), citizenship represents an ongoing series of exchange between individuals and representative of a specific state, where each party possesses enforceable right and duties solely due to the individual's membership in group, encompassing both the native born and naturalized, and the representative's affiliation with the state rather than any other authority they may hold. In the view of (Baubock 2002) "citizenship is defined as a status of complete and equally belonging within a self-government political entity, involving rights and responsibilities anchored by particular virtues; thereby implying that citizenship connotes nationality and official association with states".

Based on the aforementioned definitions, a citizen is thus classified as an individual who has officially acquired or been granted the status of full and equal belonging to a state or political community. Citizenship embodies an agreement between the state and its citizens for a reciprocal dynamic (Adejumobi, 2001). While the state provides privileges and rights to its citizens, those citizens owe the state certain obligations and commitments. Notably, the execution of this mutual agreement between the state and citizens does not imply class distinctions but rather civic equality, equal access and opportunities within state institutions frameworks as well as fairness and justice in the relationships among the state individuals and within the political community (Adejumobi, 2001).

In Nigeria, the constitution confers citizenship on every Nigerian, on equal basis. Accordingly, Nigeria's citizenship can be acquired by birth, registration and naturalization. Chapter 3 (Section 25) of the 1999, Constitution states that the following persons are citizens of Nigeria by birth, namely:

- a) Any person born in Nigeria before the date of independence, either of whose parents or any of whose grandparents belong or belonged to a community indigenous to Nigeria;
- b) Every person born in Nigeria after the date of independence either of whose parents or any of whose grandparents is a citizen of Nigeria;
- c) Every person born outside Nigeria either of whose parents is a citizen of Nigeria.

The constitution in section 26 (1-2) also states that a person may be registered as a citizen of Nigeria, if the president is satisfied that: a) He is a person of good character; b) He has shown clear intention of his desire to be domiciled in Nigeria; and c) He has taken the Oath of Allegiance prescribed in the Seventh Schedule to the constitution. The provisions of this section also apply to: i) Any woman who is or has been married to a citizen of Nigeria; or b) Every person of full age and capacity born outside Nigeria any of whose grandparents is a citizen of Nigeria.

Furthermore, any person who is qualified in accordance with the provisions of section 27 of the constitution may apply to the president for citizenship by naturalization. The provisions hold that an applicant must prove that:

- a) He is a person of full age and capacity;
- b) He is a person of good character;
- c) He has shown a clear intention of his desire to be domiciled in Nigeria;
- d) He is, in the opinion of Governor of the State where he is or he proposes to be resident, acceptable to the local community in which he is to live permanently, and has been assimilated into the way of life of Nigerians in that part of the Federation;
- e) He is a person who has made or is capable of making useful contribution to the advancement; progress and well-being of Nigeria;
- f) He has taken the Oath of Allegiance prescribed in the Seventh Schedule to the constitution; and
- g) He has, immediately preceding the date of his application, either –
 - Resided in Nigeria for a continuous period of fifteen years; or
 - Resided in Nigeria continuously for a period of twelve months, and during the period of twenty years immediately preceding that period of twelve months has resided in Nigeria for periods amounting in the aggregate to not less than fifteen years.

The aforementioned definition of citizenship in chapter three, along with the fundamental rights outlined in chapter four of the 1999 constitution, which encompasses the right to life, respect for human dignity, personal liberty, equitable hearing, freedom of movement and protection from discrimination, aims to foster national political goals of creating a unified and liberated society for all Nigerians and to enhance mutual responsibilities between the state and its citizens (CFCR, 2002). Nonetheless, the practical application of citizenship in Nigeria has encounter various challenges, it can be perceived as nominal, as citizens largely experience the denial of their citizenship rights, this situation has led individual to adopt subnational identities as a primary source of allegiance and authentic identification (Afolabi, 2016).

Concept of Underdevelopment

Underdevelopment is a complex phenomenon; therefore, it is necessary to clarify the nature of this issue alongside its antonym development. Underdevelopment is simply put, a country that is not developed, and there are several markers to determine whether a country is underdeveloped (Oduwole, 2013) and the study will seek to understand development through the lens of Seers' conception of development as a 'good change'. This perspective offers a comprehensive view of development that does not "equate growth with development" rather this approach focuses on going beyond the economic metrics by associating development with the mitigation of poverty, unemployment, and inequality (Seers, 1972) as cited in (McGillivray, 2016).

Nigeria's underdevelopment is a complex issue characterized by a range of interconnected factors that hinder its economic and social progress. These factors include dependence on a single export (crude oil), a weak industrial base, high unemployment, income inequality, and a history of corruption and poor governance (Akpomera, (2015). These issues are further compounded by a lack of diversification, inadequate infrastructure, and a poorly developed human capital base. (Seers 1972) argue that "it looks as if economic growth not merely may fail to solve social and political difficulties; certain types of growth can cause them." moreover, the term 'development' itself is synonymous with progress. Furthermore, the method that this approach determines

progress is if the following three issues are mitigated; 'poverty', 'unemployment', and 'inequality' (Seers, 1972).

Thus, this implies that the issue of underdevelopment can be viewed as the inverse of development since development indicates that the economy is developing or moving forward by tackling the issues stated above, hence underdevelopment is not only an indicator that represents a lack of development rather in certain areas there is a stagnation or regression in solving the economic ailments. Therefore, this perspective goes beyond simply relying on economic indicators as the metric to judge development as this study intends to do. Henceforth, the study utilizes the inverse of Seers' formulation as another definition of underdevelopment when the country continues to suffer from the ailments of poverty, unemployment, and inequality, thereby classifying it as underdeveloped.

Development, like many terms within the social sciences, does not have a unive rsally accepted definition. Developmental definitions often reference improvements in the quality of human life. (Naomi 1995) notes that development typically entails not just economic growth but elements of fair distribution, access to health care, education, housing and other vital services, all aimed at enhancing both individual and collective quality of life. (Gboyega, 2003) perceives development as an idea encompassing all initiatives to elevate the conditions of human existence across various dimensions. It represents a transformation or progress towards a more desirable state (Chukwuemeka, Ugwuanyi & Amobi, 2013).

If development is considered in terms of improvement in the quality of human life, it therefore implies that a country can be regarded as being developed only when it is able to provide qualitative living standard for its citizens. Regrettably, Nigeria has not been able to provide such living standard for its citizens. There have been numerous policies, plans and programmes aimed at achieving development in Nigeria, but these have not brought the required change in the country. The country still remains grossly underdeveloped and largely characterized by poverty, inequality and lack of basic infrastructure. Thus, Nigeria has failed in its development efforts, as observed by (Okon and Thompson (2020).

Policy as a Concept

Policy is an intentional set of rules to direct choices and produce logical results. Implemented as a protocol or procedure, a policy is a declaration of intent. The governance body of an organization typically adopts policies (*Voican, 2008*). It is possible for policies to support both subjective and objective decision-making. Because they must be based on the relative merits of several factors, policies used in subjective decision-making typically help senior management make decisions that are difficult to test objectively. Also, policies are implemented by governments and other organizations through laws, rules, procedures, administrative actions, incentives, and voluntary practices.

In order to facilitate objective decision-making, policies are typically operational in nature and subject to objective testing (*Gade, 2023*). It has been argued that policies ought to be evidence-based. An individual or organization is justified in claiming that a specific policy is evidence-based if, and only if, three conditions are met. First, the individual or organization possesses comparative evidence about the effects of the specific policy in comparison to the effects of at least one alternative policy. Second, the specific policy is supported by this evidence according to at least one of the individual's or organization's preferences in the given policy area. Third, the individual or organization can provide a sound account for this support by explaining the evidence and preferences that lay the foundation for the claim (*Lowi, 1972*). Policies are dynamic; they are not just static lists of goals or laws. Policy blueprints have to be implemented, often with unexpected results. Social policies are what happens 'on the ground' when they are implemented, as well as what happens at the decision making or legislative stage.

Inconsistency Policy in Nigeria

Inconsistency is the quality or state of being inconsistent. To be inconsistent is to lose the sequence of one's actions. Policy inconsistency resulting from changes in policy sometimes emerges from the attempt of leaders to reform society not necessarily to create a setback for the citizenry. Where a leader has amended a policy, not for national interests or development, but to tarnish the predecessors, such policy is likely to fail. Policy

inconsistency occurs in many countries with the change of governments. For instance, in Nigeria, several economic, political and social policies have changed due to changes in governments from one political part or same political party to another. This could be the reason why Oaikhena (2021) argued that “the restriction of national planning efforts towards economic development, only with scant reference to social, political and cultural development is often times recorded in Africa”.

Nigeria faces several hindrances in achieving its economic and developmental goals. But, one of the most profound is policy inconsistency and discontinuity. The national council on development planning (NCDC) recognized the lack of stability and continuity in programmes by succeeding governments as the bane of Nigeria’s stunted growth and development. Very few policies have stood the test of time.

Most politicians are entirely focused on getting re-elected rather than enforcing feasible and viable politics that actually drive long-term growth. As a result, the frequent change of government after election often leads to a complete or partial disruption of the policies enacted by the previous administration (Whether good or bad). While it is understandable that the incoming administration might have an alternative vision and might want to gain legitimacy by introducing new policies, the intent behind their actions is not always patriotic. Governments have a sense of “my policy”. The Abuja-Kaduna railway is a typical example; where supporters of ex-president Goodluck Jonathan did not let Nigerians forget that “Jonathan began it and Buhari finished it”.

Theoretical Framework

There have been various attempts by scholars to explain why some countries are developed and others are underdeveloped. These scholars, in their attempt, often queue behind two popular paradigms of development/underdevelopment. One of such paradigms is the modernization of school. According to (Okereke and Ekpe 2002), the central thesis of the Modernization School is that, under development in Nigeria is internally generated and perpetuated due to the traditional or primitive character of the society.

Consequently, modernization theorists advocate for the adoption of western economic paradigms as key to the development of the Third World whose

underdevelopment results from internal contradictions within their territories. As explained by Igwe (2010), such internal contradictions are evident from the way and manner resources are allocated in these societies, as well as the parochial beliefs, attitudes and values of the people which together with the character of the policies of governance are incongruent to development.

Within the Modernization School, there are several theories that seek to explain development and underdevelopment among countries of the world. One of such theories is the Socio-Cultural Theory which is based on the premise that what creates the necessary conditions for economic development in any society are the changes in social, cultural and institutional orders of society. One of the socio-cultural theorists, Manning Nash cited in (Okereke and Ekpe 2002), explained that since economic development is a process of social change, it must be seen to involve three related kinds of social action, namely: i) The choice to institute changes; ii. The bringing together of the means and facilities to implement the choice; and iii) The organization of social and cultural life so that growth becomes a built-in feature of the social system.

Nash stated further that lack of capital for productive investment is among the many problems facing Third World countries. He added that his study of Burma and Cambodia has, however, shown that the social structures and cultural patterns which enhance savings and investments vary from one country to another. In line with the views of modernization theorists, (Dike 2015) argued that Nigeria lacks the critical institutions and infrastructure capable of transforming the society into the 21st century system. For (Dike 2015), the Nigerian system is colored by unbridled corruption, non-functional health care and education systems, and institutions and infrastructure that are antithetical to capacity development; and these forces have resulted in a weak economy, rising youth unemployment, and poverty as well as insecurity in the society. In their assessment, (Okon and Thompson 2020) agreed, on one hand, with modernization theorists that the underdevelopment of Third World countries is mostly internally generated and perpetuated.

According to them, there is evidence to prove that most of Nigeria's problems are internally generated and perpetuated by Nigerian political elites - who seem to be

comfortable with the country's underdevelopment situation; notwithstanding the fact that the many years of colonialism and neocolonialism have, in one way or the other, also affected the pursuit of development in Nigeria. In another breath, (Okon and Thompson 2020) frown at the attempt by modernization theorists to demote the cultures of Third World countries.

Eme (2013) argued that culture *per se* cannot stop a peasant or an investor from taking advantage of a prominent situation that can promote his welfare. They further observed that wealth and achievement are valued among the Igbos. Therefore, given the right incentive, that progressive culture of hard-work and achievement can be stimulated to achieve the goals of agrarian modernization and industrialization. In this regard, Idachaba (1975), was of the opinion that if developing countries are interested in planned change in their peasant economies, they need to identify the positive elements which promote change within their societies, while at the same time identifying those elements that can possibly impede progress.

Methodology

This paper relied on secondary sources of data. Data were gathered by the researchers through an extensive and in-depth review of relevant literatures on Nigeria's underdevelopment. The sources of the literatures were thoroughly evaluated and analyzed. Citizens dis-alignment with government policies a panacea for Nigeria underdevelopment. Data generated were used for study analysis.

Government failures and way forward

The Nigeria government has failed in its development efforts, in spite of her citizen's right to policies. According to Dike (2015), Nigeria's system is colored by unbridled corruption, non-functional health care and education systems, and institutions and infrastructure that are antithetical to capacity development. According to him, these forces have resulted in weak economy, rising youth unemployment, and poverty as well as insecurity in the society. The Nigerian economy has over the decades been characterized by galloping inflation, unequal foreign exchange rate exasperated by devalued currency

and persistent dependence on importation (Eme, 2013), and despite the country's increase in oil wealth, majority of its citizens wallow in poverty (Okon and Thompson, 2020).

As noted by the World Bank and Department for International Development (2005), nearly 70 million Nigerians live on less than \$1 per day, 54 percent of Nigerians live below the poverty line (UNDP, 2006) and over one-third live in extreme poverty (UNDP, 2006b). Nigeria's poverty rate is hovering around 43.3 percent of the estimated population of 170 million (Emejo, 2014). Dike (2015) stated that: *“Many Nigerians appear to have entrepreneurial skills; they are very creative and innovative. But the unpredictable and un-conducive, extractive political institutions and unfriendly business environment have stunted their zeal. ...It takes a lot of passion and determination to keep your business running and to market your products or services under the poor business environment in Nigeria”*.

There is also stagnation in Nigeria's educational sector. Singapore in the early 1960s had educational statistics similar to that of many African countries, including Nigeria; but as at 2019, the nation's literacy rate stood at 97 percent while Nigeria, on the other hand, was only able to improve the literacy rate to 60 percent (Rufai, 2019). The standard of education in Nigeria has been falling; teaching and learning are based on theory with little or no practical application of what the students learned in the classroom (Dike, 2015). According to Afolayan (2014), this falling standard of education in Nigeria is due to lack of proper funding and planning. In Nigeria, students are taught under un-conducive learning environments and teachers are not adequately motivated. While Secondary School (High School) graduates in educational institutions in Nigeria churned out yearly are ill-prepared to face the rigorous of university education, the age-long disagreement between the Federal Government and the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) has disrupted the academic calendar of higher institutions.

These pose serious problems for the development of creative, innovative and productive citizens (Dike, 2015). Nigeria's health care system is plague with problems. Apart from lack of cordial relationship between health care providers and patients, poorly equipped health centres and hospitals are spread all over the country (The Health Workers Strike, 2014; Dantiye, 2015) and these have prevented the health care providers from

providing quality services to Nigerians. As opined by Musawa (2014), lots of Nigerians die from preventable diseases such as high blood pressure, hypertension, prostate cancer, diabetes, breast cancer, maternal child birth issues and malnutrition due to the country's poor health care system. Consequently, the political elites and those who can afford the cost, often travel abroad to receive high quality health care services at the expense of the masses (Dantiye, 2015). Thus, ordinary citizens often rely on the assistance of private individuals in order to resolve their basic health problems (The Health Workers Strike, 2014).

As observed by Dike (2015), the medical doctors and other health care workers are often on strike to press home their demands over diverse issues, including non-payment of salaries and allowances, which often lead to unnecessary loss of lives. However, some people are of the opinion that the health care professionals in Nigeria care only about their remuneration than provision of health services to the needy (News Agency of Nigeria, 2014). Worse still, Nigerians have lost faith in the country's health care system as their perception of Nigeria's health care workers is that of uneducated, unskilled, unreliable and hardhearted care providers (Dantiye, 2015). Given the above background, Nigeria has presented itself as a country that is characterized by failed development.

Accordingly, Okon and Thompson (2020) identify Nigeria as a country which, in spite of her huge resources, has failed in its development efforts, while Rufai (2019) described the country as one that is stuck in perpetual underdevelopment because, the more things change the more they remain the same. Citizens and Failed Development in Nigeria There are differing opinions on why Nigeria, with its human and natural resources, has failed to achieve development and this debate has been on for several decades. Some have noted that Nigeria's developmental challenges are due to the capitalist world economic system. Yet others (Achebe, 1983; Dike, 2015; Rufai, 2019; Okon and Thompson, 2020) have observed that Nigeria has failed in its development efforts because of the absence of good leadership.

According to Achebe (1983), the trouble with Nigeria is simply and squarely a failure of leadership. Dike (2015) sees Nigerian political leaders as those who seem to

have a “fixed mind-set”, which has prevented them from adopting and implementing effective socio-political and economic policies to transform the society. Rather than chart a path towards national development, Nigerian leaders engage in pervasive distribution struggles which often result in political instability and the erosion of good governance (Rufai, 2019). Leadership is of utmost importance in the development of any nation - and given the caliber of leaders that have ruled Nigeria since its independence; the country seems not to be ambitious enough for development (Okon and Thompson, 2020). Although there are enough resources to achieve the much needed development in Nigeria, the looting and mismanagement of the resources by political elites have perpetually prevented the country from achieving development. As has been rightly noted by Dike (2015), the root cause of the present social, political and economic predicaments in Nigeria is not the making of leaders alone but collective selfishness.

For instance, corruption has often been identified as being a bane of Nigeria's socio-economic development, but it is not only the political elites that are responsible for the endemic corruption in the country. There is no doubt that most of Nigeria's leaders are notoriously corrupt; however, some citizens are as corrupt, if not more, as the leaders in Nigeria. In reality, the only reason why some of these Nigerians remain incorruptible is that they lack the opportunity to be corrupt. It is on record that some Nigerians give bribes in order to gain admission into higher institutions of learning or get employment in the civil service or other organizations, regardless of qualifications and merit. Amid corruption in Nigeria, vision, policy, plan, politics, principle, conscience, wealth, commerce, pleasure sports, knowledge, science, worship and morality are all corrupt (Eneh, 2011).

This means that corruption is not only in political offices; it is also present in markets, schools, churches, stadia and in the minds of most Nigerians. For Eneh (2011), patriotism is a stranger to an average Nigerian's lexicon, the federal character and Nigerian factor having replaced merits and rights. Today, anyone in Nigeria could be extremely rich and famous without any known source of income and nobody questions such wealth and fame (Acemoglu and Robinson, 2012). Dike 2015 states that in Nigeria:

...Public servants do not show up for work on time and do not take their work seriously, and they expect to get paid every month without being productive.

The mentality that hard work and honesty does not pay (or is not properly rewarded) has found its way into the school system as students do not take their studies seriously any longer. The “I don't care attitude” and the mentality to get rich through fraud often discourage the spirit of competition and hard work, and thus, inhibit national development”t. In addition, it is the responsibility of the people to monitor the activities of the political leaders with a view to reviewing their mandate for good performance or using constitutional provisions to fire them for nonperformance (Eneh, 2011).

Every Nigerian is a stakeholder in the affairs of the nation (Dike, 2015). However, some Nigerians do not care about what happens in the country and have failed in ensuring that the leaders honour the social contract they entered into with the citizens. Instead of Nigerian leaders to redesign the system to make it function effectively, they engage in patching problems and the citizens allow them to continue in doing so (Dike, 2015). It is important to note that developed and progressive countries became what they are today because their people fought and overthrew the powerful political elites who dominated political power, and thus, create a society where political rights were properly shared and the government was responsive to the needs of the people (Acemoglu and Robinson, 2012). But the citizens have been unable to do so in Nigeria.

Thus, Nigerian leaders have been taking the citizens for a ride because the citizens seem to be enjoying the ride. Majority of Nigerians are traumatized and dying of extreme poverty and hunger, while a privileged few have, by fair or foul means, cornered and monopolized Nigeria's economic, political, health and sociocultural commonwealth (Eneh, 2011). This situation is disheartening, but it does not justify why some citizens develop attitudes that are inimical to development. Rather than hold the leaders accountable for mismanagement and injustice in the country, some citizens have resorted to wrong reactions. One of such reactions has been the insecurity situation in the country which has driven away potential investors, especially from the northern part of the country.

Also, issues of indiscriminate disposal of waste, open defecation, vandalism of public facilities and disobedience to law and order by citizens remain detrimental to Nigeria's development. Another wrong reaction or responses to Nigeria's ugly situation by citizens is brain drain (Eneh, 2008). Evidently, Nigeria's date with destiny has been put on hold because of the citizen's attitude towards the political system and the leadership behavior towards what they should be doing for the citizens, for overall development of the country (Anazodo, Uchenna and Uche, 2022). Therefore, some citizens are to blame for Nigeria's failed development, together with the leaders. Thus the way forward are highlighted as follows:

- a) Primarily, the solution to Nigeria's underdevelopment lies in good governance. Political elites must endeavor to fulfill their promises of bringing development to the country and must pay adequate attention to uplifting the impoverished and dehumanized Nigerian citizenry.
- b) There should be a change of the citizens' orientation. Nigerians must realize that they have a great role to play in the country's development and the need to participate in policy making, both at the input and output stages.
- c) Citizens must equally learn to hold leaders accountable for their stewardship and must be willing to co-operate with government in all its efforts toward the development of Nigeria.
- d) Government should be flexible in policy making.
- e) One of the major panacea to underdevelopment in any country is the involvement of the citizen(s) in taking drastic decision.
- f) Lastly, the burden of Nigeria' development does not fall solely at the feet of political elites; when faced with opportunities to contribute to the country's development, each Nigerian must remember to bear his/her own moral burden.

Discussion of findings

Target Beneficiaries: It can be said that no single government policy plan is sufficient to meet the needs of the people. It is good to target a specific group for a better policy implementation. The target group should be involved at the formulation stage in order for

them to contribute in what affect(s) their lives. This will also give them a sense of belonging and commitment.

Interaction and Communication between Government and the other Organizations:

Adequate attention should be given the nongovernmental organizations, professional bodies, organized private sector and the civil society groups in the policy process. These group invariably represents the larger citizens.

Monitoring of Project: There should be provision for adequate monitoring of projects, to stop the problem of abandoned projects and to ensure the realization of policy goals.

Adequate Resources: Adequate material and human resources needed to implement the policy should be provided.

Effective Communication: There must be effective communication between the target beneficiaries and the implementers of policy programs.

Encourage the Culture of Continuity: The culture of discontinuity of policies should be discouraged. The national and state assemblies should enact laws that will guarantee continuity of policies made to enhance growth and development. There should be continuity in policy, except when the policy is found not to be useful to the people.

Substantial Effort and Continuity of Efforts: Policy implementation will not automatically follow from policy decisions but needs to be treated as a positive purposive process in it. Consequently, substantial effort is required to follow policy from intention to action; and the resources needed for adequate implementation of relevant policies needs to be provided to realize policy objectives.

Conclusion

Without doubt, the fundamental cause of Nigeria's underdevelopment is poor leadership and governance which has resulted in weak economy, poor institutions, dilapidated infrastructural facilities and low quality education above all poor policy making etc. But beyond the country's bad leadership, citizens do also contribute to the underdevelopment in Nigeria. Without the citizens being patriotic to the country; without the citizens holding the leaders accountable for their stewardship; and without the citizens showing genuine interest in the country's development, Nigeria may continue to remain underdeveloped. It

seems difficult for ordinary Nigerians alone, without political power, to bring the needed change in the country; however, each time the citizens are faced with an opportunity to contribute to Nigeria's development, they should do so with sincerity and patriotism.

a) Recommendations

- b) In considering citizen participation for the objective of advancing public accountability in the policy making, a successful citizen participation programme should be well organized, constructive, systematic and legally binding to have chances of achieving positive impact (Golubovic, 2010). Well-organized citizen participation entails facilitation of information sharing between the institutions and actors involved in decision making. The information should be objective, reliable, and up to date and user friendly to those involved (OECD, 2001). For example, when dealing with local citizens who can barely read, it is inappropriate to design leaflets or pamphlets as information dissemination tool since it bars their chances of learning.
- c) In addition, there should also be clear goals and rules that govern the interactions and processes in the exercise of participation (Yang & Callahan, 2005). These goals and rules should define the bounds and exact intents of the participation exercise to ascertain a concrete potential base of accountability and transparency in the decision-making processes (Malena et al., 2004). The processes of citizen participation should be open to public scrutiny to ensure transparency (Phillips & Orsini, 2002:9). At the same-time, the results of a citizen participation process should demonstrate the strength of citizens' voice (Arnstein, 1969).
- d) However, often in democratic politics the dependent factors of citizen participation don't play out quite like this due to unlevelled interplay of power factors and policy making interest among involved actors or institutions. For example, many governments in developing countries despite being democratic are reported to have imbalances on information sharing, setting participatory structures and mechanisms of accountability (World Bank, 2004; Laurian & Shaw, 2008). 4. Most of these governments release generic information on citizen participation that is not user

friendly to the task at hand (Agrawal & Ribot, 1999). They also don't set supporting legal sanctions of ensuring public accountability in order to still maintain control of things over the citizens, and also avert local accountability (Agrawal & Ribot, 1999). Also, due to limited time of office, many democratic governments are interested in achieving substantive policy objectives which overrides citizen participation in achieving the substantive policies. Hence, this paper supports a continuum approach to analyzing citizen participation.

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AN APPRAISAL OF HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT AND EMPLOYMENT POLICIES TOWARDS ORGANIZATIONAL GROWTH IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The paper examined human capital development and employment policies with a view to organizational growth in Nigeria. It identifies the avenues through which human capital is developed, such as the provision of formal education, on-the-job training, adult education, health services, labour market information and support for internal migration, among others. Human capital development and employment policies are crucial for economic growth, focusing on investing in people's skills, health, and knowledge (education training) to boost productivity and create jobs. The administrative structure of the Nigerian state and the constitutional responsibilities given to each level of government (local, state, and federal), observes that the federal government plays a leading role in human capital formation and policy initiatives. It therefore considers the tasks of the federal government in promoting human capital development, bearing in mind the avenues for developing human resources. The significance of human capital development cannot be overemphasize. The study adopted Max Webbers theory, who highlighted the significance of formal organizations and bureaucratic structures in modern society. Secondary data was used for the study. It recommended that human capital development programmes that are capable of improving the skills, morale and performance of employees, should be encouraged to aid guaranteed quality of service delivery. It added that organizations should encourage on-the-job training, and further education to assist employees improve their performance and capabilities, which consequently will increase effective service delivery in terms of quantity of work produced.

Keywords: Human capital development, Employment policies, Organizational growth, Service delivery

Introduction

Human capital denotes individuals who have skills, knowledge, and attitudes, employed in the production process (Okoh, 2019). It is widely considered that human capital is the crucial element of production. The human capital organizes various production factors to create goods and services intended for human use. Human capital serves as the primary driving force behind economic growth and development (Okoh, 2019). Since 1959 and on the brink of Nigeria's political independence from Britain in 1960, when the Federal Government established the Ashby Commission to explore Nigeria's requirements for post-primary and higher education from 1960 to 1980, human capital development has been highly valued in the national development process. The federal government has prioritized human capital development via its policies and programs and has established agencies that supervise the execution of those policies and programs (Adams, 2013).

The reviewed National Employment Policy is informed largely by an International Labour Organisation (ILO) preliminary report titled "Employment Mapping and Institutional Assessment and Coordination Mechanism Study: The Case of Nigeria". The report provides an audit of the various employment programmes and projects at Federal level and selected states in Nigeria. The report assessed who is doing what in job creation, in which sector(s) and in which States. It also examined the source(s) of funding, impact and sustainability of outputs and outcomes; implementation and coordination mechanisms; and challenges facing such employment initiatives. The employment report notes that a number of programs and projects are built within the framework of the Nigerian Vision 20:2020. They are aimed to foster job-intensive and engender private sector-led growth in the economy. Existing employment-related initiatives within the private sector in the country are grouped in the following order: a) Initiatives or programmes aimed at creating employment through improving access to finance for both start-ups and existing micro small and medium enterprises; b) training programmes aimed at supporting and developing entrepreneurial and business skills of women and youths; and c) internship programmes which are aimed at integrating new entrants (including university graduates) into formal and informal labour markets. This could be the reason

why Oaikhena, (2025) observed that “authorities sometimes believe that individuals are passive followers of instructions from institutions or agencies of government, some are even conditioned to adjust to the requirements of the labour market no matter what”.

The development of human capital and suitable employment strategies are essential for the growth of organizations in Nigeria. Focusing on employee skills, expertise, and competencies through training and development initiatives, along with efficient hiring and retention practices, can greatly enhance productivity, creativity, and overall organizational effectiveness (Dadfar & Brege, 2012). Additionally, synchronizing policies with national development objectives and promoting a conducive regulatory framework are crucial for sustainable progress. Employment, unemployment, and underemployment represent significant macroeconomic challenges in Nigeria that frequently spark discussions among researchers, policymakers, and social commentators. Nevertheless, the efficient monitoring and analysis of employment have been hindered by the absence of reliable and consistent labor market data and statistics (Harbison, 2013).

This study explores the idea of human capital development and employment strategy for organizational advancement, highlighting its significance as emphasized by the Federal Government of Nigeria. It also emphasizes pathways for enhancing human capital, including formal education, in-service training, adult learning, healthcare services, and assistance for migration. The article also examined Nigeria's administrative framework and the constitutional duties assigned to every tier of government (local, state, and federal) (Harbison, 2012). It subsequently examined the responsibilities of the federal government in fostering human capital growth, taking into account the methods for enhancing human resources – formal education, workplace training, adult education, etc. It emphasizes the assistance that the federal government has provided to the private sector in its initiatives to cultivate human capabilities in the nation (Harbison 2012).

Additionally, the study recognizes the motivation that the federal government of Nigeria provides to international organizations for developing human capital as one of their obligations to member countries. Ultimately, the article offers suitable suggestions to guarantee that the country's human capital development initiatives meet the intended objectives efficiently.

Objectives of the Study

The followings were drawn out as the objectives to the study: a) to identify how human capital development affect employment policies in Nigeria; b) to ascertain the positive impact of employment policies towards organizational growth in terms of human capital development in Nigeria; and c) to determine how human capital development improve organizational growth in Nigeria

Significance of the Study

This study would be beneficial to all stakeholders who seeks organizational growth in Nigeria. It would benefit academia of higher institutions, because several studies has been on human capital and economic performance, human capital and employees commitment, but this study has not been much researched, thereby filling the gap. The study would be of significant impact to organizations to guide human capital development and employment policies in other to always take a cognizance look on selecting staff/employee, based on internship training according to the policy acts.

Human capital development

The development of human capital is seen as a crucial element in the growth and trajectory of any nation, focusing on attaining sustainable economic growth and progress. No nation has attained lasting economic growth without significant investment in human resources (Okojie, 2015). The macroeconomic objectives of countries - developing, emerging, and developed – is growth and development. Therefore, each country is advancing economic development according to their respective abilities. Some are achieving significant economic advancements while others are not. The differing results can be attributed to the abilities of each country (Lovelock, et. al., 2012). Natural scientists believes that humans are quite distinct among all living organisms (Obananya, 2022). This occurs due to the advanced reasoning abilities that humans exhibit in their interactions with their surroundings. This rationality has prompted individuals to quickly alter their lifestyles and societies; therefore, numerous scholars perceive humans as assets

to organizations and nations. Human capital has been described in numerous ways (Chuks, 2020).

The idea of human capital pertains to the talents and competencies of a nation's workforce, whereas human capital formation denotes the process of obtaining and enhancing the count of individuals possessing the education, skills, and experience essential for a country's economic growth and advancement (Okojie, 2015). It pertains to the expertise, abilities, dispositions, both physical and management effort needed to handle capital, technology, and land, among other resources, to generate goods and services for human use (UNECA, 1990). This could be the reason why Oaikhena (2025) posited that “employees that are engaged actively through dialogue and feedback mechanism easily build trust through collaboration that improve the working environment”. It is the collection of skills, understanding, and personality traits manifested in the capacity to work in a ways that generates economic values, resulting in the qualities acquired by an employee through learning and experience (Hassan, et. al., 2022). Numerous initial economic theories describe it merely as labor or human capital, which constitutes one of the three elements of production, viewing it as a transferable resources. Human resources encompass all individuals, meaning it includes those who are currently employed or are expected to gain productive employment eventually (Mayhew, et. al., 2013). It represents a continuum, an ongoing journey spanning from childhood through old age, essential for any society or organization aiming to endure the intricate challenges of a changing world (Friday et al., 2020). A compilation of recent efforts to define human capital would indicate the concept as represented in: a) human resources; encompassing the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and motivation of an organization or community, which contribute to the growth of that organization or community in achieving its goals and improving the quality of life for its members; b) the ability and efficiency of individuals produced through the knowledge and abilities gained from education, training, and experience; and supported by a conducive environment; and c) that non-physical element of the production process that adds human knowledge, abilities, and expertise in creating and delivering goods and services. Human capital is considered significant on its own, but the process of accumulation is also crucial.

However, Dadfar and Brege (2012), emphasizes the knowledge and abilities acquired through educational experiences. As per Schultz (1995), human capital encompasses the accumulation of skills, knowledge, ideas, talent, and health condition of individuals that are pertinent to the production process. Odusola (1998) noted that human capital development involves a deliberate and ongoing process of acquiring and expanding the pool of individuals possessing essential knowledge, education, skills, and experience vital for a nation's economic growth. As per Okojie (2015), the development of human capital is linked to investing in individuals and fostering their growth as innovative and productive beings. It is an ongoing journey, a relentless development from youth to seniority, and essential for any community or organization that wishes to thrive amidst the intricate challenges of a constantly changing world. The development of human capital serves as a method because it improves individuals' skills, knowledge, productivity, and creativity via a broadly understood process of human capital formation (Chuks, 2020).

Human capital is regarded as a factor of production that improves the ability to convert input into output. Consequently, human capital is the type of capital that has the ability to generate and enhance other forms of capital. The development of human capital is thus the process that focuses on enhancing that capacity. It can be described as the advancement of education and healthcare to nurture and enhance human capital (Manning, 2003). Consistent with this, Meier (1970) asserts that human capital development has a dual aim of enhancing skills and creating productive jobs for unused or underused labor. Both arise from investing in individuals through education and training, recognized as institutional methods for improving people's knowledge, skills, and abilities. According to Adamu (2013), human capacity is attained and enhanced via education, training, health initiatives, along with investments in all social services that affect human productivity. According to Oaikhena (2011), if there is anything that Nigerians of all walks of life are unanimous about, it is the fact that Nigeria has a stunted growth. The rationale for positioning health and education as fundamental for human capital development lies in the fact that many expenditures termed consumption are actually investments in human capital, with direct costs for education, healthcare, and

internal migration to seize improved job opportunities serving as clear illustrations. Individuals utilize their free time to develop their abilities and understanding, thereby boosting the effectiveness of human endeavors and overall productivity. Becker (2009) refers to them as human capital since individuals cannot be distinguished from their knowledge, skills, health, or values in the same manner that one can separate financial and physical assets. Shultz (2011) thus claimed that investing in human capital is likely the primary reason for the differences seen in productive (output) levels across the world's economies. He outlined five methods for enhancing human capital as follows:

- a) Funding for healthcare facilities and services is broadly defined to encompass all costs that influence life expectancy, strength and endurance, as well as the energy and liveliness of the population.
- b) Job training which includes traditional apprenticeships arranged by companies;
- c) Education that is systematically structured at the primary, secondary, and tertiary stages;
- d) Educational programs for adults that are not arranged by companies, including significant extension programs in agriculture;
- e) Relocation of people and facilities to adapt to evolving employment prospects.

The global concept of human capital arises from the reality that acquiring practical skills, abilities, knowledge, and supporting the individual during their education, learning, or training involves actual costs, viewed as an investment in that person, thus making this investment regarded as capital. The emphasis here is that the enhanced abilities of a worker can be viewed similarly to a machine or a tool, which streamlines and reduces effort, and which, despite incurring some costs, ultimately returns that investment with profit in the long run. The core of human resources development lies in making certain that the workforce is consistently adjusted and enhanced to address the emerging challenges of its entire environment (Yesufu, 2000).

Avenues for human capital development

As noted by Okafor et al. (2018), investments in formal education, healthcare services, job training, adult learning, and migration enhance human capabilities, making them key pathways

for advancing human capital development. Formal education may be the most crucial pathway for enhancing human capabilities. It is the type of education provided in primary, secondary, and higher education institutions. These organizations provide full-time educational courses to their recipients. Nonetheless, many higher education institutions offer part-time, evening, or sandwich causes for adults who are unable to gain admission into full-time programs or who need to balance work with their studies. A key role of education in economic growth and development is generating skilled human resources for different sectors of the economy. In addition to executing this quantitative role, formal educational institutions also teach suitable skills, knowledge, and attitudes to their students (Obananya, 2022).

These abilities, insights, and perspectives help them manage the challenges of their roles. This is referred to as the qualitative aspect of education. Employers of labor build upon the skills and knowledge acquired through formal education with on-the-job training. Education enhances labor mobility and fosters technological advancement via science and technology education. Education enhances workers' productivity by enabling them to acquire skills and knowledge. Providing health services and facilities to individuals in a community is another method of enhancing human capital. Health care services enhance life expectancy, allowing workers to contribute to national development for an extended period until retirement age, ensuring that the resources invested in them are not wasted due to early mortality. According to Salisu et. al. (2924) they argued that “as transparency is a yardstick that shows the cost in most agencies, the cost shows records of activities and also explains them in detail, showing accountability for money spent”.

Health services enhance the vitality and resilience of individuals, ensuring they maintain their well-being for effective work. Employer-organized on-the-job training programs continue to be an essential method for cultivating human capital. Regardless of the skills, knowledge, and attitudes imparted to individuals through formal education, practical experience gained from on-the-job training will continue to address certain deficiencies in human capital growth. Employers often encounter opportunities to provide on-the-job training for employees, either inside or outside the company's facilities (Scott, 2014). On-the-job training can become essential when employees are elevated, when they take on new duties, when the organization observes a decrease in productivity, when specialization among workers

is required, or when they need further skills and knowledge to meet job demands. Programs in adult education, such as adult literacy initiatives, agricultural extension services, and mobilization/enlightenment activities, enhance human capabilities. Skills in numeracy and literacy developed through adult education programs can enhance the abilities of individuals engaged in productive work.

Federal government and human capital development: This part emphasizes the federal government's involvement in human capital development through the previously mentioned means – formal education, health services and facilities, workplace training, adult education, and assistance for migration. Additional policies and programs at this level of government that have promoted human capital development are also taken into account.

Policy on formal education: The national policy on education, initially released in 1977 and updated in 1981, 1998, and 2004, reflects the goals of the Nigerian government regarding education. The National Policy on Education, NPE (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2004) comprises 13 sections, which are: Philosophy and Objectives of Education in Nigeria; Early Childhood/Pre-Primary Education; Basic Education; Primary Education; Secondary Education; Mass Literacy, Adult and Non-Formal Education; Science, Technical and Vocational Education; Tertiary Education; Open and Distance Education; Special Education; Educational Services; Planning, Administration, and Supervision of Education; and Educational Financing. Primary, secondary, and tertiary education all contribute to the growth of human capital.

Primary education serves as the basis for the other two tiers. Several objectives of primary education as outlined in the NPE include: fostering enduring literacy and numeracy, along with effective communication skills; offering the child chances to cultivate manipulative skills necessary for functioning competently in society according to the child's abilities; and equipping the child with fundamental tools for future educational progress, encompassing readiness for local trades and crafts. Primary schools generate literate individuals lacking skills who may participate in productive work later on.

Employment policies advancing human capital development: Employment policies are essential for organizational development since they create a structure for overseeing staff, promoting a positive work atmosphere, and maintaining legal adherence. These policies affect several dimensions of an organization (Berisha, et al., 2015), such as hiring, training, performance evaluation, pay, and dismissal, which ultimately shape employee morale, efficiency, and the organization's overall success.

This indicates that individuals currently employed need retraining, reorientation, or adjustment to address the new challenges. Therefore, unique human abilities can be gained and enhanced through education, training, health initiatives, and investment in various social services that affect an individual's productive capabilities (Adamu, 2013). Human capital development, also known as human capital formation, pertains to the process of obtaining and enhancing the quantity of individuals possessing the skills, education, and experience essential for a country's sustainable growth and development. The economic advantages of developing human capital come from enhancing productivity by bettering nutrition, health, education, and other social indicators through suitable and effective investments. (Okojie, 2015) asserts that human capital formation relates to investing in individuals and their growth as innovative and productive beings.

It is an ongoing progression from childhood through old age, essential for any community or organization aiming to endure amid the intricate challenges of a changing world. Economists have acknowledged that the advancement of human capital is a crucial requirement for a nation's socio-economic and political change. A significant commitment to the development of human capital is among the widely recognized causal factors contributing to the remarkable economic performance of many developed and newly industrializing nations (Adediji, and Bamidele, 2003; 1995, Barro, 2011). This has been primarily accomplished by enhancing knowledge, skills, and abilities gained through education and training by everyone from these nations. It has been emphasized that variations in the degree of socio-economic development between countries are due more to the quality and quantity of human resources rather than to natural resources, endowments, and the accumulation of physical capital. (Oladeji and Adebayo 2016) assert

that human resources are a crucial factor in the process of growth and deserve attention for their development. Human resources form the fundamental foundation for a nation's wealth. Capital and natural resources serve as passive production factors; it is human beings who actively gather capital, utilize natural resources, create social, economic, and political structures, and advance national progress. Evidently, a nation that fails to cultivate the skills and knowledge of its citizens and to employ them efficiently within the national economy will not be able to advance in any other area.

Goals of national employment policy (NEP): The goal of the National Employment Policy is to create the enabling environment for productive and employment-intensive growth in Nigeria. The goal of achieving full employment and the means of attaining such a lofty goal constitutes policy challenges. Nigeria has ratified ILO Convention No. 122 on Employment Policy, which stipulates that, “each Member shall declare and pursue, as a major goal, an active policy designed to promote full, productive and freely chosen employment.”

However, decent employment remains one of the unmet socio-economic needs in Nigeria. Thus, the goal of the National Employment Policy is to ensure a job-rich and inclusive economic growth in Nigeria. This can be accomplished through a combination of wage employment and self-employment. Focus on an employment-centered economic growth will create decent and sustainable employment opportunities, reduce poverty and expand the country's workforce, with improved quality of life and social wellbeing for all. As a macroeconomic challenge, employment policy recommends a multi-pronged approach to the generation of sufficient job opportunities from all sectors of the economy.

Employment policy: The objectives of the Employment Policy are to:

- a) Promote the goal of full employment as a priority in national, economic and social policy, and to enable all men and women who are available and willing to work, to attain secured and sustainable livelihood through full productive and freely chosen employment and work.

- b) Provide the fullest possible opportunity to each worker to qualify for and to use his/her skills and endowments in a job for which he/she is well suited, irrespective of race, sex, religion , political opinion, physical disabilities, national extraction, ethnic or social origin.
- c) Stimulate economic growth and development, eradicate poverty, and improve the levels of living by minimizing the rates of unemployment and underemployment, optimizing the utilization of labour and human resources and protecting areas in which Nigeria is well endowed. Furthermore, to promote the development of relevant manpower/human resources that will continually meet the needs of the nation.
- d) Highlight the multi-sectorial character of employment generation and the collective responsibility of key stakeholders through harmonized efforts toward achieving this goal.
- e) Design strategies that will promote skills and competencies for those in the formal and informal sector especially in rural areas.

Principles of the national employment policy

The National Employment Policy will be coordinated and implemented within the framework of national economic and social policy. In this regard, this Policy will be consistent with the overall development strategies of Nigeria as outlined in the National Rolling and Perspective Plans. The Government policy on employment generation, emphasises the provision of a favourable environment for private investment and job creation. These relate to the stabilization of the economy by checking inflation, a simple exchange rate determined by the market, a liberalised trade regime, encouraging savings and productivity, privatization and stimulation of investment, in order to accelerate economic recovery, growth and accelerated job creation. The government will endeavour to maintain stable and favourable macro-economic policies, invest in human resources and provide basic infrastructure, and provide appropriate incentives to promote the private sector as the main engine of economic growth and job creation in Nigeria. It will also guarantee security of persons and property. In addition, the Government will continually

build the capacities of relevant institutions charged with job creation to enable them play effectively both direct and catalytic roles.

It is the private sector therefore, which should play the leading role of investing in the productive enterprise that provide increased employment and generate incomes. This calls for national promotion of an “enterprises culture” which will induce self-reliance, risk taking, and a national environment that rewards effort and initiative. Individuals, groups, and the community at large, in line with decentralization and participatory development, also have important responsibility for employment creation. Consequently, individuals and groups should be ready to create their own jobs. There will be the need to move from a culture of “job seekers” to “job creators” and self-employment.

Empirical Framework

Ugoji (2012) carried out a study on how human capital development influences organizational performance. The research utilized secondary data. Four hypotheses were created to examine the effect of all independent variables on overall Organizational Performance. The findings indicate that the enhancement of human capital significantly positively influences organizational performance. A report was presented detailing the effects of investments in human capital development on company productivity and various performance metrics through a meta-analysis. The research shows a distinct conclusion that spending on training positively and significantly affects company performance metrics.

However, prior insights into how human capital development impacts organizational outcomes by examining findings from earlier research that has explored the connection between training, human resources, performance, and financial results (Ugoji, 2012). Findings from a meta-analysis of 67 studies indicates that human capital development is positively associated with human capital development outcomes and organizational performance, but shows a very weak connection to financial outcomes. Moreover, the development of human capital seems to correlate more significantly with organizational outcomes when aligned with essential contextual elements like

organizational capital intensity and business strategy, reinforcing the contingency viewpoint.

The research utilized both qualitative and quantitative data analysis, employing descriptive and inferential statistics. The population of the study consisted of the complete staff of the 25 commercial public corporations in Nigeria as of 2007, and 320 questionnaires were distributed. The research discovered that productivity is indeed a key factor in motivating investment in human capital development progress regarding employee efficiency. The study presents an overview of the existing evidence regarding this relationship and proposes recommendations for additional research. They thoroughly examined the literature regarding research results from studies that attempted to measure and comprehend the influence of training on employee productivity in different sectors. The main emphasis of their review was on training methods and employee productivity and the connection between them. The results of their research differed, according to (Udeorah et al. 2017). Although certain studies indicated a positive link between training and employee productivity, others found a negative correlation, while some revealed no association at all. Additional research has also examined whether there is a connection between skills and various organizational outcomes.

Haskel, (2015) discovered that elevated skill (qualification) levels bolster innovation and more advanced production methods, correlating with the manufacture of superior quality products. Green, Mayhew, and Molloy, (2013) also discovered a robust connection between various levels of workforce skills in the UK and product sophistication. Colombo, (2014) identified links between greater training and elevated labor productivity in various UK sectors; while Adeniji, (2014) concluded that boosting training investment lowers the likelihood of business closure. Grip, (2013) discovered that training agents considerably impacted the productivity of employees within the organization. Similarly, Nwachukwu, (2014) believes that the combined implementation of training and innovation seems to boost labor productivity growth. Harel, (2013) explores whether employee training impacts job performance, behavior, attitudes, skills, knowledge, and the attainment of business goals in Nigeria. The sample size was established based on three categories of personnel: general staff, senior staff, and

management staff. He employs chi-square to evaluate the proposed hypothesis. He demonstrates that effective training results in the development of skills and knowledge necessary for employees to perform well in their roles.

His findings indicate that training significantly enhances employee performance and diminishes job-related hazards in achieving corporate goals. A recent investigation in the same field also offers valuable insights regarding the impact of heterogeneity on firm performance (Hassan, 2022). Without a doubt, heterogeneity (as a type of human capital) can be a crucial factor in the development and improvement of human capital, as it fosters greater creativity and innovation within organizations for long-term survival in their global and international markets (Grossman, 2010). Consequently, the abilities of Technology Media and Telecommunication (TMT) are bolstered by input-oriented international human capital, transformational human capital, and output-oriented international human capital (Huang et al., 2012). Nonetheless, some contend that the link between innovative human resource practices (despite the absence of direct human capital practices) and organizational performance might be characterized as ‘non-linear’ (Becker & Barry, 1996). Oribabor (2010) argued that the goal of human capital development is to enhance competencies like technical, human, conceptual, and managerial skills to promote the growth of individuals and organizations.

Human beings are inherently dynamic, and the demand to stay current and pertinent in all areas of human activities necessitates staff development to remain aligned with contemporary events and practices. Adeniyi (2019) has captured the interest of everyone regarding the immense importance of developing human capital. It provides a way to gain additional and fresh knowledge while enhancing the skills and methods needed for effective functioning. Researchers, specialists, social scientists, and educational leaders now acknowledge that training is clearly essential not only for individual growth but also to enhance the productivity of employees. Training is not persuading or convincing individuals to act as desired but instead establishing organizational environments that will encourage staff to aim for improved performance. Oladeji (2015) explored the link between human capital (via education and efficient health care services).

To emphasize its internal contributions to the growth process (Romer, 1996, 1990; Lucas, 1998) asserted that all developing nations were encouraged to focus on human capital development, in which Nigeria also took part. The Nigerian government not only began training individuals in schools but also developed educational policies concerning primary, secondary, and tertiary institutions to enhance the effectiveness of education in Nigeria. Nigeria has made significant progress in her development planning endeavors. A key element of the development planning process is the impact on human capacity development via education and training. Employee performance is a crucial element that supports organizational development and longevity, particularly influenced by the incentive system utilized within a company (Ntagu & Onuorah, 2020). In recent decades, the global business landscape has experienced a significant change. The world has gotten smaller, not in size, but in communication, competition, and economics because of globalization.

Management specialists contend that a key role of a manager is to nurture individuals and to guide, motivate, and educate subordinates for maximum effectiveness. According to Stahl (2016), training equips employees for specific roles that are distinctive to the public sector. Okoh (2019) highlighted the significance of developing human capital: An organization focused on results must hire and train specialized staff. The upcoming public service will demand that professionals with the necessary skills and expertise receive ongoing training to adapt to the constantly evolving public sector.

Training must be integrated into a holistic educational planning program because, among all personnel management aspects, training is arguably the most crucial for us in Nigeria. Thirty years later, following pre-colonial public sector reforms regarding human capital development policies in Nigeria, a new reform initiative (the 1988 civil reforms) highlighted mandatory and regular training as a crucial aspect of improving employee performance in the Nigerian Public Sector. A core question is “what occurred regarding this significant topic from 1974 to 1988?” The response appears clear. Hardly anything has been accomplished. Even though management experts and the government acknowledge the significance of training in white papers addressing various reforms in Nigeria, the reality of Human capital development in the Nigerian public

service has often been characterized by deception and wastefulness (Ewuim & Onuorah, 2020). It is regrettable that the majority of training programs initiated at different government levels in Nigeria have failed to yield the expected outcomes. Despite the presence of human capital development policy, it appears to have not been very successful lately, as it does not significantly result in effective organizational growth Obananya, (2022). The execution of human capital development in various organizations is marked by issues such as the absence of strategic alignment of compensation and reward systems, along with selection based on merit. Likewise, the organization's mission regarding human capital development strategy lacks clear definition, and for any organization lacking strategic coherence, executing the human capital development policy will remain unattainable

Methodology

This paper relied on secondary sources of data. Data were gathered by the researcher through an extensive and in-depth review of relevant literatures on Nigeria's underdevelopment. The sources of the literatures were thoroughly evaluated and analyzed.

Theoretical Framework

Institutional Theory

Institutional theory: this theory comes from management and organizational studies, explores how formal and informal regulations, norms, and frameworks affect the actions and results of organizations (Scott, 2014). The theory originates from the contributions of academics like Max Weber, who emphasized the importance of formal organizations and bureaucratic systems in contemporary society (Weber, 1947). Nonetheless, it was the groundbreaking research of Meyer and Rowan (1977) that established the basis for contemporary institutional theory. They claimed that organizations implement structures and practices not merely for their efficiency but also to secure legitimacy and approval from outside stakeholders, such as governments, customers, and society at large. Institutional theory's fundamental assumptions center on the notion that organizations are

situated within institutional environments defined by norms, values, and regulatory structures (Scott, 2014).

Organizations adapt to these institutional pressures to achieve legitimacy and preserve social approval, even if such practices may not be the most efficient or logical when viewed solely from an economic standpoint. Institutional Theory asserts that institutions are dynamic and develop over time, shaped by transformations in societal values, technological progress, and alterations in political and economic environments. Critics of Institutional Theory contend that it often neglects the agency and independence of organizations, depicting them as mere passive entities molded entirely by external influences (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983). Moreover, certain academics argue that Institutional Theory overlooks the influence of power relations and conflicts in driving institutional change, prioritizing consensus and conformity instead (Scott, 2014).

Moreover, critics highlight that Institutional Theory frequently fails to clearly articulate the mechanisms by which institutional pressures affect organizational behavior, resulting in ambiguous and circular explanations. Nonetheless, Institutional Theory provides important perspectives on how government policies impact organizational behavior and outcomes, especially regarding Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in the Abuja metropolis. Government strategies, including regulatory structures, tax policies, and economic motivations, signify institutional pressures that affect the actions and effectiveness of SMEs (North, 1990). For instance, SMEs might adhere to regulatory standards and tax policies to establish legitimacy and prevent sanctions or penalties

Conclusion

The growth of organizations in Nigeria relies heavily on developing human capital and implementing suitable employment policies. Through prioritizing employee development, enforcing equitable labor practices, and cultivating a supportive work atmosphere, companies can boost their productivity, creativity, and overall competitiveness over time. Additionally, tackling issues in the education system and fostering cooperation among stakeholders are vital for establishing a solid groundwork for human capital development in Nigeria.

Considering the breadth of Nigeria's employment policy and its human capital growth, the nation should serve as Africa's entry point for development to foster domestic and foreign investments, leading to expected national savings. Thus, to fulfill this crucial leadership role, Nigeria's organizations must progress in the correct direction towards sustainable growth and development. To accomplish this, the foundation of employment policy, based on the enhancement of human capital, needs to be promoted; hence, Nigeria's primary policy challenge is to implement concrete measures to address human capital shortcomings and take the lead in Africa by strategically investing resources in the training of its workforce. The result of all this for Nigeria is that it will now transform into a human capital training center in Africa.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from the study, the researcher concluded that developing human capital is a crucial element in ensuring effective service delivery within an organization, and there exists a notably positive relationship between the factors of human capital development and the employment policy at the Edo State Universal Basic Education Board. In light of the study's findings, the following recommendations are made to enhance human capital development within organizations for better service delivery.

1. Management of Edo State Universal Basic Education Board should allocate more resources for human capital development programmes that are capable of raising the skills, morale and performance of employee that would guarantee quality service delivery.
2. The organization should encourage on-the-job training, and further education that employees require to improve their performance and capabilities, which consequently will increase effective service delivery in terms of quantity of work produce.
3. Organizational leaders in Nigeria should stimulate and foster a culture that increases employees productivity
4. Nigerian government should take responsibility for providing security of lives and properties as enshrined in section 14(2b) of the 1999 constitution as amended.

5. The management of organization should institute merit award for employees at various levels (Junior, middle and senior cadre) so as to stimulate productivity competition.

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